

Development of a Platform-independent Modeling Language for Robotics Process Automation

Master in Business Informatics

Submitted by:

Nicolas Sahli
Route Saint-Nicolas-de-Flüe
1700 Fribourg

Supervisor:

Prof. Dr. Hans-Georg Fill

Digitalization and Information Systems Group

Department of Informatics

University of Fribourg

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Abstract

In this work, an approach to platform-independent modeling of Robotics Process Automation (RPA) processes is developed. The starting point is a modeling language that is created within ADOxx. With this modeling language, it is possible to develop RPA process models independently from any software provider. The goal is then to be able to transfer a created model into a desired RPA software such as UiPath or Blue Prism. To achieve this, a script is developed which translates an ADOxx process model into a usable format for either RPA solution. The final solution consists of a desktop application in which an ADOxx model can be translated into either a UiPath or a Blue Prism process model. From there, further developments can be made in Blue Prism or UiPath to fully automate the process. The work successfully demonstrates how RPA processes can be modeled in a platform-independent way and used in different RPA environments. This represents an important step towards a more flexible and efficient use of RPA in different software environments. However, the prototype consists only of the most important and basic RPA actions. Therefore, more extensions and optimization of the developed prototype are necessary in order to make the product usable in real scenarios.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

New technological possibilities offer companies the potential not only to achieve efficiency gains but also to fundamentally rethink and optimize many of their business processes. In this sector, robotic process automation (RPA) has been growing constantly in recent years. Hence, many new but also many established software companies offer promising RPA solutions. The automation of repetitive tasks by software robots offers considerable potential for reducing costs and increasing productivity. However, the large number of RPA software providers, each having its own modeling environment, can propose challenges in certain scenarios. To solve such challenges, this thesis is dedicated to exploring a new way of modeling RPA processes in a platform-independent way and therefore enabling companies to be more flexible and efficient in their use of different RPA software.

1.1 Background and Motivation

In the era of digitalization and automation, the business world is becoming more complex day by day. Companies face the constant need to gain efficiency, in order to keep costs low and output high. For this, optimizing processes are key to remain competitive and meet increasing demands. In this context, robotic process automation (RPA) has gained importance as a technology. RPA enables companies to make their business processes more efficient and cost-effective. This is especially interesting for companies, as RPA is one of the most cost-effective and efficient options for automating processes (Davenport & Ronanki, 2018). Additionally, the RPA software market is growing strongly and automation through robotics has become increasingly relevant in recent years (Miers et al., 2019). This recent growth means that each company can easily access and use an RPA software in order to gain efficiencies in many sectors.

However, in the world of robotic process automation, there is a remarkable variety of RPA software and tools available. At the same time, each organization uses one or multiple solutions to automate its business processes. These are either from established vendors or emerging technology companies that offer a wide range of features and solutions tailored to the diverse needs

of organizations (Enríquez et al., 2020). Nowadays there are over 60 different software providers that offer robotics process automation. Whereas only 18 of them are widely used (Afriliana & Ramadhan, 2022). Such a wide range of possibilities makes it difficult for a company to find the perfect RPA software for its purposes. Additionally, a company that already uses an RPA solution always has the possibility to switch provider. However, such a switch can be very money and time-intensive.

Therefore, the motivation for this research arises from the need to develop a modeling language for RPA processes that is platform-independent and can be applied to different RPA software providers. Such a modeling language would offer several advantages to organizations in terms of dependency on a single RPA software: A modeling language of this kind allows a company to use different RPA solutions and still have uniformly modeled processes. For example, if a company wants to use different RPA software in different areas of the company, the basic process can still be modeled in this uniform modeling language. Only in the second step would the process be transferred to the selected RPA software. This allows a company-wide uniform modeling of the processes and at the same time the flexibility to use different RPA software. Another advantage is that this modeling language allows a much easier switch between different providers of RPA software. If a company decides to switch from one RPA software provider to another, not all existing processes need to be modeled from scratch. Instead, they can simply be transferred from the base model to the new RPA software and thus be implemented much more efficiently in the new tool. Hence, the cost and time barrier of switching RPA software would be much lower. Overall, the main motivation of this thesis is to create a solution that allows users to easily develop RPA processes, without being tied to one single software provider. Such a modeling language could enable a simple and uniform way of modeling processes that can be applied to any desired RPA software. Hence, said solution could create the bridge for the two above-explained scenarios.

1.2 Objectives and Research Questions

The present research questions address three key dimensions: Conceptual understanding (RQ 1), technical implementation of a modeling language (RQ 2), and applicability of platform independence (RQ 3). In doing so, it highlights which key elements are important for the representation of RPA processes in modeling languages, how these can be technically implemented, and to what extent the resulting modeling language is platform-independent and applicable on different RPA platforms.

1. Research Question (RQ 1):

What key elements and concepts are necessary to represent RPA processes in a modeling language?

2. Research Question (RQ 2):

How can a modeling language that represents RPA processes be technically implemented?

3. Research Question (RQ 3):

To what extent is the developed modeling language platform-independent, and how efficiently can it be applied to different RPA platforms?

Through these questions, a bridge is built between conceptual considerations, technical implementation, and practical application. They provide a structured framework for the various phases of the work and help to drive the research forward in a targeted manner.

1.3 Structure of the Work

This thesis is divided into six main chapters. Within these chapters, the reader is guided through the theoretical, practical, and analytical aspects of developing a platform-independent RPA modeling language. In the first chapter the topic of the thesis is introduced by explaining the background and motivation for the development of a platform-independent RPA solution. Then in a second chapter the methodological approach used in this thesis is explained. These two chapters are followed by the main part of the thesis which takes place in the chapters three, four and five.

In Chapter 3, the examination of some theoretical background lays the foundation for the research. First, robotic process automation (RPA) is introduced and then it is analyzed whether approaches to platform-independent process modeling exist in the RPA landscape. Tools such as the process design document, Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) models, Visio flowcharts, and process mining techniques are inspected. Each of these approaches is analyzed in order to determine if platform independence has been reached. Finally, the chapter concludes with an outlook on the possibilities for creating a universal RPA modeling language that can be applied to various existing RPA providers.

Chapter 4 focuses on the planning and specification of the prototype. In this phase, first all the requirements and functionalities for the prototype that is to be developed are specified. In the second part the tools and methods used for the development of the prototype are defined. Various methods from low-fidelity prototypes to more sophisticated methods are covered. Each method having its own purpose ensuring that the final prototype meets the objectives set. These include Wireframes, Storyboards, ADOxx, two RPA software providers, and tools for the implementation of a coded prototype.

In Chapter 5, the design and development of the prototype takes place. It begins with two low-fidelity prototypes in order to get a visual representation of the entire project, especially the modeling language. In a further section, the core elements of RPA processes in Blue Prism and UiPath are examined. These learnings are then used in the implementation of the RPA modeling language in ADOxx. In the next step, scripts are created to integrate the ADOxx process models in both Blue Prism and UiPath. Finally, the finished prototype is tested, and its results are evaluated.

To conclude the thesis in Chapter 6, the results of the entire prototype are summarized and discussed. The chapter also addresses the various challenges and limitations encountered during the research and development of the prototype. Finally, recommendations for future work and the implications of a platform-independent RPA modeling language are discussed.

Chapter 2

Methodology

In the complex landscape of RPA modeling, it is crucial to choose a methodology that allows to gain deep insights into the specific requirements in this field. It is key to understand how RPA software works and how it is applied, in order to develop a new RPA modeling language. Therefore, this research combines qualitative and practical research approaches, with the goal of laying a good theoretical foundation for an optimal practical implementation.

In the theoretical part, a systematic literature review and internet research is conducted to gain a comprehensive overview of existing approaches in the area of platform-independent modeling for RPA. This analysis and additional examination of multiple RPA software providers give the necessary understanding of process modeling in RPA. This overview is then used to set up requirements and best practices, in order to create a platform-independent RPA modeling language. Such a systematic approach ensures that the literature search is comprehensive and reproducible (Keele, 2007).

Subsequently, in the practical part of the thesis, a prototyping approach is followed. The goal is to develop and test a modeling prototype for RPA processes based on the knowledge gained through the literature review. In this way, the theoretical findings can be directly put into practice and tested for their applicability. This prototype is implemented according to the principles of Arnowitz, J., Arent, M., & Berger, N. which they describe in their book “Effective prototyping for software makers”. The book is used as a main guideline in the prototype development process. From planning and setting up requirements to the development of low-fidelity prototypes and then finally the development of the final prototype.

Taken together, both the theoretical and practical methodological approaches enable a broad and variable overview of the entire work. The combination of a theoretical foundation with the understanding of RPA itself and the clear path to the practical implementation of a prototype make up a great mix for this thesis.

Chapter 3

Theoretical Background

This chapter lays the theoretical foundation for the implementation of a platform-independent Robotics Process Automation (RPA) modeling language. Firstly, an introduction to RPA and the application of this technology is given. Followed by an in-depth analysis of existing approaches for a platform-independent RPA solution. Including RPA-specific solutions such as the Process Design Document and widely known tools such as Microsoft Visio or BPMN. Lastly, the modern approach of process mining is explored. The goal of this analysis is to examine the potential of those solutions in relation to platform-independent modeling of RPA processes. The main question is whether there already exists a fully functional solution on the market and if not, how mature these approaches are. Learnings from this chapter will then contribute to the development of a new platform-independent RPA modeling language in the practical part of the thesis. Hence, this theoretical chapter forms an important basis for the further work in this thesis. The information contained in this chapter, unless otherwise referenced, is based on practical experience as RPA developer. In addition, many of the explanations are taken from the documentation of various RPA software providers and relevant tools such as Visio and Camunda.

3.1 Introduction to Robotics Process Automation

The development of Robotic process automation began with the emergence of automation technologies in the business world. In situations where human labor or the development and integration of business process management systems (BPMS) are too costly or cannot be justified by business requirements, RPA serves as a transitional element between human labor and business process automation (Hofmann et al., 2020). One example for this are simple and repetitive tasks, where a clerk has to take information from an Excel sheet and type it into the software of the company. Now instead of paying for a full-time position, this process could simply be automated. In the earliest days, companies relied on early automation tools and macros to simplify such repetitive tasks and optimize workflows. These basic tools paved the way for the idea of software robots that could mimic human actions and perform routine processes (Antwiadjei, 2021). Typically, these were very simple and repetitive tasks, such as copying data from one spreadsheet to another.

Nowadays, RPA automates repetitive and often tedious tasks that require little mental effort, freeing up human workers for activities that require creative thinking, intellectual judgment, or social skills (Hofmann et al., 2020). For example, software robots can assist with preparatory work such as collecting data, which is later used for further processing by the employee. This means that often the automation of a process through RPA is not based on the principle of separating and isolating humans and robots but aims to enable efficient interaction between them. In such a way that each of them, the robot and the human, performs the tasks for which they are best suited. Meaning RPA is often not used to completely replace the human in their workplace but to assist with certain tasks.

The efficiency and reliability of such automation paved the way for the further evolution and popularity of RPA. This increase in efficiency enables RPA to improve process key performance indicators, without changing the process itself (Hofmann et al., 2020). But how exactly does RPA work, and why does the process itself need no changes when using software robots?

Software robots can perform the exact same steps that a human would perform on the graphical user interface. This interaction with software robots via the user interface is also referred to as surface automation. This surface automation is a different approach compared to most other used process automation solutions. Instead of constructing new APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) or entire software in order to automate a process, with RPA, no new solutions have to be developed. All the existing tools and software can be used as before, with the sole difference being that a software robot, instead of a human, accesses them via the user interface. This interaction with the user interfaces of various programs has significant advantages. For example, a robot is able to operate a wide variety of applications within a process without requiring changes to the existing infrastructure. This can be very time-saving if existing applications do not have to be modified for automation.

A software robot works by being programmed with a specific process logic. This means that it follows and executes predefined steps, such as clicking on certain buttons or writing into a textbox on the user interface. Each of these actions corresponds exactly to what a human would do on a computer. Except that the robot cannot think for itself; it simply carries out the tasks assigned to it in a precise and fast manner. Therefore, it is important to develop a robust and error-free process logic. The software robot then executes these process steps on a virtual desktop. As virtual desktops are used in robotics processes, multiple robots can work simultaneously on multiple virtual machines. Making the process even faster, as more workload can be done in less time.

Finally, RPA software is available in various forms and from numerous providers. Each software has its own strengths and special features but basically works according to similar principles. A later chapter will go into more detail on how two of these RPA solutions work. In the existence of such a wide variety of providers, the question arises as to whether there are platform-independent

solutions that enable the integration of multiple different RPA software. Given the large number of providers and solutions, it would be a great advantage if a standardized platform could seamlessly connect these different systems. The next chapter examines what platform independence is and whether there are already existing approaches that meet this challenge in the RPA landscape.

3.2 Existing Approaches for Platform-independent RPA Modeling

As part of this section, it is analyzed whether there is a software or tool that can be used to model RPA processes and then import these models into different RPA software. This means that said software would have to be platform-independent. In relation to RPA, platform independence means that the software makes it possible to model a process once and then implement this process in several different RPA platforms without the need for adaptations or new developments. In practice, this would mean that a company, regardless of which RPA software it uses, can use the same process models in different RPA software without having to adapt them again. This means it would need to offer a uniform modeling language that is compatible with various RPA solutions, or at least offers a way to integrate models into it.

However, a look at conventional methods shows that the modeling of processes in RPA is traditionally carried out directly in the respective software and not in a third-party tool. Nevertheless, these implementations often rely on documentation such as the process design documents (PDD) or instructional videos. Such conventional methodology ensures a close link between the theoretical planning and the practical implementation of RPA processes. In addition to this conventional approach, however, there are alternative methods that are used in practice for modeling RPA processes. These modeling approaches include BPMN for process orchestration and the representation of processes using flowcharts in tools such as Microsoft Visio. Furthermore, process mining represents the most modern way of process modeling by using data analytical methods to automatically create process models. This raises the question of whether one of these tools enables the implementation of platform-independent RPA models that can then be imported into multiple RPA software. Overall, this chapter provides an analysis of the modeling methods mentioned, focusing in particular on the question of whether one or multiple methods already allow platform-independent modeling of RPA processes.

3.2.1 Process Design Documents

A Process Design Document (PDD) is a detailed document that describes the processes intended for automation. It is created after the process has been analyzed by subject matter experts and serves as a guide for the development of RPA solutions. The PDD defines each step of the process, identifies automation possibilities, and documents everything necessary for end users and developers (Vinocha, n.d.). Simply explained, the PDD is a Word document in which the process

is documented step by step in detail. For example, every single action, such as clicks or keystrokes are shown with a picture and description. Figure 3.1 shows three steps of such a PDD for a login process. For each individual step, there is a row with a screenshot and an explanation of what exactly is being done. Based on these images and descriptions, the developer can then implement the process in the RPA software.

Step	Description	Additional Info	Image
1.	Type Username	<i>Use Test User for developing purpose</i>	
2.	Type Password	<i>Password is saved in KeePass</i>	
3.	Press Login Button		

Figure 3.1: PDD for a Login Process

Although the Process Design Document is not a modeling language per se, it plays an important role in the context of RPA process documentation, as it is recognized as best practice in the industry (Cullen, n.d.). A broad internet search shows that all market leaders in the field of robotic process automation recommend the use of a Process Design Document for the development of RPA processes. In addition, these providers often provide their own guidelines and templates to facilitate and standardize the creation of PDDs.

It can therefore be concluded that the PDD is a platform-independent tool. This conclusion is based on the fact that the recommendation to use a PDD is consistent across different RPA

platforms, regardless of the specific technological characteristics or functionalities of the individual tools. The provided guidelines and templates for the creation of PDDs by different providers additionally underline its universal character and its suitability as a standardized instrument in RPA process development. It can thus be argued that the PDD plays a central, cross-platform role in the conception and planning of automation projects. However, the PDD is not part of the implementation itself in the RPA software. As it only serves as guidance and documentation in the development of an RPA process. There is no way of translating a PDD into an RPA software without having to model and implement the entire process step by step. But this means that the Process Design Document offers the potential to serve as the basis for the development of a process modeling language that could be applied to various RPA software providers across platforms - similar to the PDD itself. In summary, for now the PDD is used as a documentation tool only and does not provide any integration into any RPA software itself. This raises the question if there are approaches that offer more integration into RPA software. One such approach could be the use of BPMN, which is explored in the following section.

3.2.2 Business Process Model and Notation

BPMN, which stands for Business Process Model and Notation, is a standard for business process modeling. BPMN enables a graphical representation of business processes in the form of a business process diagram. It was developed to create a universally understandable and common notation that can be understood by all business users. These include business analysts who draft the initial processes, the technical developers implementing the technology, and the business people who will manage and monitor the processes. Serving a wide range of purposes, BPMN is largely used for documenting processes, executing business processes, and simulating processes. It enables businesses to visualize their internal procedures clearly and systematically. Thus, helping to find and implement improvements and enhancements in each process. Furthermore, BPMN models can act as a common language, allowing for better communication across different business users and stakeholders. Since its first version in 2004, BPMN has undergone several upgrades and changes, with a significant one being BPMN 2.0. This version, for example, introduced the execution of semantics for BPMN elements and introduced choreography for better modeling interactions between participants. Overall, BPMN stands in a leading position in the area of business processes and workflow modeling, especially with its capability of creating accurate representations of processes and therefore aiding business process improvements (Chinosi & Trombetta, 2012).

BPMN models can be implemented in various tools. A particularly outstanding and widely used tool for this purpose is Camunda. With Camunda, BPMN models can not only be created but also simulated, optimized, and converted into real workflow applications. Furthermore, it can be integrated with other software and platforms, such as for robotic process automation. This integration allows for the automation and execution of processes based on BPMN models (Chiş, 2020).

Camunda takes a strategic lifecycle approach to dealing with RPA bots. This approach called the “RPA Modernization Journey”, consists of three steps. First, Camunda enables companies to gain insight into, monitor, and analyze the activities of their RPA bots through a process automation platform. Next, through BPMN and Decision Model and Notation (DMN) standards, RPA bots are integrated into existing process flows so they can be seamlessly coordinated with other systems. Finally, Camunda aims to drive modernization through process orchestration, gradually replacing RPA bots with more advanced technologies such as APIs or microservices (Camunda, n.d.-c).

This is how Camunda enables the easy integration of external systems into BPMN processes: With a so-called out-of-the-box connector, an external system, in this case, an RPA software, can be built into the BPMN. Connectors for various RPA platforms, including UiPath, Blue Prism, and Automation Anywhere, are already available (Camunda, n.d.-a). Essentially, a connector acts as a bridge between the BPMN diagram and an external service. Through the Web Modeler, users can simply drag and drop the connector into their diagram. After integration into the process flow, the connector is configured. During this process, users enter specific details such as API keys and endpoints to ensure proper communication with the external system. The connector is then always triggered as soon as the specific block in the BPMN process is executed (Camunda, n.d.-b). Through such connectors, multiple different tasks and processes can now be integrated and orchestrated within a single BPMN process. For example, automated tasks that are executed by RPA software (Johnston, 2023).

Figure 3.2: BPMN Process with an RPA Bot Connector

The BPMN process presented in Figure 3.2 is about requesting a budget. The process starts with a manual step in which a budget is requested. After the request is made, a check is made to see if the amount requested is less than 100. If it is, an RPA process is automatically activated whose task is to approve the budget, if possible. However, if the RPA bot encounters problems or is unable to successfully complete the request, the process is redirected to an employee. This person then takes over the manual review and, if necessary, approval of the requested budget.

The detailed subpage for the block named RPA Bot is shown in Figure 3.3 below. It illustrates the concrete process of connecting to a UiPath robot. As soon as this robot is triggered, it attempts to execute the assigned task. A fault tolerance has been built in: if the bot unsuccessfully executes the task more than twice, a notification is automatically generated. This notification, already mentioned above and shown in Figure 3.2, then informs the responsible employee about the problem. This approach ensures that potential problems or obstacles in the automated process execution are detected early and forwarded to a human for resolution. This ensures a combination of automated efficiency and human problem handling all in one process.

Figure 3.3: BPMN Model Triggering an RPA Bot

Process orchestration with Camunda and BPMN modeling offers a wide range of benefits. First, it allows modeling a process in Camunda, in which one or multiple robots can then be integrated and triggered. This integration even allows robots from different RPA software providers to be included into a single Camunda process, which provides great flexibility and compatibility. This enables the possibility of collaboration between different IT teams, which might use different tools. The ability to link multiple RPA processes within a single BPMN model also allows different workflows to be integrated and merged into one single BPMN process. With this possibility comes the advantage that all these different workflows can be monitored centrally in Camunda, regardless of where and in which tool they are executed. Such a centralized view not only facilitates management but also control over all automated processes. Overall, process orchestration greatly simplifies and optimizes automation, integration, and monitoring in an enterprise (Johnston, 2023).

In conclusion, Camunda provides an efficient and elegant solution for large and modern companies that want to use different RPA software providers in different areas. However, the core problem of platform-independent RPA modeling remains. In practice, this means that an RPA process still needs to be modeled in the original RPA software despite its integration with Camunda. This could be seen as a double layer of process modeling, creating the specific RPA process first and then including it in a BPMN process in Camunda. While Camunda definitely offers advantages in orchestrating and merging different processes, the modeling in the actual RPA software cannot be bypassed. In conclusion, the concept of complete platform independence, where a single tool allows implementation of processes for multiple RPA providers, cannot be

achieved with BPMN and Camunda. As a result, the question comes up if there are tools that offer more complete integration without the need for those additional steps. Such an approach could be offered by Microsoft Visio in combination with Power Automate, which is explored in the next chapter.

3.2.3 Visio Flowcharts

Since the very beginning of electronic data processing, flowcharts have been used to visualize the structural designs of complicated software systems. Based on this flowchart, the programmer would then implement the program in the respective programming language (Ensmenger, 2016). This is exactly how flowcharts can be used in robotics: A selected process is represented by flowcharts that include action specifications, parallel and alternative routing structures, and data streams. These can visualize the behavior of a software robot. Based on this representation, the robot can then be implemented in the desired robotics software (Agostinelli, Marrella, & Mecella, 2020).

Microsoft is taking such an approach with its RPA software Power Automate and the flowchart modeling program Visio. Power Automate allows users to configure their workflow logic in detail. However, if one wants to create a rough sketch of the process logic first, one can use Microsoft Visio directly within Power Automate to create a flowchart (Microsoft, n.d.). The process in Power Automate is simple and efficient. In a first step, the user selects a Visio template in Power Automate. Within this template in Visio, the desired flowchart can then be designed and modeled with BPMN. Once the model is complete, it can be easily exported back to Power Automate. For this, it is essential that the model created is validated first. This means that all BPMN rules in the designed workflow must be correctly followed. Are these given, it is important to assign the individual shapes and blocks of the flowchart to the appropriate actions in Power Automate. This ensures that the entire model is transferred to Power Automate correctly and without loss (Microsoft, n.d.).

Overall, Microsoft provides a convincing approach with Visio. This makes it possible to model a robotics process independently of the RPA software, which can be transferred to the RPA software Power Automate in a later step. However, for Visio to be used as a platform-independent modeling language for RPA, it should be compatible with other RPA software solutions. In reviewing three leading RPA providers on the market - UiPath, Blue Prism, and Automation Anywhere - it turns out that only one offers the ability to import a Visio flowchart (Gartner, 2023). It is UiPath which offers such a feature (UiPath, n.d.-b). For Blue Prism and Automation Anywhere there is currently no built-in option to import Visio flowcharts. However, for UiPath, it is important to emphasize that a Visio model can only be uploaded to the so-called 'Task Capture'. Task Capture is primarily used to identify and document new processes that could be automated. This means that the Visio flowchart cannot be used directly to automate a process in UiPath. An imported Visio

model would serve as documentation and template from which the process can then be developed in UiPath. Nevertheless, this possibility accelerates the process of automation (UiPath, n.d.-c).

There may be several reasons why RPA providers such as Blue Prism or Automation Anywhere do not offer the possibility to import a Visio model. One of them is that RPA providers want to maintain strategic control over the entire process modeling cycle. Such that the commitment of the user to the software is strengthened. If processes could be modeled externally and then imported, it would be much easier for the user to switch RPA providers, as the process could be maintained independently from the used RPA software. By restricting such import options, companies tie customers more closely to their platform, which ultimately strengthens their market position. Another reason could also be of technical origin. If processes are modeled externally, there is a risk that they are not fully compatible with the specific RPA software. This could lead to problems with automation. By modeling within its own platform, the provider can ensure that the processes run optimally and error-free.

In summary, Microsoft's Visio offers a promising approach to RPA modeling, as it is already possible to import a Visio model into one RPA software, and a second one offers a way to use Visio within its software. Especially in terms of a platform-independent modeling language, this is a step in the right direction. Going forward, it could be possible that more RPA providers create plug-ins which allow the import of Visio models as RPA processes. This could be the way for a truly platform-independent solution in RPA modeling. However, it is apparent that RPA software companies have various reasons to not enable the import of externally developed process models. Hence, true platform independence in the RPA landscape has not yet been fully achieved with Visio, as full integration only works with Power Automate. As a result, the search for a platform-independent RPA modeling language remains unresolved. This leads to the most modern approach, process mining, which could possibly bring the solution, and is analyzed in the next chapter.

3.2.4 Process Mining

Having looked at three established approaches that offer partial platform independence, or at least great potential to reach it in RPA modeling, next the focus turns to a more modern approach: process mining. This innovative approach is still relatively new but shows great potential for the future of process automation. Especially the possibility that process mining could offer a great platform-independent solution in the RPA field.

Typically, potential use cases for RPA are identified through a series of discussions with a knowledgeable partner who has insight into the process in question. As discussed, in a first step, the selected process is often visualized using BPMN, a PDD, or any other process modeling tool. During these discussions, the suitability of the process for automation with RPA technologies is

then assessed (Agaton & Swedberg, 2018). However, these methods are time-consuming and therefore quickly reach their scaling limits in organizations with a high number of potential processes (Leno et al., 2021). This is where process mining comes into play.

Process mining is a data-driven technique that traces the flow of business processes using transaction logs from enterprise IT systems. For example, all the logs are collected from the computer of an employee who often performs repetitive work. This method enables the analysis of all activities within the business processes that this person goes through and identifies process patterns. By visualizing the data, analysts can conduct more in-depth investigations, identify deviations from the ideal process, and uncover causes of inefficiencies (Geyer-Klingenberg et al., 2018). Figure 3.4 shows a UML (Unified Modeling Language) sequence diagram of how such a process mining software works.

Figure 3.4: UML Sequence Diagram of Process Mining

Altogether there are three main techniques in the world of process mining. The first one being process discovery. In this technique, a process model is generated from event logs without any prior information. This process model can then be used to identify patterns that could be automated or optimized. A second technique is the conformance check. With this method, an existing process model is compared to the gathered event logs through process mining of the same process. Such comparison can be used to identify differences between the model and actual process execution, providing a quality or performance measure for the process. Finally, as last method comes process enhancement, which aims to optimize a process model based on the real process information from an event log. For example, by analyzing the average waiting times in a process and then find solutions to reduce them. In all these techniques, process diagrams are created that graphically represent the structures and workflows. Which are then often visualized using notations such as BPMN or Petri nets (Van Der Aalst, 2012). All three of these methods can be of

great value in combination with RPA. Not only do they serve to discover new processes that are suitable for automation, but they also make it possible to continuously monitor whether existing RPA-supported processes can be further optimized or expanded.

Innovative approaches such as SmartRPA have already bridged the gap between process mining and RPA and offer a fully automated solution for combining these two technologies. SmartRPA facilitates the automation of routine tasks by recording and processing user interactions on the user interfaces. The initial action logger records every single action done on the user interface during a routine. At the end of a training session, these are merged into a data structure. In the next step, the event abstraction process filters out unimportant events and summarizes recurring ones. This serves as the basis for process discovery, in which the most frequently repeated routines are identified. Finally, SmartRPA generates executable RPA scripts from the data obtained, which instruct software robots to imitate the observed user behavior. This fully integrated approach enables smooth and efficient automation of routine tasks, significantly reducing manual processes (Agostinelli, Lupia, et al., 2020). However, such a process mining approach does not allow the transformation to multiple different RPA solutions yet.

Another approach is offered by the RPA provider UiPath, which has its own process mining tool. In this case, the so-called task mining makes it possible to identify workflows that can be automated in a later step in UiPath itself (UiPath, n.d.-i). However, this method is a specific approach that can exclusively be used with their own RPA software. It would not be possible to use task mining in UiPath and then import the findings into any other RPA software. There are various reasons to why RPA providers are only interested in implementing and allowing their own process mining solution. These can be technical difficulties but also strategic considerations. One of them being the isolation of the software from competitors and thus retaining its clientele. Otherwise, as explained in the previous chapter, customers could switch RPA providers much more easily.

Overall, in the current landscape, combinations of RPA and process mining solutions are usually tied to one single software. This means that there is currently no universal process mining tool that allows the creation of a process model that can then be used in multiple RPA software for automation. Therefore, the process mining approach does not currently offer a platform-independent solution for modeling RPA processes. But as seen with UiPath, certain RPA providers are already working with process mining, as it's a very powerful tool to find potential RPA cases. These developments show that process mining in combination with RPA is gaining in importance. It is therefore exciting to observe future innovations in this area, which could potentially lead to a platform-independent solution.

3.3 Summary and Outlook: Platform-independent RPA Modeling

In this theoretical chapter, it was explained how RPA and its technology has evolved from simple automation tools to complex software robots capable of mimicking human actions in business processes. RPA is being used to automate repetitive tasks, and therefore freeing up humans for more demanding activities. However, as there are a number of different RPA providers it was examined whether there are any platform-independent solutions available in this sector. For this, various approaches to modeling RPA processes have been explored, including the Process Design Document, the integration of BPMN with Camunda, and the use of Visio in combination with Power Automate.

On the one hand, PDD is used very widely, but as seen it is only used as a documentation tool and therefore does not offer any integration into any RPA software. On the other hand, Visio has integration possibilities. However, these integration solutions remain tied to one specific RPA platform. As a third approach, BPMN and its integration possibilities with multiple RPA providers were investigated. Combined with the use of Camunda, it became clear that although the integration of different RPA software providers is possible, it still requires double modeling of the processes. Lastly, the modern approach of process mining was investigated. Process mining shows great potential for the future of RPA but as of now is also tied to specific software solutions. Overall, it has been shown that these solutions have the potential to reach platform independence. However, none of them is at this point yet, as they either only fit to one single RPA solution or modeling in the RPA software itself is still necessary. But why does no platform-independent RPA modeling tool exist that can be implemented into multiple RPA software?

One main reason is that from an RPA software provider's perspective, it gives not many advantages to develop or integrate a platform-independent solution. Obviously, a company could win new customers with such a solution, but at the same time, there is the big risk of customers leaving for one of the many competitors. A platform-independent solution would make it much easier for one to switch between RPA providers. Therefore, any company that wants to keep its customers would want to make it as difficult as possible to switch from one RPA software to another. For example, a large company can easily have around 100 active RPA processes running daily. All these processes would need to be developed again if the company is to switch RPA software. This switch means a huge money and time investment. Most companies would not take this path because of this large barrier and therefore prefer to stay with its initial software provider. On the contrary, if a platform-independent solution existed, the investment and risk for a change would be much smaller. As a result, it would be much more difficult to retain customers when there is so much competition in the market. Overall, it is strategically advantageous for providers to keep their tools and software exclusive to their own platform in order to secure their market position and strengthen customer loyalty.

As a result of this, a platform-independent RPA modeling language would therefore have to be developed by a company that does not offer RPA software itself and has no direct interest in retaining customers. This raises the question of whether it is technically possible at all, or whether RPA software providers generally do not allow a third-party provider to integrate such a solution into their RPA software. In the next section of this thesis, this question is addressed practically. The goal is to create a prototype of a platform-independent modeling language and then find a solution to import a model into multiple RPA software. The practical part that follows in the next chapters will show what this solution could look like and what challenges need to be overcome.

Chapter 4

Planning and Specification of the Prototype

Developing a platform-independent modeling language for RPA processes is the challenging goal of this thesis. To ensure that the entire prototyping process is well structured and as efficient as possible, the structure is based on an existing framework. Inspired by the book “Effective Prototyping for Software Makers”, written by Jonathan Arnowitz, Michael Arent, and Nevin Berger, the design process of the prototype is based on four phases: Planning, Specification, Design, and Results. Whereas in this chapter the first two phases, planning and specification are addressed. The objective of the first two phases in this approach is to create a basis and framework for the development of the prototype. This includes defining the requirements and selecting the tools and methods, which are used to develop and design the prototype in phase three. It is therefore essential to have a structured plan and define precise specifications in the first two phases so that the prototype can be developed in an efficient manner.

Before the planning and specification of the prototype takes place, it is useful to create an overview. For this, a scenario and the presentation of the task flow will provide a better insight into the planned use of the prototype. This introduction ensures that the further examinations in this chapter are based on a clear understanding of the planned application of the prototype. After this introduction, the planning phase starts with the definition of the requirements for the prototype in order to set a clear framework for the later development. Next, the fidelity level is defined, which determines how detailed each part of the prototype is expected to be. In the second phase, the focus is on defining specifications for the final prototype. These specifications include the methods and tools which are to be used in the design and development of the prototype. The procedure is as follows: First a method is chosen and then a fitting tool is selected for this specific method. Overall, the goal of this chapter is to create a solid foundation which is crucial for the realization of the prototype. A good framework and foundation ensure that the prototype can be designed and developed effectively and efficiently.

4.1 An Outside Perspective

Before planning and specifying details, it is necessary to understand the use and purpose of the prototype. There are several possible methods that can be used for this purpose. Arnowitz et al. (2010) propose the two proven techniques of creating scenarios and task flows. These methods offer a fresh perspective on the project by providing a more detailed view of user interaction and process sequences. In the following steps, both techniques are therefore used to develop a comprehensive understanding of the prototype and the associated processes.

Based on the quote “Scenarios ... are a necessary component in the specific activity of defining and building a prototype.” (Arnowitz et al., 2010, p. 34), it can be argued that thinking through and applying scenarios is essential in the development of a prototype. Scenarios make it possible to simulate realistic and practical use cases in which the RPA modeling language is used. They help to anticipate user interactions, system requirements, and potential challenges. In this way, adjustments can be made at an early stage to make the prototype not only functional but also user-oriented and adaptable to different business processes. As a result, a short scenario is presented that demonstrates how a platform-independent RPA modeling language could be used in a real context.

Mike, head of a robotics development team at an international company, is facing a challenge. His team uses several RPA software providers across different departments. As a result, the processes are never modeled uniformly in one software. Mike’s goal is to first model all processes in a unified tool using a universal modeling language before transferring them to the specific RPA software. This would enable uniform modeling of the processes and simplify their transfer between different RPA providers.

Mike’s scenario illustrates a problem within their company that needs to be solved. This solution would be a tool or a modeling language that allows developers to model processes independently from any RPA software. Such that each RPA process, regardless in which RPA software it is used, can be mapped uniformly. A second important part includes the possibility to then transfer these uniformly designed processes to one or even multiple of their RPA providers in use. This means that the modeling language has to be platform-independent, but transferable to multiple platforms. In conclusion, Mike needs a platform-independent RPA modeling language that is applicable to each of their RPA software in use. This would allow his team to have process models in a uniform language that can be understood by everyone.

This is just one scenario for the use of such a platform-independent RPA modeling language. In reality, there could be many other cases where such a software could be useful. One example would be if a company is not satisfied with its current RPA software and wants to switch to a concurrent RPA provider. In such a scenario the modeling language could be very helpful to conduct

a switch between both providers. Since all existing processes do not need to be developed again within the new software.

Now that the scenario has shown how the RPA modeling language could be practically applied in Mike’s company, a visual representation of how the process could look like is presented. This visualization demonstrates the specific steps Mike’s company would need to take in order to use a platform-independent RPA modeling language.

Figure 4.1: Flow of Tasks for a Platform-independent RPA Modeling Language

Figure 4.1 visualizes the workflow of steps performed by a user of the prototype. The simple flowchart diagram includes all the various applications used in the process. Starting with the modeling of the RPA process in a modeling software. In a second step, a script is used to transfer the modeled process into the selected RPA software. Lastly, in a third step of this workflow is the import of the result into the corresponding RPA software. This completes the entire process which includes the prototype. Obviously, from there on, the user can do further work in the RPA software itself and deploy the process.

In conclusion, the combination of the task flow and the scenario provides a comprehensive insight into how the prototype could be used in practice. This is an important view and helps to pave the way for its successful implementation. Now that the purpose of the prototype is understood, the next step is to define the scope and dimensions of the prototype. For this, the next chapter elaborates on the so-called “fidelity level” of the individual components of the prototype.

4.2 Defining Requirements for the Prototype

“The basic prototyping strategy advocated in effective prototyping is the practice of basing your prototype design on a mixture of requirements and assumptions.” (Arnowitz et al., 2010, p. 32). Based on this quote, a good strategic way to approach a prototype is to first set a good mixture of requirements, on which the prototype can then be built. These can be defined in detail in the four proposed categories: business, functional, technical, and usability. This approach creates a

comprehensive framework for the development of a prototype that ensures technical feasibility and usability. Additionally, the described scenario and task flow will support the specification of each requirement.

The goal of this prototype is primarily to check the feasibility of a platform-independent RPA modeling language. This means that the business aspect does not play a central role in this project. This creates a contrast to traditional approaches, where companies want to create a profitable product and therefore the business aspects play a central role. The goal is not to present a finished end product, but rather to demonstrate the practical feasibility and if possible, develop a solution. The main focus of the requirements is therefore on the functionality and technical aspects in order to show the feasibility in the form of a prototype.

Table 4.1 lists the five initial defined requirements for the prototype that is being developed in this work. These reflect the central aspects and objectives that are needed for the development of a platform-independent RPA modeling language. Each requirement is classified according to its type. The priority rating indicates the importance of the requirement for the prototype.

#	Requirement	Type	Priority
1.	Modeling language capable of representing RPA processes	Functional	High
2.	The ability for models to be translated and used across multiple RPA software platforms.	Functional	Medium
3.	Creation of a Modeling language within a modeling tool	Technical	High
4.	Script or software for efficient model transfer between the modeling language and RPA software.	Technical	Medium
5.	Intuitive design of the modeling language to facilitate ease of use for developers.	Usability	Low

Table 4.1: List of Requirements for the Prototype

Based on the strategic approach, which focuses on the feasibility and less on the business aspects at this stage, precise requirements for the prototype in the areas of function, technology, and user-friendliness have been defined. These requirements reflect the core objectives of the prototype: the representation of RPA processes through a modeling language, the integration within a modeling tool, the translatability of the models for different RPA software platforms, and an intuitive user interface to facilitate the application by developers. The prioritization of these requirements, from low to high, shows the importance of each aspect for the design and development of the prototype. Therefore, the higher the priority, the more important a requirement is in the development phase of the project.

Requirements 1 and 3, which focus on the development of a modeling language and its implementation within a modeling tool, are given high priority due to their essential role in the

foundation of the project. They form the core of the prototype, as without a functional and correctly integrated modeling language, neither an effective representation of RPA processes nor their transfer to RPA software would be possible. Requirements 2 and 4 build on the basic requirements 1 and 3 and are therefore classified as medium priority. This classification reflects the fact that, although their implementation is essential for the completeness and effectiveness of the prototype, they cannot be realized without an established basis in the form of the modeling language within the modeling tool. Additionally, the requirement two is key in order to reach the platform independence status. If the modeling language can only be applied to one single RPA software, then platform independence is not reached. Therefore, to successfully complete requirement two, the transfer to at least two different RPA providers will be necessary. Finally, requirement 5 is given a low priority as it primarily addresses user-friendliness, which, although important for the end product, is less critical in the initial prototyping phase than functionality and technical feasibility.

With regard to the previously described scenario in which Mike and his team want to model RPA processes independently, it becomes clear that a platform-independent RPA modeling language is essential. Hence, Requirement 1, which enables platform-independent modeling, is key to meet Mike's needs. The second requirement, that enables the ability to transfer modeled processes to the corresponding RPA software is also necessary, such that Mike's team can process the models created directly in their preferred RPA environment. In addition, the technical requirements, which form the basis for the functional requirements, should also be fulfilled in order to satisfy Mike's needs. Lastly, the design is not a top priority in the initial development phase, but it would certainly be an advantage if the interface were user-friendly in order to enable easy utilization for Mike's team. Overall, it is clear that all the requirements have to be fulfilled to some lengths, to create a usable product that meets the specific needs of Mike and his team.

However, all these requirements are not definitive in any way. During the development of the prototype, it should be noted that the proposed requirements may be constantly changing. According to the quote "it is assumed here that the software requirements-gathering process is occurring in parallel and is incomplete" (Arnowitz et al., 2010, p. 34), the process of requirements collection takes place in parallel and is not complete at this point in time. This means that new requirements can be added and requirements that have already been defined must be adapted in order to meet current findings and needs. While the requirements can continuously be adapted, it is also important to keep the prototype at an appropriate level of detail. The next chapter is therefore used to define the fidelity level of the prototype.

4.3 Defining Fidelity Level of the Prototype

In this chapter, the aim is to define the content and fidelity level of the final prototype. The fidelity level determines how detailed and close to a final product a prototype should be. For example, a low-fidelity prototype can be a simple sketch with pen and paper that illustrates basic ideas. On the

other hand, a high-fidelity prototype is much closer to a final product and has for example actual functional features. Such a distinction helps to make the development process more efficient. As by clarifying the level of detail and functionality on which the current focus lies, a certain frame and goal for the prototype is set. Furthermore, the decisions about the fidelity level have a significant impact on the resources and time required to complete the project. A prototype with too much detail and complexity can tie up resources unnecessarily, as these details may need to be reworked anyway in later iterations. On the other hand, a prototype with too little fidelity may not provide enough information to verify the requirements (Arnowitz et al., 2010, p. 85).

The book “Effective Prototyping for Software Makers” defines six different types of content to which different degrees of fidelity can be assigned: Information Design, Visual Design, Interaction Design and Navigation Model, Editorial Content, Brand Expression, and System Performance and Behavior. In this project, the Brand Expression part is left out, as this work is not about a company that wants to sell a product, and therefore no branding is needed. Editorial content, which deals with the use of text, i.e. style and appearance, is also omitted in this project. This content type is not relevant, as style and appearance are not important for such a prototype. The main focus is therefore on the other four content types.

Arnowitz et al. (2010) emphasize that information design focuses on the structuring of information in interactive software. This includes data in the form of input and display fields, menus, tables, graphics, and other information expressions. This is particularly relevant for the modeling language itself, as the user interacts directly with the modeling software in order to create a process model. It is crucial that it is clearly recognizable for the user which building block in the modeled process represents which action. This contributes significantly to the clarity and comprehensibility of the prototype. However, the structure of the prototype is not of high importance, as long as the user understands how to use it. For this reason, the fidelity level here is limited to a medium level. Consequently, the structure must be good enough so that a user can easily use the prototype without too much effort, but on the other hand, not too much time should be invested into that part of the project.

Next, the visual appearance of the prototype is considered. The visual design is not of primary importance for this prototype, as the focus is on functionality and technical implementation. When developing a tool that focuses on process modeling and transferring these models, practical applicability and correct functionality are more crucial than aesthetic aspects. It is primarily about having a simple and efficient design and nothing more. The visual design can be refined in later phases when the basic functional and technical requirements are met. Therefore, there is only a low-fidelity grade for this aspect.

In the “Interaction Design and Navigation Model” category, the focus is on user interaction with the software, for example how the system responds to user actions (Arnowitz et al., 2010, p. 93). Although modeling software provides the environment for modeling processes, it is of

central importance that processes can be designed efficiently and easily. Another important aspect is the use of the script that enables the transition from the created model to the RPA software. Simple and fluid interaction for the user is crucial here. For these reasons, a fidelity of medium is considered appropriate for this area to ensure a solid user experience.

In the “System Performance and Behavior” section, the focus is on the technical side and the performance of the prototype (Arnowitz et al., 2010, p. 99). It is essential for the RPA prototype to be able to model a process and transfer it to an RPA software. This means that the process can be performed error-free and reliably without any difficulties. Furthermore, aspects such as the execution speed of the script also play a role. A user should not have to wait long for a process model to be transformed into the desired RPA software. Therefore, the performance and behavior of the prototype are considered important and deserve a high-fidelity level.

In summary, this chapter highlights different types of content and their level of fidelity for the prototype. It is outlined how choosing the right fidelity levels for the different content categories is important in order to use time and resources efficiently while meeting the requirements and expectations of the project. On one hand, two content types were left out, as they do not play a role in this project. On the other hand, particular attention is paid to “System Performance and Behavior”, which is evaluated as a critical aspect with a high-fidelity level. The table 4.2 provides an overview of the content categories discussed and their respective fidelity levels, which provides a clear direction for the further development phases of the prototype. It is to note, that these fidelity levels are set for the final prototype, which means that during the process of development, it can very well be that one part of the prototype has a lower fidelity level than its goal.

Content	Fidelity level
Information design	Medium
Visual design	Low
Interaction design and navigation model	Medium
System performance and behavior	High

Table 4.2: Fidelity Levels for the Prototype

After having examined the requirements, the fidelity level, and given an outside perspective on the use of the prototype, the focus slowly turns to the implementation. But before the actual implementation, the specification of the tools to be used in the project is carried out. Therefore, the next chapter involves the selection process of all the tools and software needed in order to develop the prototype.

4.4 Specification of the Prototype: Defining Methods and Tools

After completing the first phase of prototyping by setting requirements and the level of fidelity, more concrete decisions have to be made in the second phase. This phase of prototyping builds on the foundations of the first phase to make concrete decisions regarding the prototyping method and the selection of the right tools. Thus, the quote “In the planning phase you determined what to prototype. This phase decides how to prototype” (Arnowitz et al., 2010, p. 107) explains the connection between these phases in a short and accurate manner. Decisions made in this chapter are based on the previously evaluated plan and aim to identify the most suitable methods and tools for the development of a platform-independent RPA modeling language.

In this chapter, multiple prototyping tools and methods are examined using the following procedure: First, a suitable prototyping method is selected. Secondly, the right tool is chosen to implement this method. Choosing the method before selecting the tool is crucial as it sets the framework for the entire prototyping initiative. Once the method is determined, a suitable tool can be chosen to support and enable that specific methodology. Such an approach ensures that the chosen tool is an optimal fit for the selected method, which maximizes the efficiency and effectiveness of the prototyping process. The following sections examine this approach in detail, starting with low-fidelity prototypes that aim to visualize the entire project.

4.4.1 Low-fidelity Prototyping

To start up the project two low-fidelity prototypes are created in order to get an overview of how the end product should look like. Both these are used as a base and guideline after which the final prototype is developed. This means they should give a certain idea of how the end product could look like, and therefore help in the design and development process. One of the low-fidelity prototypes has its focus on the main part, the modeling language itself, while the other focuses more on the entirety of the final product. The following sections examine which prototyping tools are used for this purpose and why they are chosen.

In order to capture the entirety of the project in a clear framework, the creation of a storyboard proves to be particularly effective. A storyboard acts as a narrative prototype that is usually used in the early stages of the software development process (Arnowitz et al., 2010, p. 139). It provides a visual representation of the processes and functions that a user of the product will perform. In this case, it illustrates everything from modeling the process to deploying it in the RPA software. Overall, this method makes it possible to gain an initial clear picture of the project flow and the functionalities of the end product. A storyboard allows everyone involved to understand the vision of the project and see how the individual components interact. By creating a storyboard, the prototype gets broken down into unique, visually comprehensible elements. This helps to reduce the complexity of the project into multiple parts and therefore lays a solid foundation for the further development and fine-tuning of the project.

Choosing the right storyboard tool is the first step in the preparation phase of any project that requires a visual representation and storytelling. With a wide variety of options available, it's all about choosing the most suitable storyboarding tool for the project. Nowadays many different approaches can be taken, such as traditional methods like using pen and paper, or more advanced digital solutions that offer a wide range of features. The possibilities for creating a storyboard are almost limitless. All it takes is a quick Google search to find multiple providers, which propose a digital tool to create storyboards in a fast and simple way. These specialized storyboarding software providers have mostly user-friendly interfaces and large libraries of pre-built elements that can speed up the creation process.

Probably the most innovative approach, that can speed up and simplify the creative process is by using artificial intelligence (AI). With AI, ideas can be transformed into detailed visual stories without the need for drawing or designing skills. An AI image generator can take a simple text known as a prompt and generate visual elements that fit the given input. This can for example be a very specific scene with exact descriptions, or just a few simple words which gives the AI more freedom for its own creation. This not only opens up new creative possibilities but also makes the creation of storyboards more accessible and efficient, especially for people with less artistic talent. In view of these considerations, and the fact that this work is about an automation project, the decision was made in favor of the most innovative approach for the creation of the storyboard, artificial intelligence. This choice is based on the ability of AI to not only speed up the design process but also greatly simplify it by generating visual elements from simple text descriptions. The use of AI makes it possible to create complex and detailed visual images that would otherwise require drawing or designing skills which are not given to everyone.

Given the rapid developments in the field of artificial intelligence in the last few years and months, the market has already been flooded by many different AI image generators. Therefore, the challenge is to choose the best one from the multitude of tools available. As each of the countless vendors offers an AI with different strengths, specializations, and functionalities, the decision comes down to the following criteria: Firstly, the AI must be able to create images that fit the given prompt. Secondly, it must be possible to give additional prompts to the created image, such that the AI can adapt its generated image. Thirdly, the generated images must be copyright-free, so that they can be used in a thesis.

Based on Zapier's report, DALL-E 3 stands out as one of the best and easiest tools to use (Guinness, 2024). Thanks to its integration with ChatGPT, DALL-E 3 enables users to brainstorm together with the AI and refine the images precisely (OpenAI, n.d.). This synergy between text-based input and visual output opens up new dimensions of creative work. Users can interact with the AI in natural language to formulate and refine their ideas. If an initial prompt generates a promising image, but some small details do not quite meet expectations, these aspects can be specifically adjusted and refined with a follow-up prompt. The iterative approach makes it pos-

sible to generate images that largely correspond to the user's expectations in terms of precision and detail and thus offer a customized visual representation. Another decisive aspect in favor of DALL-E 3 is the clarity of usage rights. All images created with DALL-E 3 are the property of the user, without the need for separate permission to reprint, sell, or market the images (OpenAI, n.d.). Having this freedom in the use of the generated images offers an invaluable advantage for projects where copyright issues may play a role. In conclusion, the first low-fidelity prototype for this project is created by using the DALL-E 3 image generator. This storyboard should then represent the entire process of how the final product is used.

After choosing a storyboard to provide a clear narrative of the overall process, the next step is to create the second low-fidelity prototype which focuses more on the modeling language itself. This is where the wireframe comes into play. A visual representation, through the use of a wireframe, gives a deeper understanding of the concept and design of the modeling language itself. A wireframe serves as a basic sketch that provides initial insights into the possible design of the software (Arnowitz et al., 2010, p. 139). In this case, it forms a visual basis that shows what the modeling language could look like in its later form.

This wireframe not only makes the design concept more understandable but also makes it possible to precisely plan and visualize the structure and layout of the modeling language. Based on this wireframe, the development of the modeling language can be driven forward in a targeted manner. Overall, the wireframe serves as a guideline for implementation by providing a clear idea of the user interface and the interaction elements that are to be implemented in the modeling language. This creates a solid foundation for further development, ensuring that the modeling language is not only functional but also user-friendly.

Selecting a suitable tool for creating wireframes is very similar to the process of selecting a storyboard tool. Although a wireframe naturally differs from a storyboard in its function and objective, the range of tools and methods available is quite comparable. On the one hand, it is again possible to rely on the traditional pen and paper method. On the other hand, numerous prototyping software solutions offer specialized tools for creating wireframes. These digital tools make it possible to develop precise and detailed wireframes that can be integrated directly into the further development process. Furthermore, just like with the storyboard, there is also the possibility to create a wireframe with the use of artificial intelligence. AI-based tools can support the process by automatically generating design elements or layout suggestions based on an exact prompt.

But there is one difficulty: AI image-generating tools are not that good with the creation of text in the images. This causes a problem since a process model most likely includes elements that are named and therefore some sort of text is needed in the wireframe. For this reason, it makes little sense to use an AI tool for this task. But as said there are plenty of other good options on the market. Of all these providers, Lucidchart stands out as a particularly suitable tool. Lucidchart is a great software solution that enables the creation of diagrams for a wide range of purposes.

From visualizing processes and system architectures to designing new features or user interfaces. Lucidchart provides the tools to illustrate ideas with ease (Lucidchart, n.d.).

This versatile toolbox provides a simple and efficient way to create an initial visual representation of a new modeling language. Through this visual representation, it is possible to illustrate the concept of the modeling language in a comprehensible way. For this reason, the low-fidelity prototype of the modeling language in this project is developed in the form of a wireframe with the tool Lucidchart. This basic first visualization of the modeling language is then used as a template in order to create the real version of it.

In conclusion, both low-fidelity prototypes are created with modern approaches, namely DALL-E 3 and Lucidchart. The goal is to get a first glimpse into what the final prototype could look like. In the case of the storyboard the entire project and in the case of the wireframe the modeling language is represented. Both these prototypes are used as guidelines and templates in order to develop the final product. To create the final prototype, it is necessary to define further tools which are used in the creation process. Hence, in the next chapter, a suitable tool to develop the modeling language is elaborated.

4.4.2 Metamodeling Platform

After choosing a wireframe as a prototyping tool for the first version of the modeling language, an approach needs to be defined on how the language itself is developed. In order to develop a modeling language from scratch there are multiple possible approaches. One possibility is obviously to create everything starting from zero, including an entire editor. This would be very time-intensive and difficult. To avoid this, multiple different platforms and tools exist, which facilitate the creation of a modeling language. These provide an entire framework and enable an efficient way to create a modeling language without the need to start from scratch. Again, the goal is to find a fitting software for this project.

A wide range of approaches and tools were available for the prototypes discussed so far. This diversity made it possible to respond flexibly to different requirements and preferences. In contrast, the situation is very different when implementing a new modeling language. In this case, the available options are much more limited. This limitation results from the specialized nature and complex requirements associated with the development of a custom modeling language. The creation of such a language requires not only an in-depth understanding of the underlying domain but also special tools and frameworks that are geared towards the design and implementation of language structures. It is precisely these specialized requirements that are met by metamodeling platforms. These platforms provide a set of tools and an environment specifically designed to support the development of new modeling languages. A metamodeling platform makes it possible to precisely define the syntax, semantics, and notation of a new language through the careful creation

of a metamodel (Karagiannis & Kühn, 2002). This ability to design custom modeling languages that are precisely tailored to the specific needs of a domain or project makes metamodeling platforms an ideal tool for developing a new modeling language.

In the search for a suitable metamodeling platform that meets the specific requirements for the development of a new modeling language, ADOxx proved to be a very suitable choice. ADOxx enables the development of a comprehensive and professional modeling tool that can be seamlessly integrated into specific application environments. Users can create their own graphical modeling language tailored to specific domains by individually developing syntax, semantics, and graphical notations (ADOxx, n.d.). In addition, ADOxx offers a wide range of pre-developed functionalities that allow the modeling language to be extended with existing or custom algorithms and mechanisms to create a fully-fledged modeling tool that can be deployed as an installable and distributable software package (ADOxx, n.d.).

Given these features and capabilities, ADOxx is the ideal environment for developing a new modeling language. With its ability to create a complete and customized modeling language that is precisely tailored to the specific needs of a domain, ADOxx offers just the right level of flexibility and support. For these reasons, ADOxx was selected as the platform of choice for the development of the modeling language in this project. As the modeling language tool now has been defined, the last part that remains is a script in form of a coded prototype. Since the created models need to somehow be transferred from ADOxx to an RPA software, there is a need for some sort of script. These tools used in order to create such a script are examined in the following chapter.

4.4.3 Coded Prototype

After the creation of a modeling language in ADOxx, the complete prototype is still not finished, as the process models still need to be transferred into an RPA software. Therefore, a script or program in the form of a coded prototype comes into play as another important component of the project. This is essential in order to transfer the developed model from the platform-independent modeling language into a specific RPA software. The coded prototype moves beyond the boundaries of a graphic illustration and stands as a fully functional prototype. To fulfill these functions, the prototype must consist of executable code. This implementation takes place in the form of a script or program that acts as a bridge between the modeling in ADOxx and the RPA software.

When implementing a coded prototype, developers are faced with a variety of code editors that hardly differ in terms of functions. Many of these editors offer similar basic functions and are also available free of charge, which makes the decision in favor of a specific tool much less dependent on its price or exclusive features. In this context, the choice of the right editor becomes a question of personal taste and individual preferences.

For this project, Visual Studio Code was chosen as the preferred environment for the development of the coded prototype. Visual Studio Code is a powerful, free editor developed by Microsoft. It is characterized by its versatility, and an extensive range of supported programming languages, such as Java, Python, C++, and many others (Visual Studio Code, n.d.). In addition, Visual Studio Code offers an intuitive user interface, efficient navigation, a robust debugging tool, and an impressive selection of extensions. All that put together can significantly simplify and speed up the development process. These features make Visual Studio Code an excellent choice for creating a coded prototype. Finally, it is to add that the code for the prototype is written in Java, which is greatly supported by Visual Studio Code.

With the decision to use Java and Visual Studio Code as editor all the tools necessary to develop a platform-independent modeling language are given. However, there is still one last component which does play a significant role in the development of the prototype: the RPA software. Therefore, in the next chapter, the most suitable RPA providers for this project are examined.

4.4.4 Selection of RPA Software

In order for the coded prototype to unfold its full significance, it is essential to have a target software within which the modeled RPA process can be used. This makes it essential to define at least one RPA software as a tool. In view of the goal of developing a platform-independent modeling language, this necessity extends to the inclusion of at least two different RPA software providers. This is supported by the earlier defined requirement number two; “The ability for models to be translated and used across multiple RPA software platforms”. This strategic choice makes it possible to test the versatility and adaptability of the developed language and ensure that it can be applied beyond the boundaries of a single platform. The specific RPA software solutions selected for this project are presented in detail in the following sections.

Given the large number of options available on the market, selecting suitable RPA software is both a challenge and an opportunity. A look at the Gartner report, which lists the 16 leading RPA providers, reveals the diversity and range of solutions available. Within this landscape, four market leaders emerge that clearly stand out from the competition thanks to their performance, innovative strength, and comprehensive range of functions: Automation Anywhere, UiPath, Blue Prism, and Microsoft Power Automate (Ray et al., 2023). Of these four competitors, UiPath, with a customer base of over 10,000, is currently the biggest player on the market (Ray et al., 2023). This position is the result of various factors, such as consistent innovation and the ability to offer a user-friendly, scalable, and robust RPA solution. Given these factors, selecting UiPath as one of the RPA providers for this project seems like a logical choice. For the project, it is important to choose a platform that provides a solid foundation for the development and implementation of RPA solutions, just like UiPath. Additionally, user-friendliness is an important aspect, as this makes it easier to understand the software and therefore facilitate the development of the prototype.

The other three of the top four; Blue Prism, Automation Anywhere, and Microsoft Power Automate all offer a similar range of functions and options. Overall, only small differences can be found between each software, however those are mostly not noticeable if the product is not known in full detail. Which means they are in close competition, and the differences between their offerings are only marginal from an outside perspective. The similarity in functionality and the small differences between the individual software solutions make it a challenge to clearly identify one provider as the best of the three.

Given the similarity of all three software tools, the criterion of user-friendliness decides which tool is selected. As already said, developing a prototype for user-friendly software is much simpler, than for a complicated software that needs a lot of time to be understood. This approach makes it possible to quickly develop a functioning prototype without getting lost in the steep learning curves of more complex systems. An intuitive tool not only significantly reduces the familiarization period, but also facilitates the early validation of concepts and agile adaptation to feedback. In prototyping, where ideas need to be tested quickly and refined iteratively, a user-friendly and easy-to-use tool can make all the difference. Overall, it therefore makes sense to choose a simpler software for the first prototype. It makes sense to only switch to more complex software in later phases of the project. Such an approach can minimize the risk of delays and frustrations, which often come with learning and using complex systems. It also ensures that the project is built on a solid foundation right from the start.

In order to find the most user-friendly tool, a report from the G2 platform is used to determine the software with the best usability. G2 evaluates 20 RPA software solutions using a specially developed algorithm and assigns a usability score. This score directly reflects user-friendliness: the higher the score, the easier the software is to use (G2, n.d.). The ranking of the chosen four RPA software solutions in the report is as follows: UiPath takes 4th place, followed by Blue Prism in 5th place, and Automation Anywhere, takes 6th place. Microsoft Power Automate is valued the worst of these four and can be found in 10th place (G2, n.d.). These rankings again underline the decision for UiPath as an excellent choice. Since the software is in a leading position in the area of user-friendliness. In addition, the close ranking suggests a tiny preference for Blue Prism as the second RPA software, just ahead of Automation Anywhere. The difference between these two is small and probably Automation Anywhere would be a great candidate too for this project. But as Blue Prism ranks slightly better in user-friendliness, the choice is made in favor of Blue Prism.

With the selection of UiPath and Blue Prism as the RPA software for this project, two strong competitors with good user-friendliness have been found. With this decision, all the necessary tools and software solutions in order to create a platform-independent RPA modeling language have been defined. These decisions create the necessary prerequisites and framework conditions for the development of the prototype.

Finally, with the RPA software UiPath and Blue Prism, all the essential tools for the entire project have been chosen. At the end of this phase, it is important to summarize and reflect on the decisions made and plan the next steps. Exactly this is the goal of the next and final chapter of the planning and specification phase.

4.5 Summary and Conclusion of the Planning and Specification Phase

First, in this chapter, an outside view of the whole problem was made. For this, a scenario and a task flow diagram were developed. With these, it was possible to get a better understanding of how and why a platform-independent RPA modeling language can be used. Next, the first phase covered the definition of the requirements for the prototype. These were set up in a way that if all requirements are fulfilled, a functional platform-independent RPA modeling language should be achieved. Additionally, the fidelity level for different aspects of the prototype were defined. In summary, the focus of the prototype was clearly placed on its functionalities. The main objective is the modeling of an RPA process that can then be used in various RPA software solutions. Design aspects, such as the visual appearance of the prototype, were given less weight and therefore should be limited to the essentials. It should also be emphasized that the defined requirements are flexible. In the course of development, these can change, or new ones can be added in order to optimize the design and functionalities of the prototype. In conclusion, the plan laid out in this phase is used as a reference and guideline for the further development of the prototype. Such guidelines lead the project throughout the development process and therefore ensure that each step and all decisions remain aligned with the requirements. The defined plan thus sets the foundation for a goal-oriented development of the prototype.

In the second phase, a selection of different prototyping methods was made. With the goal that the requirements, scenario, and fidelity levels examined in the first phase can be achieved using said prototyping methods. Additionally, these methods lay the foundation for the development of the project. In addition, specific tools were identified and chosen for each method. The goal of these tools is to enable the methods, in such a way, that they can be implemented effectively. This combination of methods and tools forms the foundation on which the further steps of the development process are built. These early decisions ensure that in the design and development phase of prototyping, no more new tools need to be found, as everything is already planned. This helps that the practical part of the project can be carried out with the greatest possible efficiency.

Overall, the selected prototyping methods cover a broad spectrum to effectively support the project from conception to implementation. First of all, the storyboard is used to visually capture the basic concept and provide an initial overview of the planned functionality and process. The latest technology in the form of artificial intelligence, specifically DALL-E 3, enables the visual representation of the storyboard and thus opens up new dimensions in creative design. It enables a quick and intuitive presentation of the ideas before they are converted into concrete models.

Secondly, the wireframe made in Lucidchart then refines this overview by focusing specifically on the design of the modeling language. The goal of this low-fidelity prototype is to give a detailed view of the user interface and the interaction elements of the modeling language. These initial prototypes create a solid basis and framework for the further development of the RPA modeling language.

After selecting tools and methods for the low-fidelity prototypes, ADOxx was chosen as software to develop the modeling language. This metamodeling platform provides the necessary tools and functions to design and implement a new modeling language from the start. As the last method a coded prototype was defined, in order to develop the script that transfers the created models from ADOxx to an RPA software. For this Visual Studio Code and Java were chosen to develop the coded prototype. UiPath and Blue Prism were defined as the two RPA software providers.

With the defined requirements and the selected tools, the project is ready for the next phase: the actual realization and development of the prototype. In conclusion, the decisions made in the first two phases laid the foundation for further development of the prototype. Hence, in phase three, which is covered in the next chapter, the implementation of the prototype begins.

Chapter 5

Design and Development of the Prototype

In this chapter, the complete development process of a prototype for a platform-independent RPA modeling language is documented. With the goal of putting the previously developed plan and requirements into practice. The chapter includes every part of the project, from the low-fidelity prototypes to the modeling language itself, and finally to the integration into the RPA software. The final goal of this practical chapter is to have a prototype of a platform-independent modeling language that can be implemented into multiple RPA software solutions.

In the first part, the foundation of the project is laid out with the creation of low-fidelity prototypes. This first part of prototyping consists of a storyboard that captures the idea of the project in its entirety. Additionally, a wireframe is used to display a more detailed look of the modeling language itself. Both these low-fidelity prototypes serve as a guideline for the later development of the final prototype. Furthermore, both these visual prototypes help to give a better understanding of the project and its purpose.

The next step in this chapter is the analysis and selection of RPA software that is used for the implementation of the prototype. For this, the market-leading RPA software providers are inspected. Additionally, a closer look is taken at the technologies and functions of these RPA solutions. This is essential in order to understand how RPA processes are modeled and what key elements are used for it. Based on this analysis a platform-independent RPA modeling language is developed. Whereas a detailed description is given of the modeling language in ADOxx. This includes all the developed classes and attributes that contribute to the modeling language. The goal is to create a solid but simple modeling language that can model simple RPA processes platform independently.

Finally, in the last part of the project, a solution is found on how to transfer a process model from the platform-independent RPA modeling language to one RPA software. For this a script is developed, that is able to transform an ADOxx XML (Extensible Markup Language) file into the

RPA provider's format, such that it can be imported. In a further step, exactly the same process is done again but for the second RPA provider, in order to prove the platform independence of the prototype. Lastly, both the created scripts are brought together in a small desktop application. The goal of this application is to enable an easy way of transforming an RPA process model from ADOxx, such that it can be imported into both RPA solutions.

5.1 A Visual Conception of the Prototype

This chapter presents a detailed illustration of two low-fidelity prototypes that play an important role in the development of the project. The goal is to set a first visual impression of what the final product could look like. First, a storyboard is created to give an overview of the entire project. Followed by a Wireframe, which gives a more detailed view of the modeling language.

Before looking at the first low-fidelity prototype, it is important to know that the images of this storyboard are not created in a traditional way, but instead through the innovative application of artificial intelligence. As defined earlier each image is generated with the use of the AI image generator DALL-E 3. As a reminder: the AI and especially DALL-E 3 enable a new and modern way of creating images through prompts. This enables the visualization of concepts and ideas into concrete images without the need for much creativity and designing skills. Such a visual display provides a clear understanding of the idea behind the prototype. For this, the storyboard serves as a good low-fidelity prototyping method, which helps to display and explain the entire prototype in a simple way. In its entirety, the storyboard should contain each part of the final product and additionally showcase how a user would make use of it.

One important aspect of the storyboard is to have a coherent visual style across all images generated by DALL-E 3. To ensure this consistency, it is crucial to include specific instructions in each prompt, which describe the desired design style of the image. For this storyboard a design, that stands out for its simplicity is chosen, by using simple black and white drawings. In order to achieve this clear and concrete form of design, the description "black and white line drawing" is inserted into each prompt. Such a precise specification about the colors and the drawing style gives the AI a clear limitation on the style of each generated image. This ensures that each image is created with a consistent look across the storyboard. Overall, this instruction helps to save time, as the first created image has already the desired style and therefore the refinement with follow-up prompts can focus on details of the image itself.

Additionally, to the stylistic part of the image, it is necessary to formulate a suitable prompt for what the image has to represent. Here the goal is to make a very clear and precise description of what should be displayed, such that the AI does not have much room for interpretation. This means, that the better the description, the more resemblance to the imagination each result has. But often the images generated have flaws or too much unnecessary is going on in the picture. As

a result, this process often requires an experimental approach with different word combinations until the desired result is finally achieved. In the following sections, each of the five images that make up the storyboard are presented and described in detail.

Figure 5.1 represents the first image in the storyboard. It shows a moment in which a man sits focused in front of a computer to model a process in the ADOxx software. The image aims to visualize the first step of the process. In which the interaction of a user with the ADOxx software, while designing an RPA process using a specific modeling language, is shown. The prompt which enabled the creation of this illustration reads as follows:

“Black and white line drawing of a guy sitting in front of a pc. On the pc is a modeling language like BPMN but the software name is ADOxx”

Figure 5.1: Storyboard Part 1

One of the challenges in creating this image was to make some sort of modeling language recognizable on the screen. After several attempts and different approaches, it became clear that the use of the term “BPMN” led to convincing results. This keyword proved to be well known by DALL-E 3 and therefore served as a great help in order to represent a modeling language. But with this another problem came up: the screen mostly displayed the name “BPMN” in some form. To solve this, in the last part of the prompt the name of the displayed software, namely ADOxx was introduced. Not a perfect result was achieved with this, as only “ADOX” is displayed on the top left, but this was as good as a result was possible. The rest of the prompt was then formulated in a relatively straightforward manner and the artificial intelligence was able to implement precisely what was to be represented.

The second image of the storyboard, shown in Figure 5.2 gives a more detailed insight into a process that has been modeled by the user. The goal is to present a fully developed process in the modeling software. The result is achieved with the following prompt:

“Black and white line drawing of a pc screen. On the screen, a process model in the style of a BPMN model is shown”

Figure 5.2: Storyboard Part 2

Again, to achieve this result, the term “BPMN” was used in order for DALL-E 3 to visualize a type of process model. The remainder of the prompt was formulated specially to focus on a screen that should display the process model. It was necessary to specify the one screen, as otherwise DALL-E 3 would often create an image with multiple screens or even just process models on a wall for example. Therefore, this prompt made it possible to create an image that not only shows one single screen but also draws attention to the details and structure of the modeled process that is displayed. Overall, the goal of this image is to show some sort of RPA process model, which is ready to be transferred into an actual RPA software.

Next up in Figure 5.3, the third image of the storyboard captures another step of a user: the export of the previously carefully created model. The illustration is intended to show that a user can export the model after it has been created within ADOxx. Such that it can then be transformed and imported into an RPA software. This scene is created by the following prompt:

“Black and white line drawing of a man sitting in front of a pc screen. On the screen is a software named ADOxx. In the middle of the screen, there is a big Export Model button”

Figure 5.3: Storyboard Part 3

In this prompt, the first sentence serves as the basis for the drawing, which sketches a man sitting in front of a computer. Furthermore, the goal was to create a visualization of the ADOxx software on the one hand and an export button on the other. The representation of ADOxx on the screen did not quite meet expectations since it has very little resemblance to the actual software. However, it was still possible to successfully visualize the essential element: the export process button. The text “Export Model”, placed in the center, allows every viewer to immediately recognize that the user is now exporting the previously created model in image two of the storyboard. Concluding, even if the representation of ADOxx is not really good, the main message of the image can be identified pretty quickly, which is obviously the most important aspect of a storyboard.

The next step in the storyboard deals with the conversion process of the exported model, using some sort of script or program in order to prepare it for use in an RPA software. This crucial step of the overall process is captured in Figure 5.4, generated with the following prompt:

“Black and white line drawing of a pc screen. On the screen a script in visual studio code is running. no background”

Figure 5.4: Storyboard Part 4

In this case, too, the prompt was formulated directly and purposefully: A PC should be displayed with a script in Visual Studio Code on its screen. DALL-E 3 has succeeded particularly well in rendering Visual Studio Code as software. It also quickly becomes clear that some code is actually displayed on the PC screen. In order to concentrate the display on the essentials, “no background” was also integrated into the prompt. This addition served to prevent the AI from generating further elements in the background that were unnecessary for this specific scene, thus ensuring a clear and focused visualization of the script.

In the final part of the storyboard, the user’s final action is depicted: the integration of the model into the selected RPA software. The illustration in Figure 5.5 is intended to show how a user can upload the model to the RPA software of his choice. This decisive phase, which marks the transition of the model into its application environment, is captured visually and translated into an illustration using the prompt:

“Black and white line drawing of a man sitting in front of a pc screen. On the screen, there are two Upload to RPA buttons”

Figure 5.5: Storyboard Part 5

As already implemented in images 1 and 3, the first part of the prompt was formulated in such a way that the image represents a user in front of their PC. The second part of the prompt was specifically aimed at the content of the screen. In order to lead DALL-E 3 to the representation of multiple buttons the words “two upload to RPA buttons” were used. The two upload buttons stand symbolically for the possibility of uploading the model into multiple RPA software. This makes it clear that the user can choose between different RPA providers, which represents the platform independence of the prototype. Overall, this image allows viewers to immediately understand that there is now the option to integrate the model into multiple RPA software. This final image of the storyboard creates the bridge between the script and the practical application of the model, which also completes all the steps the user has to take in order to implement a platform-independent RPA process model into an RPA provider of his choice.

Altogether each image is characterized by its own prompts and innovative implementation by DALL-E and has highlighted one aspect of the entire process - from initial modeling in ADOxx to integration into the chosen RPA software. Therefore, after the careful development of the five images, it is now time to bring the entire storyboard together in Figure 5.6. This next step leads to the overall view of these individual moments, united in a single storyboard. This final image summarizes the sequential order of actions and provides a holistic view of the workflow that has been built up step by step through the previous illustrations. Putting these images together into a complete storyboard makes it possible to understand the entire process at a glance and fully comprehend the logical sequence of actions shown.

Figure 5.6: Complete Storyboard

Each of the five images is accompanied by a short description that serves to make the overall picture even easier to understand. These explanations provide additional context and facilitate understanding of the specific actions and processes visualized in each step. They act as a bridge between the visual representation and the viewer by putting the depicted scenes into words and thus further deepening the story told by the storyboard.

Finally, this carefully forged and detailed illustrated storyboard forms the basis for the entire project. In first line, it serves as a visual guide for the development and implementation of the entire project. But it also can be used as a communication tool in order to explain and show the idea and goals behind the prototype. By showing each single step visually supported by a short description, this storyboard lays a solid foundation on which the project can be built on. In conclusion, the storyboard not only sets the direction but also serves as a source of inspiration and a reference point throughout the development process.

Now that the storyboard has been established as a solid basis that covers the entirety of the project, a closer look at one main element must be taken. This element being the platform-independent modeling language itself. Hence, as defined in the specification phase, the next step is to create an initial sketch of the modeling language that is developed with the help of a wireframe created in Lucidchart. This wireframe serves as a visual illustration that gives a first impression of what the final implementation of the modeling language could look like. It provides a concrete insight into the structure and potential appearance of the language even before it is fully developed. As this part of the project has a visual appearance that any user can see and use, it makes sense to create a first low-fidelity sketch which then serves as a guideline and idea of how the final prototype of the modeling language could look like.

The wireframe in Figure 5.7 outlines a representation of the modeling language within the ADOxx software, which has been selected as the development tool earlier. This prototype shows a simplified view of the ADOxx modeling toolkit, in which an RPA process can be modeled.

Figure 5.7: Wireframe of the Modeling Language

In the center of the illustration is where the modeling takes place. It is an area in which the building blocks can be put together to form a complete process. In this case, a simple process consisting of three actions is displayed. This process for example could be the login process that has already been used in an earlier chapter. This wireframe serves as an example and illustrates how a small process could look like within the modeling environment. In order to create such a model different building blocks have to be used. These essential elements used for modeling can be found on the left-hand side of the wireframe. In this mock-up, different building blocks are included, such as the circular start and end elements, which symbolize the start and end of a process. They are supplemented by rectangular elements that represent the various steps within the process. These steps are provisionally labeled “Action 1-3”. Each action would represent one specific task that a software robot would execute in an RPA process. Since these specific tasks have not been defined yet, each of them gets this provisional name. Next, the arrow element visualizes the process flow by connecting the elements and thus defining the sequence of steps in the process. Putting all this together, the small example process would work as follows: first, the process begins with the “Start” element. Then the actions 1-3 each represent a small task which are to be executed one after another by the software robot. Whereas one action could for example represent a click on a button. Finally, the process concludes with the “End” element.

Altogether the wireframe gives a visual illustration of a small RPA process model, for example, a login process, which is modeled within ADOxx. Such a low-fidelity prototype of the modeling language, just like the storyboard, serves as a guideline and basis for the development of the final modeling language. Combining these two sketches and the first prototypes, the way is

now paved for the next phase: implementation within the ADOxx environment. However, before a platform-independent RPA language can be implemented, it is necessary to understand how RPA software itself works. Without this knowledge, it would be impossible to then later adapt a modeled process into any RPA software. Therefore, the next step includes the exploration and analysis of the two RPA providers Blue Prism and UiPath, in order to get a better understanding of what is required in an RPA modeling language. This examination is done in the next chapter.

5.2 The Basics of Robotic Process Automation

After creating low-fidelity prototypes in order to mock up the entire project, it is time to get to the actual implementation of the prototype. As a first step, before the actual implementation, it is key to understand how RPA software works. This includes various things, such as what process models look like in the software, how they are modeled, and which aspects are needed to create a functional process in an RPA software. Therefore, the aim of this chapter is to provide a comprehensive overview of the functionalities of RPA software in order to structure the further course of the project and define the requirements for the self-developed modeling language. The focus of this chapter is set on the two chosen RPA software providers Blue Prism and UiPath. The technical details presented below are mainly based on practical experience and knowledge gained while working with Blue Prism and UiPath. In addition, information has been compiled from various online sources, most of which are documentations of Blue Prism (Blue Prism, n.d.-a), UiPath (UiPath, n.d.-h), or general resources that cannot be specifically cited.

To better understand how RPA software works, it is important to highlight the basic components required to model and create a functional process. Each RPA software generally has two main components or steps in order to model and create a functional process. Firstly, there is a construction kit in which the process is modeled, similar to for example BPMN. A process consists of various individual blocks that represent different actions. These blocks are assembled in a drag-and-drop construction kit. In this way just like in BPMN, a process model can be built on the user interface. Both, Blue Prism and UiPath use a similar modeling environment with such a drag and drop technology.

The second component of an RPA software is then used to make these blocks active. This means that each block becomes interactive and can interact with the user interface of a program. To achieve this, elements such as buttons or text boxes need to be identified and linked. Said identifying of elements is called “spying” in Blue Prism and is also referred to as such in the rest of this work.

If both components, the blocks, and the spied elements are combined, an executable RPA process is obtained. For this, the identified buttons and fields in the target application must be linked to the corresponding modeled blocks. For example, a “click” block can be assigned to a spied

element such as a button. When executing the process this block performs a click on the assigned button. In essence, RPA software works by executing each block in turn and performing the corresponding actions on the application's user interface.

Looking at both components, it becomes clear that the first part with the building blocks is quite straightforward. In the context of this project in which a process is to be imported into Blue Prism or UiPath, the individual blocks have to be defined. It is mainly about identifying the key blocks and finding a way to import them into the modeling interface of the RPA software. This aspect is covered in the next chapters, where the essential building blocks in UiPath and Blue Prism are analyzed in more detail.

On the other hand, the second part which involves spying the elements is much more complex. There are numerous methods for identifying elements on user interfaces, which are used by various RPA software providers, each with its own characteristics. Every software uses different approaches to identify elements based on their technical framework and purpose. How exactly this process works and whether it can be imported into RPA software such as Blue Prism or UiPath has to be examined. In the following section, a closer look is taken at UiPath and Blue Prism. The specific techniques used by each of these tools to identify elements on the user interface of a program are presented and explained. This analysis provides an insight into the variety of methods available and explains how a few of these technologies work.

Blue Prism uses the so-called "Application Modeler" to spy on elements on the user interface of any program. Various spying options are available in the Application Modeler, depending on the software to be spied on. These include Win32, Java, HTML, UI Automation, Accessibility, and finally Region mode. Each of these spy modes is optimized and specialized for a certain type of application. Win32 is used for classic Windows desktop applications, Java obviously for Java-based applications, and HTML is used for spying in a browser. The Accessibility mode is specially for applications that support Microsoft Active Accessibility and the UIA Mode is useful for modern Windows applications based on Frameworks such as Windows Presentation Foundation (WPF) and Universal Windows Platform (UWP). Lastly, the Region spy mode is a variant that does not really interact with the application itself as it uses a pixel-matching technique to identify elements.

Across all spying modes, spying in Blue Prism generally works by attempting to uniquely identify an element in an application, such as a button for example. For the software to work, it is essential to be able to identify each element uniquely on the user interface of an application. A software robot in Blue Prism otherwise does not know on which button to click in a process if there are multiple similar ones. This uniqueness is achieved by assigning certain attributes to a button for example, which make that element uniquely identifiable on the user interface of the application. Attributes can vary depending on the spy mode. When spying an element within the Application Modeler Blue Prism automatically proposes a few attributes and its values.

In most spy modes structures of the application's user interface are used to give each element attributes, which make them uniquely identifiable. For example, in the HTML mode, one main attribute is the so-called "XPath". XPath (XML Path Language) is a query language that is used to navigate XML documents. It allows searching and selecting nodes in an XML document by using path expressions. XPath is often used together with the Document Object Model (DOM) to identify specific elements in an XML or HTML structure. A DOM is a tree structure-like representation of the HTML of a website in this case. To use the XPath as an attribute, Blue Prism creates a DOM of the website to create a detailed structure of the page. Within this structure, every single element on the user interface of the website can be uniquely identified using its XPath. However, this is only one of many attributes that can be selected when spying on an element with the HTML mode. RPA developers modeling and spying in Blue Prism can manually select which attributes are used for each individual element used in the process. When choosing attributes the goal is to find a combination with which Blue Prism can identify the element uniquely and reliably on the website. This ensures that exactly the right button is pressed in the defined sequence of a process.

In Blue Prism most spy modes use the same, or a similar approach as described with the HTML mode. Depending on the mode, different attributes and technologies are used to identify each single element in an application. Only in the Region mode, a different, more graphical approach is used. In region spy mode a picture is taken and assigned to the element that is to be spied. Instead of finding the matching attributes of an element, Blue Prism tries to identify the region on the user interface that matches the pixels on the picture that are assigned to the element. This means if the software robot is to press an element in a process, Blue Prism searches the screen for the perfect match of the saved image. As soon as the image is found, it is pressed. Region mode sounds simple but is unsafe when an application has user interface changes. For example, when just a slight change is made in the appearance, such as a color change of a button, then Blue Prism won't be able to identify the element, as the pixels are not matching anymore. For this reason, the Region mode is only used as an emergency solution in cases where none of the other modes work.

Overall Blue Prism offers solutions for spying most applications. However, the approaches are often very diverse and hardly documented, making it difficult to understand the individual spy methods down to the technical detail. With regard to a platform-independent RPA modeling language, this already poses various problems. One of them is the existence of all these different spy methods in Blue Prism. Each of these methods is optimized for a specific type of application. This means that not only a single spy method would have to be developed, but all the different spy methods supported by Blue Prism would have to be replicated in order to create processes for different types of applications within the platform-independent modeling language. In addition, there is the technical difficulty of having to implement these custom spy methods in such a way that they are compatible with Blue Prism. This means that the externally developed spy methods must also be adapted in such a way that the spied elements can be integrated into the Blue Prism Application Modeler.

Even if it were theoretically possible to import a spied element into the Blue Prism Application Modeler, there is still a great chance that it would not be compatible and efficient. As an RPA developer, it's often necessary to experiment when identifying elements. Different attributes have to be tested and tried to ensure that the correct and appropriate combination of attributes have been selected. This is often necessary that the elements, such as a button, for example, can be clearly identified by Blue Prism. Attributes that would be imported may not be optimal, which may cause the Blue Prism software to work inconsistently with identifying imported elements. This means that if elements could not be found efficiently, additional customization would be required anyway. Such additional manual adjustments would be unnecessary and time-consuming. Instead, the elements could directly be spied in the Blue Prism Application Modeler rather than spying, importing, and then editing them again.

In conclusion, importing an Application Modeler or spied elements for Blue Prism is very complicated and difficult to do, if possible, at all. The technical and structural challenges are enormous, even if the focus is only on a single RPA software. If it is almost impossible or extremely difficult for an application such as Blue Prism to import the spied elements, the question arises as to how this can be achieved for a platform-independent modeling language, which would be able to import spied elements into multiple different RPA software. For this to be feasible several RPA providers would have to use the same or at least very similar methods. If this is not the case, having a platform-independent RPA modeling language that can also spy elements would be very complex and unrealistic to achieve. In order to be able to judge this more precisely, the second RPA software UiPath must be examined to determine whether or not similar approaches are used to spy on elements.

When analyzing UiPath, it becomes clear pretty fast, that different approaches and techniques to spy out elements on the user interface are used. Whereas in Blue Prism the developer has to choose the spying mode, in UiPath the automatic mode is set as default. Another difference is that UiPath does not have an Application Modeler like Blue Prism, where all the spying is done. Spying an element in UiPath is simply done on the modeled block itself. To identify elements, UiPath uses so-called "Selectors", these are comparable to the attributes in the Blue Prism application modeler. These selectors are set automatically by UiPath when choosing an element on the user interface. But just like in Blue Prism, these selectors can be manipulated manually too.

Comparing the spying of a browser element in UiPath with the spying in Blue Prism reveals many differences in the approaches of each software. In Blue Prism, as discussed, the HTML mode is used to spy on elements in a browser. This mode works with various attributes, one of the most common being XPath. UiPath, on the other hand, has a different approach for spying in a browser. If an element in a browser is to be spied in UiPath, no specific mode has to be chosen manually. UiPath automatically selects the appropriate mode as soon as an element is spied. Once the element has been identified, the user can view the various selectors in the properties window

of the respective activity. UiPath also provides options for manipulating and fine-tuning these selectors. But other than Blue Prism, UiPath does not use XPath as a selector for browser elements. Instead, UiPath relies on its own method for element identification in the browser, which is a fundamental difference in approach. The main mode used in UiPath is the so-called “Computer Vision”. Computer Vision is a machine-learning-based approach that uses an AI to choose optimal selectors for each element. These selectors are often a combination of image matching, text recognition, and object detection on the user interface. How exactly this technology works is not documented and therefore hidden from outsiders.

Both spying methods show that the two platforms, Blue Prism and UiPath, take completely different approaches in order to spy elements in a browser. While Blue Prism relies on different attributes such as XPath, UiPath uses a more advanced technology with its own AI-powered mechanisms to identify elements. With regard to a platform-independent modeling language, this technology from UiPath does make the spying outside of UiPath, and importing it pretty much impossible. This new AI technology, which is a company secret, is impossible to replicate and even more difficult to import from an external tool into UiPath. In other words, in UiPath, the spying of elements must be performed in the RPA software itself.

In conclusion, the development of a platform-independent RPA modeling language faces considerable challenges, particularly when it comes to spying out elements and integrating them into different platforms. As seen, Blue Prism and UiPath use completely different approaches to identify elements. Such differences in the methods make it almost impossible to implement a standardized spying method in a platform-independent modeling language. To overcome these differences, the modeling language would have to support multiple spying methods, which would be inefficient and redundant. It would not make sense to replicate every spying method, as the respective RPA software already offer sophisticated mechanisms for this. In addition, certain spying methods are highly complex and hardly replicable, such as the AI-based UiPath approach. Instead, the platform-independent solution should focus on importing process models. These models would contain the basic objects of a process. Consequently, only the process model would be imported from the platform-independent RPA modeling language into the destination RPA software. And then in a second step, the user interface elements would have to be spied out in the specific RPA software and assigned to the corresponding components of the process.

To summarize, this means that a platform-independent modeling language may be able to import process models, but the actual spying of the elements must take place within the specific RPA software. Platform-independent spying and subsequent import into different RPA software is not practicable due to the different techniques and approaches of the existing tools. Consequently, the focus of this project is set to develop a prototype modeling language that can be used to import a process model into various RPA software. But before such a modeling language can be developed it is necessary to know which elements and building blocks exist within each RPA software. Only after the identification of the most important modeling elements in RPA, it is possible to create

a platform-independent modeling language. Therefore, in the next chapter, these building blocks for RPA processes are examined and defined.

5.3 Core Elements of RPA: Analyzing the Essential Building Blocks

In modern computing, the range of interactions that users perform with their devices through the keyboard and mouse is very wide. These include precise mouse movements and targeted clicks, or the most basic keystrokes. Such everyday actions provide the basis for robotic process automation technologies since RPA makes it possible to replicate precisely these human actions using software robots. By replicating many of these actions a user would make it possible to create and automate an entire process using RPA. As seen earlier, within Blue Prism or UiPath, these actions are modular building blocks that can be assembled into entire processes. But what types of actions and building blocks exist within these two RPA software?

This chapter focuses on exactly this question in order to answer the first research question (RQ1) formulated, “What key elements and concepts are necessary to represent RPA processes in a modeling language?”. Hence, the main goal is to identify the most important actions and building blocks that are used in an RPA process. In order to gain an in-depth understanding of these key elements, a detailed analysis of the two RPA providers Blue Prism and UiPath is carried out. The objective of this evaluation is to precisely identify and categorize the essential and basic building blocks used to create an RPA process.

This means in a first step; the focus is on the core actions to illustrate the concept of a universal modeling language for RPA. These fundamental elements form the basis for the modeling language prototype and clarify the underlying concept. Which means, first only the most basic elements are identified, in order to create the first version of the modeling language. In a subsequent phase, it is possible to extend the modeling language by adding further building blocks, thereby increasing its scope and effectiveness. Consequently, in the following analysis, only the main and most basic elements are examined, to create the prototype of a platform-independent RPA modeling language.

5.3.1 Blue Prism

The first RPA software in the analysis is Blue Prism. One of the central components of Blue Prism are the so-called “stages”. A total of 28 different types of stages are listed in the Blue Prism documentation (Blue Prism, n.d.-d). These building blocks are parts of the modular system with which a user can model processes. For this, the user can step by step drag and drop the desired stages, in order to model the process. Each stage type represents a specific action or task within a process. They range from simple operations such as reading and writing data to more complex functions

such as decision-making or exception handling. This wide variety of building blocks gives Blue Prism its flexibility and power that allows users to model almost any business process.

Despite the large list of stage types, it is worth noting that not all of them are necessary in order to model a simple process. An example of this is the “Note stage”, which is mainly used to leave descriptions or notes directly in the modeled process. Even if it can be helpful to take notes during the modeling phase, it is not an essential stage for an RPA process. For this reason, less relevant stages such as the “Note stage” are ignored in this phase. As the focus is now only on the fundamental and most basic stages that are essential to automate an RPA process.

The most simple and intuitive building blocks required for modeling a process in Blue Prism are the start and end of a process. Blue Prism provides the “Start” and “End” stages for this purpose. As each process obviously starts and ends somewhere, this is where those building blocks come into play. Otherwise, these two-stage types are pretty much self-explanatory and require no further investigation. Besides the start and end, there are multiple other stages that are very important, as these directly interact with the user interface of an application. Three such of them are the “Navigate”, “Write” and “Read” stages. Contrary to the start and end a bit more investigation needs to be done on them.

The “Navigate” stage in Blue Prism is an element used to perform multiple different tasks on the user interface of a target application. Including actions such as clicking buttons, closing windows, or sending keyboard input (Blue Prism, n.d.-b). Therefore, this stage enables a wide range of possibilities to recreate interactive actions on the user interface. These are actions that a user typically performs on the user interface of a program or website. For example, the navigate stage can be used to execute a mouse click on a specific button. Such an interaction is a standard way of navigation within a web application or desktop program and therefore also one of the most important actions in any RPA process. Additionally, to the mouse clicks, the navigate Stage allows the execution of keyboard shortcuts. One example would be the classic copy-paste shortcut, Ctrl+C to copy and Ctrl+V to paste text. Such shortcuts can significantly increase the variability of actions done by a software robot and therefore increase the efficiency of automated processes. In summary, the Navigate Stage makes it possible to automate a large number of actions that any user performs with the mouse and keyboard on the user interface of a program.

Another key building block for data input in a Blue Prism process is the “Write” stage. This stage allows text or data in general to be entered into applications (Blue Prism, n.d.-e). Which, along with mouse clicks, is one of the main activities that a user performs on the interface of a program. A good example of the use of the Write stage is the automation of the login process by entering a username and password. For this, two write stages are required, which contain the username for one and the password for the other write stage as an input. By adding a navigate stage that executes the click on the login button, a complete login process can now be modeled and automated in Blue Prism. This synergetic use of both stages makes it possible to precisely

imitate and efficiently automate the entire login process by first entering the login data and then executing the login by clicking the login button.

After looking at how user input is automated by the write and navigate Stages in Blue Prism, the read Stage now comes into play. The read stage makes it possible to read data from the target application and save it (Blue Prism, n.d.-c). This is used to capture information, similar to a person reading content on a screen. One use case for a read stage is when in a business process data needs to be transferred from a program to an Excel file. In this case, the required information can be extracted from the program using a read stage and then inserted into the Excel spreadsheet using a write stage. In order to save the read data, either a single data item stage or a collection stage is needed. These are both stage types used to store information which has been read in a process or information that will be written during the process.

In conclusion, in Blue Prism, the three stages Navigate, Read, and Write form the essential building blocks that are necessary for automating a process. These are complemented by the start and end stages, which give each process a clear beginning and a defined end to round off the whole structure. Many others, such as the Note stage have much less importance and are therefore left out for the first version of the prototype. The stages that store information could be argued are very helpful and necessary in order to create an RPA process. But as in this project, the main goal is to make a working platform-independent modeling language, these are also left out in order to keep the prototype simple. But in a later phase, the prototype can then be expanded with further stages in order to complete the modeling language. In conclusion, the main and basic elements of a Blue Prism RPA process have been identified. Hence, the next step is to do the same for UiPath, with the goal of comparing and identifying the results.

5.3.2 UiPath

Next, the second software UiPath is examined in more detail, in order to compare it with Blue Prism. As already explained, different types of “stages” are used within Blue Prism, these are known as “activities” in UiPath. Activities in UiPath are very similar to Blue Prism stages in terms of their functionality and area of application. UiPath provides an extensive library of hundreds of pre-built activities that are specifically tailored for a variety of applications. These include customized solutions for Microsoft software products such as Excel (UiPath, n.d.-a). In addition, UiPath offers a wide range of basic user interface automation activities that can be used universally for various applications to address automation needs effectively and efficiently. These are provided in the “UI Automation activity package”.

UiPath’s UI Automation activity package provides a comprehensive set of tools that allow users to interact with the graphical user interface of applications in a human-like manner. This toolkit includes over 25 activities that perform behaviors such as clicking buttons, entering text

into fields, and supports the automation of complex and routine business processes (UiPath, n.d.-d). Analogous to the “Read” and “Write” stages in Blue Prism, UiPath offers equivalent functions through the “Get Text” and “Type Into” activities (UiPath, n.d.-g). These make it possible to capture text or enter it into text fields, thus offering a direct equivalent to the Read and Write stages in Blue Prism.

In terms of the execution of mouse clicks, UiPath has taken a different approach than Blue Prism. On the one hand, Blue Prism executes mouse clicks with the “Navigate” stage, which can perform a range of other navigation tasks such as keyboard shortcuts. On the other hand, UiPath offers a more single-action approach with its “Click” activity. This activity is designed to execute mouse clicks only. Therefore, UiPath provides a more targeted solution for such actions (UiPath, n.d.-e). Such a distinction shows that UiPath offers a dedicated method of automating mouse clicks, as opposed to the broader functionality that Blue Prism provides with its Navigate stage. But this also means that UiPath needs an extra activity in order to execute shortcuts. This is reflected in the “Keyboard Shortcut” activity, which was developed specifically for the execution of key combinations, such as copy (CTRL+C) and paste (CTRL+V) (UiPath, n.d.-f). Overall, UiPath offers more activities that are specialized for a single action. Contrary to Blue Prism which integrated multiple functionalities into their Navigate stage.

However, the way of executing mouse clicks is not the only difference when comparing Blue Prism and UiPath. As seen Blue Prism uses specific “Start” and “End” stages to define the beginning and ending for each process. For this, UiPath takes a different approach in its process models. In UiPath, the structure of a process is determined by the design of the workflow. This means there is no need for an explicit start and end activity. The start of a process in UiPath is just defined by the first and the end by the last activity in the workflow. This means that the starting activity can vary depending on the first step of the process. The developer just has to specify the activity with which the workflow begins, and this defines the starting point of the process. The same goes for the end of a process, which is determined by the last activity in the workflow. As soon as a UiPath software robot has executed this final activity, the process naturally ends. A practical example of a process model in UiPath could be, that the start point is defined by opening a particular application, while the endpoint is reached by closing that application.

In addition to the activities already mentioned, UiPath offers a wide variety of other activities. Exactly like in Blue Prism, many more or less useful activities can be used in different scenarios. Whereas some activities and stages are very similar to each other, but also many are very different from each other. Overall, both RPA providers have common building blocks but also each offers its own approach in the form of activities and stages. However, this study focuses on the most important core activities that are essential for automating a process. This means the less important activities in UiPath are not examined. Overall, the most important actions are covered by the three activities Click, Get Text, and Type into. In conclusion, UiPath offers similar activities in comparison to the stages in Blue Prism but in some cases, a slightly different approach is taken

by each software. Hence, in the next section, the findings of the last two chapters are summarized and conclusions are drawn.

5.3.3 Defining Core RPA Elements

After carefully analyzing two leading providers in the field of RPA software, Blue Prism and UiPath, the focus is on identifying common elements. These findings serve as the basis for the development of a uniform modeling language that is designed to be applicable and transferable to both software. This means, that for each action that can be modeled in the platform-independent modeling language, there should be a matching activity in UiPath and stage in Blue Prism. The main actions that were identified for both RPA software are reading and writing text and mouse clicks. In the next paragraphs, these actions from UiPath and Blue Prism are compared, in order to then create the platform-independent RPA modeling language.

As it has been examined, both tools follow similar strategies for reading and writing data, with Blue Prism using the “Read” and “Write” stages and UiPath using the “Get Text” and “Type Into” activities. This parallel makes the development of a universal modeling language considerably easier: it makes sense to define one class for reading and one for writing data in order to include these basic actions in the modeling language. Each of these classes can then easily be transferred from the platform-independent modeling language into either Blue Prism or UiPath.

When dealing with mouse clicks, Blue Prism and UiPath take different approaches. Blue Prism uses the “Navigate” stage as a versatile building block that can be used for both mouse clicks and other types of interactions, such as keystrokes. UiPath, on the other hand, has multiple activities, each specialized for one single type of interaction. This includes the “Click” activity which is specially used for mouse clicks. Other dedicated activities in UiPath are then used for different tasks, which would all be executed in a Blue Prism navigate stage. To minimize complexity and focus on the basic actions for the universal modeling language, the “Navigate” stage in Blue Prism can be limited to the function of mouse clicks. This makes it possible to define a unique class for navigation actions with the mouse. This means in the universal modeling language the Navigate class would be equal to the “click” activity in UiPath and also to the “Navigate” stage in Blue Prism. Hence, when a navigate element is transferred from the platform-independent modeling language to Blue Prism, then it would be necessary that the click action is chosen on the imported element. For UiPath this is not necessary, as it would automatically be a “Click” activity when imported.

Lastly, Blue Prism and UiPath follow different concepts with regard to the modeling of process starts and ends. While Blue Prism uses explicit “start” and “end” stages to mark the beginning and end of a process, UiPath defines these points implicitly through the first and last elements within a workflow. This differentiation requires a compromise in the development of a universal modeling

language. As the modeling language either has to include start and end classes or not. Overall, the implementation of “start” and “end” elements within the universal RPA modeling language provides benefits by giving each process a clear boundary and structure. This explicit start and end of a process model would facilitate the understanding and navigation within the process. But this would mean that the translation into a UiPath model, where start and end activities do not exist, would be a challenge in this project. A solution that leaves the start and end elements away would be required when translating a model into UiPath in order that a model can be imported correctly. On the other hand, if the platform-independent modeling language does not include a start and end class, then a special solution for Blue Prism would be needed. Therefore, it makes sense to include start and end elements in order to have more clarity in the initial model and then find a solution to leave them out when transferring to UiPath.

In conclusion, by identifying and analyzing the central building blocks and actions for RPA processes, the essential elements necessary for creating a platform-independent RPA language could be worked out and thus successfully answer the research question one (RQ 1). Following these examinations, a universal modeling language can be developed that aims to represent the most essential actions of an RPA process. Whereas the three basic interactions that can be found in both tools are mouse clicks, writing, and reading. Together with a clearly defined start and end point of each process, the foundation of a platform-independent RPA modeling language can be built. Five core classes thus crystallize as the basis: “Start”, “End”, “Navigate”, “Read” and “Write”. This structure provides a solid framework for universally representing the elementary functions in RPA processes. Additionally, as mentioned at the beginning of the chapter, this basic concept offers the possibility of being expanded in later phases by adding further actions. In conclusion, this chapter examined all the main components of the platform-independent RPA modeling language. The next step and goal of the following chapter is to develop the modeling language within the ADOxx software.

5.4 Implementation of the Modeling Language within ADOxx

In the earlier phases, the planning of the prototype and its requirements were defined. Now in the third phase, two low-fidelity prototypes were made, whereas one displays the modeling language that is to be developed. Before the actual development could start, a few things needed to be examined and understood. On the one hand, how an actual RPA software works. On the other hand, the core elements and building blocks for an RPA modeling language were elaborated. With this knowledge and information, it should be possible to develop an RPA modeling language with which basic processes can be modeled and thus answering the second research question (RQ 2), “How can a modeling language that represents RPA processes be technically implemented?”. Exactly this is the goal in this chapter. It is intended to be a simple first version of the modeling language, which can still be expanded and improved later. The aim is to have a first prototype with which the concept of a platform-independent RPA modeling language can be implemented

and demonstrated. As specified in an earlier phase, this prototype is created within the ADOxx software. Hence, the details described in this chapter and the following subchapters are largely based on the official ADOxx documentation (ADOxx, n.d.).

The implementation of a modeling language in ADOxx begins with the creation of a new library in the Development Toolkit. This library serves as a container for all classes of the modeling language. These classes are then implemented within this library in a further step. There are two main types of classes used in ADOxx: the regular classes and the relation classes. Regular classes represent the basic objects within the modeling language. Relation classes, on the other hand, define the relationships between these objects. Relations allow complex structures and interactions to be represented within the model. In the RPA modeling language, each regular class represents one action, such as for example reading data. As defined in the last chapter, the aim is to create the following five classes: “Start”, “End”, “Navigate”, “Read” and “Write”. Each of these classes in the library consists of various attributes that can be defined and adapted as required. These attributes determine the properties of the respective class and are decisive for the exact modeling and functionality of the language. There are various standard attributes that can simply be adopted, or completely individual attributes can be created for a single class. In order to develop such classes and attributes, the ADOxx toolkit provides a great environment. This means the entire process of defining and implementing classes and their attributes takes place in the ADOxx Development Toolkit. Hence, the goal of the following chapters is to explain the creation of the modeling language within the ADOxx toolkit. However certain details such as importing an empty library or user management in ADOxx are not explained in this chapter. A detailed description of these aspects would go beyond the scope of this chapter and is only of minor importance for the actual project. The focus of this chapter is rather on the definition of classes and their attributes, which form the foundation of the modeling language.

The explanation of the implementation of the modeling language is structured in the following way: In the first sub-chapter, the attributes “ClassName”, “Object-id”, “Class cardinality”, “AttrRep”, “Input”, and “GraphRep” are explained in detail. These attributes have been specifically adapted and edited for individual classes in order to optimize the functionality and display of the models in ADOxx. In the second sub-chapter, all five classes and the relation class are defined. At the same time, each attribute used in the respective class is customized. Finally, in the last part an example process, using the created modeling language is developed and explained. Lastly, to conclude this chapter and an important part of the project, a first conclusion is drawn. An initial assessment of the defined requirements that have been set in advance of the prototype is performed.

5.4.1 Attribute Definition and Customization

Each created class in ADOxx has several attributes, some of which can be edited and adapted depending on the needs of the modeling language. Additionally, new attributes can be defined

and implemented in any class. Hence, the objective of this chapter is to explain the various attributes used in the RPA modeling language and show what they are used for. The most important attributes are examined in detail and then later assigned to the corresponding classes. It is important to understand which attribute stands for what. Such that in the next step each class and its assigned attributes can be explained in a comprehensive manner. This structured view provides a clear understanding of the customization of attributes in ADOxx.

Before starting with the first attribute, it is to know, that every attribute in ADOxx has a specific type. There are a variety of attribute types, similar to any programming language, such as integer, string, or special types for date and time. However, the most important and most frequently used attribute types are integer and string. An integer attribute represents a numerical value and is often used to store values such as IDs or counting variables. A string attribute, on the other hand, is a sequence of symbols that can contain up to 3699 symbols. These two types are particularly important in this prototype as they are used for most attributes in this modeling language. Next, the first attribute can be examined.

The first attribute “ClassName” is a basic attribute of any class. It gives the class its specific name and serves as an identifier within the model. By naming a class, its identity and purpose within the model are clearly defined, which makes the model structure easier to understand and comprehend. The type for this attribute is “STRING”. Most names of the classes have already been mentioned and were chosen so that it is immediately clear what the class stands for. The classes of the objects are “Start”, “End”, “Read”, “Write” and “Navitage”. This means that the attribute “ClassName” is set accordingly for these classes. Only the relation class in the library has not been named yet. Hence, “Flow” is chosen for the relation class in this prototype. The naming is straightforward since the relation class connects the objects in a model and therefore indicates the flow of the process. Consequently, the attribute “ClassName” is defined as “Flow” for the only relation class in the prototype.

Another fundamental attribute is the “object-id”. This attribute assigns a unique identification number to each single object. When creating an object in the ADOxx modeling toolkit an object-id is generated automatically as soon as the object is placed in a model. This unique ID is of type “EXPRESSION”, which means the value of the attribute consists of a formula. In this case, the formula that defines the object-id is “EXPR type:integer expr:fixed:(objid)”. By execution of this formula, the value of the object-id attribute is created and assigned to its object. This value can then be retrieved and displayed in the object itself. How and where this is represented is discussed in a later attribute. The ID consists of a five-digit number, whereas each object and relation receives its own unique number. This ensures that each element within the model has a unique identifier. This unique identification enables precise assignment and management of each component within the model, which will be of great use in a later stage when the model is to be transferred from ADOxx to an RPA software. For this reason, each of the five classes in the modeling language has the attribute “object-id”. The relation class “Flow” does not use the attribute, but

each relation element in the model still has an object-id which simply remains in the background.

Next comes an attribute that gives rules and restrictions to each class and therefore to the overall model. The “Class Cardinality” attribute in ADOxx is used to define and maintain a correct semantic structure for models. One set of rules that can be implemented is the frequency with which an object of a certain class may occur in a model. This means a rule can be set up, in which the minimum and maximum values of how often an object of a certain class is allowed to appear in one model. The definition “max-objects: 1”, for example, specifies that a class only occurs a maximum of once in a model. On the other hand, a minimum number can be set with “min-objects”. These specifications make sure that the structure of the model meets the desired requirements and that there are no unnecessary or missing objects.

In addition to the frequency of objects, the attribute Class Cardinality also allows the number of relations between objects to be defined. It can be determined how many outgoing and incoming connections are allowed for an object of this class. Again, both the minimum and maximum values can be defined in order to control the desired links between the classes. For example, “min-outgoing: 1” specifies that an object of this class must have at least one outgoing relation. Conversely, “max-outgoing” can be used to set an upper limit for the number of outgoing relations. Of course, the same can also be defined for incoming relations with “max-incoming” and “min-incoming”. Such restrictions help to control the complexity of the model and therefore ensure that only the defined number of allowed connections between objects are made.

Lastly, the Class Cardinality attribute allows the definition of how often a given class can be connected to another specific class. For example, it can be defined that objects of class X must have at least one connection to objects of class Y. Ensuring that certain logical and necessary relationships between classes are present if needed. Additionally, with such restrictions, it can also be defined that a certain class can not be connected to another specific class. Ensuring that no forbidden connections are made between restricted classes. Essentially, these restrictions serve to prevent the creation of models that do not make sense or cannot be implemented in practice. To further facilitate the modeling process, it is possible to specify in the ADOxx Development Toolkit that incorrect modeling is displayed directly by a pop-up. For example, the user can be prevented from placing too many objects of a restricted class by receiving a corresponding error message. This immediate feedback helps to identify and correct errors at an early stage. Which makes up for a more efficient and error-free model development for a user. Thus, further increasing the quality and consistency of the models created.

Next, a custom-made attribute “Input”, which is used exclusively for the “Write” class is introduced. “Input” is simply an attribute that saves an entry of type string. This means that it can contain either numbers, text, or a combination of both in string form. As the “Input” attribute can be used to store any string of up to 3699 symbols, it can be used for short textual information such as usernames, passwords, or also larger-sized texts. The main purpose of this attribute is to

provide the text that the robot is to enter as input in a process. For example, when in a process a string has to be written into a text box, then it is the content of this attribute that will be used as input. In this case, during the modeling of a “Write” object, the text input must be entered in the corresponding object and saved there. In order to display and manipulate this attribute in an object of a “Write” class, it is necessary to introduce the next attribute.

“AttrRep” is sort of a notebook for a class object. This notebook can be opened when modeling an object of any class containing said attribute in the ADOxx Modeling toolkit. To do this, the placed object must be opened with a double-click. Various things can then be edited or viewed in it, depending on what has been defined in the AttrRep attribute of this class. Various elements are available to define the AttrRep attribute to create a notebook. Firstly, there are the chapters. Each notebook must contain at least one chapter in order to display the values of other attributes. In each of the chapters, individual or multiple attributes can be defined. Each chapter is a page in itself on which then all the displayed attributes can be viewed and manipulated. These attributes can be the object-id, for example. This means that during modeling, the user always has the option of opening an object and seeing what the object-id is in the object’s notebook.

A notebook is created for all classes, except for the “Flow” relation class. Each notebook contains specific chapters and attributes that support the purpose and function of the respective class. All classes, that have a notebook, contain the “Debug” and “General” chapters. The chapter “Debug” contains the “object-id” attribute, which represents the ID of the object. This attribute is important in order to uniquely identify and manage each object. The second chapter “General” contains the “Name” attribute. This attribute is used to give the individual objects a name that can be adapted to their function. This name can be edited as desired in the notebook of an object. As a result, this also has an influence on the visual appearance of certain classes. But more on this in the next segment. In addition, the notebook of the “Write” class also contains the “Input” attribute, which was introduced in the section above. This attribute is also displayed in the “General” chapter of each Write objects notebook. This attribute is used to specify the input that is to be written in the RPA process. It therefore enables precise definition and management of the content that is processed by the Write class. This structured organization of the notebooks ensures that the models remain clear and organized, while all necessary information and functions are easily accessible. This contributes significantly to the efficiency and quality of modeling in ADOxx.

Last but not least, the attribute “GraphRep” plays a central role in modeling with ADOxx, as it defines the graphical representation of a class. GraphRep can be used to precisely define how an object of a class is visually represented in the ADOxx toolkit. Various parameters can be manipulated and designed such as its shape, color, or labeling. To create the desired design different style elements can be used such as shadows, font styles, or a pen that can be used to draw lines. GraphRep also allows the usage of other attributes in order to create a dynamic visual design. For example, the name that can be set in the notebook for each object can be used as a variable that is then displayed on the object. This enables a clear and intuitive visualization of the model struc-

tures, which significantly improves the comprehensibility and readability of the model. GraphRep is of type “LONGSTRING”, which means the value to define the graphical representation is a text which is then interpreted by ADOxx. Each visual representation of the classes are discussed and shown later. However as defined in phase one, the requirement for the visual representation of the prototype is of low priority. Therefore, the design of each class remains simple and efficient.

With GraphRep explained, all important attributes have been examined. In the table 5.1 all elementary attributes are listed with their type and functionality.

Attribute	Type	Function
ClassName	String	Name of the class
Object-id	Expression	Unique identifier for each object
Class cardinality	String	Restrictions and rules for class objects
AttrRep	Longstring	Notebook
Input	String	Data input that is to be written in a process
GraphRep	Longstring	Graphical representation of class objects

Table 5.1: Attributes, Types, and Functions

In conclusion, the main and most important attributes of the platform-independent RPA modeling language were explained. This knowledge is an important basis for a better understanding of the next chapter, in which all the classes and their attributes are developed. Hence, the next section describes the development of all classes of the modeling language, which enable the creation and modeling of basic RPA processes.

5.4.2 Creation and Configuration of the Classes

After multiple different attributes, were explored and explained, the next step is to develop all the classes of the modeling language. In this chapter, the five classes “Start”, “End”, “Navigate”, “Read”, “Write” and the relation class “Flow” are implemented. At the same time, the focus lies on the configuration of all the important attributes of each class. Additionally, the visual appearance of each class is shown in a small illustration. After successfully setting up everything within ADOxx, the goal is to demonstrate the modeling language with a small example process.

The first class to set up is the only relation class in the RPA modeling language: “Flow”. For the relation class “Flow” a simple arrow is designed that points from one object to another. The arrow always indicates the direction in which the process is running. This means, that when modeling a process and connecting objects with the “Flow” relation class, it is important to start at

the object that is to be executed first, followed by the next one. Otherwise, the arrow could point in the wrong direction. The following figure demonstrates the graphic design for this class:

Figure 5.8: Relation Class: Flow

The left side of Figure 5.8 represents the code, that is implemented in the “GraphRep” attribute of the class, which translates to the graphical representation on the right part of the figure. First, the “SHADOW off” instruction switches off the shadow effect for the arrow, which means that the arrow is displayed without any additional visual effects. The line drawing is then defined with “PEN style:solid w:0.05cm”. Here, “style:solid” means that the arrow is displayed as a solid line without interruptions, and “w:0.05cm” specifies the width of the line, which in this case is 0.05 cm. “EDGE” is a context element that triggers the drawing of the above-defined line from one object to another. This code can therefore be used to draw a straight line between two elements.

To create an arrow, something must be added at the end of the line. For this, two diagonal lines are drawn, which create the arrow at the end of the line. The context element “END” defines that everything from now on is drawn at the end of the already drawn line. The first line, which forms the upper part of the arrowhead, is defined by “LINE x1:0cm y1:0cm x2:-0.2cm y2:0.1cm”. Here x1:0cm y1:0cm”. The entire system can be imagined as a coordinate system. Where x1 and y1 are the starting point of the line and x2 and y2 are the endpoints of the line. Here the starting point is at the coordinates (0/0) which represents the end of the line between the two objects. The endpoint of the line is then -0.2cm on the x-axis and 0.1cm on the y-axis. A second line for the lower part of the arrowhead is defined as “LINE x1:0cm y1:0cm x2:-0.2cm y2:-0.1cm”. However, it runs in the opposite direction along the x-axis and is therefore the mirror image of the first line. Together, these two lines create the typical arrowhead, which runs from the end of the arrow shaft to the top left and bottom left to complete the arrow shape. This graphic representation of the arrowhead helps to visualize the arrow clearly and indicates the process flow in the model.

Overall, this explanation should illustrate how exactly the graphical representation comes together in the GraphRep attribute. Altogether the relation class has no other important attributes that are implemented. Since the only purpose of this class is to connect the objects and indicate the workflow of a process. Therefore, the next step is to look at the first and last classes used when modeling an RPA process.

Both classes that define the beginning and end of a process are logically named “Start” and

“End” in their ClassName attributes. Additionally, as already mentioned both classes contain the object-id attribute in order to uniquely identify each single object in a process. This object-id is then displayed in the notebook of each Start and End object. Alongside it in the Notebook is the name of the object, which can actively be edited while modeling. As examined earlier the content of the notebook for each class is defined in the AttrRep attribute. Next, for both classes, some restrictions are implemented in the Class cardinality attribute. First, the max objects for either are set to one. As there is only one start and one endpoint in a simple RPA process, there is no need for multiple Start or End objects. Another logical restriction is, that a start object cannot have an incoming relationship, as it is always the first element. Equivalent to this restriction, End-class objects are restricted to zero outgoing relationships, as they are always the endpoint and therefore cannot have an outgoing relationship.

Lastly comes the graphical design for the End and Start class. Both classes have a similar appearance except for a small difference. Every Start and End class object is graphically represented by a circle. The only difference is that the End class has “End” and the Start class has “Start” written in the middle of the circle. Both classes have the same design, such that the start and end of a process are clear and easy to see. This is underlined by the fact, that no other class is represented by a round graphic design. On figure 5.9, both visual designs for each class can be seen.

Figure 5.9: Start and End Classes

The objects shown in Figure 5.9 are achieved by two simple lines. The first line “TEXT “Start” w:c h:c” adds the text “Start” and positions it centered within the graphic display. The parameters w:c and h:c stand for the horizontal and vertical centering of the text. For the End class obviously, the text displayed is set to “END”. The second line “ELLIPSE x:0cm y:0cm rx:1cm ry:1cm” defines an ellipse that draws a circle around the word “Start” or “End”. The center of the ellipse is located at the coordinates x:0cm and y:0cm. The parameters rx:1cm and ry:1cm define the radius of the ellipse so that it has a radius of 1 cm in the horizontal and vertical directions. Combined, these elements result in a graphical representation in which the text “Start”, or “End” is displayed centered within a perfectly round circle. In this way, the start and end of each model is clearly visible. Overall, the Start and End classes have both very similar attributes and visual representations. Next up are the three classes which contain all the actions in an RPA process.

The three classes that define all main actions in an RPA process “Read”, “Write” and “Navigate” are named accordingly in the ClassName attribute. Also, each of these classes has the

attribute object-id which is represented in the Notebook alongside with the name of the object. Overall, all three classes have very similar attributes, except for the Write stage which has the additional attribute “Input”. As discussed earlier the Input attribute is represented in the notebook of each Write object with the goal of storing the text input that is to be written when executing the process in an RPA software. Additionally, each of the classes have the same restrictions in the Class Cardinality attribute. These rules are that each object has a maximum of one outgoing and one incoming relationship. Obviously, in large and complex RPA processes, it would very well be possible that some specific objects can have multiple outgoing or incoming paths. But as this modeling language is kept simple and avoids complex processes, the setup of such restrictions makes sense. Finally, in the last part, the visual design of these three classes is examined.

In the last attribute “GraphRep” each of the three classes Read, Write, and Navigate gets an edgy-shaped visual design, in order to have a clear distinction between them and the Start and End classes. But at the same time, it should be ensured that these three classes can also be visually differentiated from one another. For this purpose, these three classes are designed in a rectangular shape, each with its own distinct form. The simplest design of these three classes comes from the “Navigate” class with a simple rectangle. The line “RECTANGLE x:-1.5cm y:-0.5cm w:3cm h:1cm” draws a simple rectangle starting from the coordinates x: -1.5cm and y: -0.5cm. From there on a box with the width of 3cm and height of 1cm is drawn. Figure 5.10 displays the navigate class and its GraphRep code.

Figure 5.10: Navigate Class

The instruction “ATTR ‘Name’ x:0cm y:0cm w:c:3.5cm h:c:1cm” defines a text field for displaying the name of an object. ATTR represents the element in the Notebook in which the name of the object can be set. In the example given, the name of the object is “Click Button”. This representation makes it possible to give each object in a model a specific name for its action. For example, the name “Click Button” indicates that this Navigate object refers to a mouse click on a button. The name can be chosen by the developer of the model while modeling. Such naming helps with the clarity and interpretation of the model. Instead of having 5 objects with the name “Navigate” in a model, each Navigate object can be named individually depending on its function.

Exactly the same is built into the design for the “Write” and “Read” classes. This means that these individual objects can also each be given a name. The only difference for these two classes is the design of the box, which is drawn around the name of the object. Just like the Navigate class, the Write class has a rectangular shape. The right side is shaped to a point so that these objects can be visually distinguished from Navigate objects.

Figure 5.11: Write Class

As can be seen in Figure 5.11, the style element “LINE” is used to draw three lines that form the box. The right-hand side, on the other hand, is formed with the style element “POLYLINE”. The instruction “POLYLINE 3 x1:1.5cm y1:-0.5cm x2:2.0cm y2:0.0cm x3:1.5cm y3:0.5cm” makes it possible to draw a line sequence that runs over several points and thus forms uneven line segments. In this particular case, three coordinates are defined so that the line contains a corner. This arrangement of points creates a line that first runs from the point (1.5, -0.5) to the point (2.0, 0.0) and then forms a corner to finally reach the point (1.5, 0.5). The same is done for the class “Read”, except that the second coordinate (1.0, 0.0) in the “POLYLINE” element is shifted 1cm to the left and thus the shape is mirrored. Figure 5.12 shows the code and the image of the “Read” class. Here with the example name “Read Text” for this object.

Figure 5.12: Read Class

Overall, the three main classes Read, Navigate, and Write have a similar shape, but each has its own unique look. This is necessary in order to be able to instantly recognize each object by its class. This will help any user to quickly understand what is happening in the process and therefore the modeling language offers some user-friendliness. Additionally, the display of the object name in the design adds a lot to this. Since at first glance, it can be identified what each object stands for. This brings the benefit that an external person does not need much effort to understand what the individual objects in the process stand for.

The table 5.2 sums up all created classes and each corresponding attribute. A green checkmark means that the class has this attribute, while a red cross means that this class does not contain the attribute. In the GraphRep column the object design is once more shown for each class.

ClassName	GraphRep	Object-id	AttrRep	Class cardinality	Input
Start		✓	✓	✓	✗
End		✓	✓	✓	✗
Read		✓	✓	✓	✗
Write		✓	✓	✓	✓
Navigate		✓	✓	✓	✗
Flow		✗	✗	✗	✗

Table 5.2: Classes and Attributes

Finally, with all the necessary classes and attributes specified, it is possible to form the Meta-model for the defined modeling language. Figure 5.13 displays the UML class diagram of the metamodel of the developed modeling language. This diagram provides a graphical representation of the classes listed above in the table, their attributes and relationships. It illustrates how the various elements of the modeling language are connected to each other and which logical structures underlie them. Compared to the tabular representation, the UML diagram provides a clearer and more systematic overview of the modeling language.

Figure 5.13: UML Class Diagram: Metamodel of the RPA Modeling Language

In conclusion, this chapter gave an overview of all six classes that were created in order to develop the modeling language. Additionally, for each class all the important attributes were explained. Now that everything has been developed, the next step is to create a first example process

in order to demonstrate the modeling language in action. Hence, in the next chapter, a small process is illustrated, followed by a conclusion and overall evaluation of the platform-independent RPA modeling language that has been created within ADOxx.

5.4.3 Practical Example and Evaluation

In order to bring the previous developments together and illustrate the modeling language, a small example model is presented. This example illustrates the application of the described classes and attributes in a concrete scenario. The process selected is a simple login process that occurs every day in a wide variety of situations. For example, when logging into any application at work or a personal account of some sort. This simple example is intended to illustrate the basic principles of modeling an RPA process in ADOxx with the created modeling language. This process, which many of us use in everyday life, includes the following steps: type username, type password, and then click the login button. The process begins with the “Start” class, which marks the start of the process. This is followed by two “Write” classes, which are responsible for entering the username and password. Each of these classes contains the “Input” attribute, which in this case represents the username and password entered. As described earlier, once the object has been placed in the process, the input must be set manually. To do this, the object must be opened with a double-click and then, for example, the username that is to be entered can be defined.

Next, the “Navigate” class is used in order to represent the mouse click on the login button. This object is the last interactive action in the process. No additional input is needed for the navigate object since the action consists only of a button click. After completing the navigate object, the last step in the model is reached, the “End” class object. With the execution of the end object, the process is completed. This means that in practice the user should be successfully logged in.

Figure 5.14 shows the entire model, illustrating the use of different class objects to create and understand the simple login process in ADOxx. Overall, the defined attributes played a central role in this by enabling a clear structure and comprehensible representation of the process. One example for this are the class cardinalities that have been strictly adhered to in order to ensure the integrity and correctness of the process. This means, for example, that only a single relation emanates from the “Start” object, and its counterpart the “End” object has only one incoming relation. Moreover, there is only one object of each of the classes “Start” and “End”, exactly as defined in the attribute “Class cardinality”. Compliance with these cardinalities ensures that the model meets the defined requirements and therefore represents a valid and functioning model.

Figure 5.14: Login Process Model

Another example is the use of the attribute “GraphRep” and the user-defined names that can be set in the Notebook allowing the attributes to be given the desired name and look. The ability to assign an individual name to each object means that the various steps in the login process can be clearly identified. For example, the objects of the Write class were named “Write Username” and “Write Password”, and the Navigate object was given the name “Click Login Button”. These names ensure that the purpose of each step in the process is immediately recognizable. Thanks to this clear naming and precise graphic representation, the process is easy to understand even for people who are not familiar with the specific model. At first glance, it is clear that this is a login process where a username and password are entered and then a login button is clicked.

In this case, the process is very simple and therefore easy to understand anyway. However, in reality, a business process can often be much larger and more complex than just a few individual actions. Therefore, such transparency is particularly important to ensure that the model is intuitive and understandable without prior knowledge. This means that even an outsider or an employee involved in the automation project can quickly understand and follow a process. Hence, the use of ADOxx to create clear and understandable process models is very effective. Finally, with this example, the modeling language is now complete and fully explained. Therefore, it is time to make a first conclusion in the next sections and examine whether the earlier proposed requirements are met with this prototype modeling language.

In a first step, before creating the modeling language, a wireframe was created which represents a rough concept of the modeling language. This wireframe indicated the direction in which the modeling language should go. In a second part, the most important elements of RPA modeling were then identified by analyzing two of the biggest names in RPA, Blue Prism, and UiPath. This led to the identification of 5 stages in the case of Blue Prism or activities for UiPath. These five building blocks then formed the basis of the modeling language to be developed in ADOxx. Looking at requirement number two set earlier, which demands the possibility of transferring a model into two different RPA software; these five basic stages create a good fundament for a modeling language that can be later applied to Blue Prism and UiPath. Consequently, the prototype is on the right track to accomplish this requirement.

After these important elements have been identified, the creation of a modeling language in the ADOxx Development Toolkit was described in detail. First, specific attributes were defined for the five central classes and one relation class. Specific attributes were then assigned to these classes. Each of these attributes was explained in detail and their use in the respective classes were described. With these classes and attributes, it was possible to create an RPA modeling language that covers the most important actions in an RPA process. With this being done the requirements one and three are accomplished. On the one hand, for requirement three, a modeling language within a modeling tool, in this case ADOxx, was created successfully. On the other hand, for requirement one, a modeling language that is capable of representing RPA processes was implemented. But it is worth mentioning that in the future more actions can be added to the modeling language in order to have an even more complete and distinctive modeling language. However, these basic actions in the modeling language are sufficient for the prototype and a first proof of concept.

Finally, in this chapter a simple practical example of a small login process is shown. Including the steps of entering the username and password and clicking on the login button, this process demonstrated how such a process can be modeled using the created modeling language in ADOxx. Not only the appearance of a model is demonstrated, but also the concept of how click and write actions can be used to model an RPA process that can later be used in a desired RPA software. As a result, it becomes clear that processes can be mapped clearly and comprehensibly through modeling in ADOxx, which forms the basis for successful automation. With this being said, requirement number five is also accomplished; an intuitive design of the modeling language that facilitates the use for developers. The simple and efficient design of each class makes the modeling of a process very intuitive and straightforward. Finally, for requirement number four, no conclusions can be made yet, as the script part is to be developed yet.

In conclusion, the first part of the project, the creation of an RPA modeling language in ADOxx, has been successfully implemented and therefore the second research question (RQ 2) has been covered. From here, the project is ready for the next step, which includes the transfer of a process model from ADOxx into multiple RPA software. Therefore, the following chapter

evaluates how such a model from ADOxx can be transferred to an RPA solution in order to further develop an RPA process and put it into practice.

5.5 Transferring a Process Model into RPA Software

With the completion of the RPA modeling language in ADOxx, the first stage of the project is completed and two of the three initial research questions have been covered. Consequently, the next step is to address the last remaining research question (RQ 3), “To what extent is the developed modeling language platform-independent, and how efficiently can it be applied to different RPA platforms?”. To explore this question, the project now moves into the phase of developing a solution that allows the transfer of the developed model to multiple RPA solutions, specifically Blue Prism and UiPath. This requires identifying a method that enables compatibility with both platforms. Throughout this chapter, the process of how the model developed in ADOxx can be integrated into RPA software such as Blue Prism or UiPath is described. The goal is to find a way to transfer the model from the developed modeling language in ADOxx into a format that can be used by Blue Prism or UiPath.

One key aspect that is needed in order to transform a model, is to have some sort of representation of a process, that can easily be read by a program. This means that a script can read a process, deconstruct it, and reassemble it in a way that it can be imported into an RPA software. One common language that is used to represent processes, such as BPMN for example, is XML. Since XML files have a clear and consistent structure, they offer great potential for such a transformation. This means such an XML model of an RPA process can then easily be processed by a script and rearranged in a suitable way for each RPA software. Consequently, the first step in the transformation procedure is to find a way to create an XML file out of an RPA process designed in ADOxx. How to get from an ADOxx model to an XML file is discussed in the first sub-chapter.

Having created an XML file out of an RPA process, the next step is to find a way how to transfer it to one or multiple RPA software providers. At this point one critical aspect comes into play: each RPA software uses a different approach in order to represent its processes. Therefore, for each single RPA provider, a different solution has to be built. Exactly this is to be done in the following sub-chapters. First for Blue Prism, followed by UiPath. Lastly, in order to combine both solutions, a small desktop application is built, such that the user has a simple way of transferring a process from ADOxx to either UiPath or Blue Prism.

The following chapters examine how all aspects mentioned above can be achieved. The first chapter is about exporting a process model out of ADOxx in a usable XML format which can then be worked and transferred to an RPA software. In further chapters, the goal is to understand how Blue Prism and UiPath represent objects and how these can be imported into either modeling environment. Once these basics, the export out of ADOxx, and the understanding of the representation

in the RPA software are given, a solution can be implemented. Finally, the objective is to develop a solution for both RPA software so that a model exported from ADOxx can be imported either into Blue Prism or UiPath. All the transformations and analyses of the XML files presented were developed independently, as there is no documentation for these particular components.

5.5.1 Exporting an RPA Process Model as XML File

To export a model from ADOxx, there is no need to search long, as the software itself already provides an option to export a model. One of the export features of ADOxx allows users to export any model as an XML file. Such a feature is particularly valuable for the project as XML (Extensible Markup Language) provides a flexible and widely used method of storing and exchanging data. In short, an XML file consists of a series of elements organized in a hierarchical structure. This structure makes it possible to organize data in a tree-like form, which facilitates both readability and processing. By using the export XML function, it is possible to create such a structured view of the model, which has been created in ADOxx, but in XML form.

Important to know is, that each of these generated XML files out of ADOxx follows a standardized notation and structure. Having such a specific and structured XML file of a process model provides an ideal basis for converting these files using a script or program. Enabling a usable solution to be created from the XML file, which can then be imported into an RPA software. Therefore, the XML approach enables a solid foundation for further processing of the models into various RPA environments. But to achieve this the structure and notation of an XML file created out of a ADOxx model must be understood.

To illustrate the whole concept a little better, an XML of an RPA process modeled in ADOxx is examined in the next paragraphs. As an example for exporting a model as XML, the login process already illustrated in an earlier chapter is used again. As a reminder: the login process consists following elements: Start, write username, write password, click login button, and End.

```
1 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
2 <!DOCTYPE ADOXML SYSTEM "adoxml31.dtd">
3 <ADOXML version="3.1" date="10.05.2024" time="15:16" database="adoxx18" username="
  Admin" adoversion="Version 1.8">
4 <MODELS>
5 <MODEL id="mod.41801" name="LoginProcess" version="" modeltype="RPA Model">
6 <MODELATTRIBUTES>
7 </MODELATTRIBUTES>
8 <INSTANCE id="obj.45822" class="Start" name="Start-45822">
9 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:8.25cm y:2.25cm index:1</
  ATTRIBUTE>
10 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
11 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:45822</ATTRIBUTE>
12 </INSTANCE>
13 <INSTANCE id="obj.45825" class="Write" name="Write Username">
```

```

14 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:8.25cm y:4.75cm index:2</
    ATTRIBUTE>
15 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
16 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:45825</ATTRIBUTE>
17 <ATTRIBUTE name="Input" type="STRING">USERNAME</ATTRIBUTE>
18 </INSTANCE>
19 <INSTANCE id="obj.45828" class="Write" name="Write Password">
20 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:8.25cm y:6.75cm index:3</
    ATTRIBUTE>
21 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
22 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:45828</ATTRIBUTE>
23 <ATTRIBUTE name="Input" type="STRING">PASSWORD</ATTRIBUTE>
24 </INSTANCE>
25 <INSTANCE id="obj.45831" class="Navigate" name="Click Login Button">
26 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:8.25cm y:8.75cm index:4</
    ATTRIBUTE>
27 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
28 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:45831</ATTRIBUTE>
29 </INSTANCE>
30 <INSTANCE id="obj.45837" class="End" name="End-45837">
31 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:8.25cm y:11.25cm index:5</
    ATTRIBUTE>
32 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
33 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:45837</ATTRIBUTE>
34 </INSTANCE>
35 <CONNECTOR id="con.45840" class="Flow">
36 <FROM instance="Start-45822" class="Start"/>
37 <TO instance="Write Username" class="Write"/>
38 <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:6</ATTRIBUTE>
39 </CONNECTOR>
40 <CONNECTOR id="con.45841" class="Flow">
41 <FROM instance="Write Username" class="Write"/>
42 <TO instance="Write Password" class="Write"/>
43 <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:7</ATTRIBUTE>
44 </CONNECTOR>
45 <CONNECTOR id="con.45842" class="Flow">
46 <FROM instance="Write Password" class="Write"/>
47 <TO instance="Click Login Button" class="Navigate"/>
48 <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:8</ATTRIBUTE>
49 </CONNECTOR>
50 <CONNECTOR id="con.45843" class="Flow">
51 <FROM instance="Click Login Button" class="Navigate"/>
52 <TO instance="End-45837" class="End"/>
53 <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:9</ATTRIBUTE>
54 </CONNECTOR>
55 </MODEL>
56 </MODELS>
57 </ADOXML>

```

The code above displays the exported XML file of the login process in ADOxx. In order to understand its structure, all the important elements have to be examined. On the first line is the XML Prolog declaration. It specifies that the file uses XML version 1.0 and that the character encoding is UTF-8. This is crucial for the correct interpretation of the characters in the document, especially when international characters are involved. The second line defines the document type of the XML document. It refers to an external DTD (Document Type Definition) file called

“adoxml31.dtd”. This DTD file specifies the structure and the permitted elements of the XML document, ensures that the document is formatted correctly and according to the defined rules, and supports the validation of the content.

After the declarations, an XML always begins with a root element, which is the parent of all other elements. That root element also marks the start of the document. The root element of the XML document generated in ADOxx contains metadata such as the version of the ADOXML format, the creation date and time, the database used, the username of the user who generated the model, and the ADOxx version. Subsequently, on line three, the definition of the model starts directly with the <MODEL> element, which describes the entire model. This includes the ID and the name of the model, in this case, “LoginProcess”. There is also the model type “RPA Model” defined in the library and information about the library type.

On line 6 of the XML, the element <MODELATTRIBUTES> begins, but this is hidden as it does not contain any essential information about the model itself. This element lists various attributes relating to metadata, such as the author of the model, the creation date, and the date of the last change. Although these attributes are useful for managing and tracking the model, they are not relevant to the actual structure or content of the model and are therefore not important for the next steps in the project. By hiding this data, the focus can be placed on the really relevant elements and structures of the model that are important for further steps of the project.

From line 8 onwards, the individual objects that have been placed in the model are described. These are marked with the <INSTANCE> element, and there are five of them, just as there are in the example login process model: Start, Write, Write, Navigate, and End. Within these instance elements, there are various attributes that contain important information about the respective objects. These include the class name, the name of the object, the object-id, and the position. In this case, the position is an x and y coordinate, which shows exactly where the object is located on the model.

For the Write class element, for example defined in the lines 13-18, the attribute “Input” is particularly important in the XML document as it contains the specific input values, which have to be written in the robotics process. This is important to ensure that this input value is not lost when it is transferred to the RPA software. In general, it is important that the XML contains all the information required to create the corresponding activities in UiPath and stages in Blue Prism.

From the line 35 onwards, the last four elements in the example XML document are the <CONNECTOR> elements. Simply said, these elements represent the relations between the objects. They are structured in such a way that they contain the attributes such as the class name and the ID, in this case, it is the connector-id and not an object-id. A key feature of the connector elements are the “From” and “To” attributes. The “From” attribute specifies the object from which the connection originates and includes both the name and the class of the source object. The “To” attribute

specifies the target object of the connection, also with the name and class. With such a structure, the connector elements in the XML document are able to describe the order of the objects and how they are connected to each other. Therefore, the connector elements show the flow of the process and make it possible to clearly define and understand the relationships and order of the previously defined objects.

In conclusion, the generated XML of the login process, which has been modeled in ADOxx with the developed modeling language, provides a structured and comprehensible representation of the model. It provides all the necessary data needed to be transformed into RPA software later on. Including all the essential attributes such as the name of the objects and the inputs for Write objects. All this information is crucial to create the final process which is then imported into an RPA software. Hence, the goal is to find a way to transform such an XML document so that it is applicable to different RPA software solutions, notably UiPath and Blue Prism. To achieve this, a transformation process in the form of a script needs to be developed. At the same time, this solution needs to take into account all the specific requirements and formats of these RPA platforms in order to enable smooth integration and automation of the process models. Therefore, in the next chapter, the way of how Blue Prism displays its object is examined. When this is understood, a script can be developed which enables the transformation of such an ADOxx XML file into a usable format for Blue Prism.

5.5.2 Blue Prism: Analysis of the XML Structure

Before a script that transfers an ADOxx XML file into Blue Prism is developed, it is important to understand how the software itself works, and how process models are displayed in the RPA software. Hence, in the next sections, Blue Prism is looked at and most importantly it is examined how objects and processes are displayed in it.

Blue Prism uses a drag-and-drop user interface to model individual processes. In other words, the objects or stages, as they are referred to in Blue Prism, that are to be modeled can simply be placed on the user interface. However, these stages are all prefabricated and the user does not directly see what is behind the individual stages on the user interface. But in order to import stages from outside Blue Prism onto the modeling interface, it is essential to know the underlying structure and notation. Therefore, the next sections are about understanding what is behind the drag-and-drop stages in Blue Prism.

Blue Prism uses XML as a primary format for defining and storing its process models. Meaning each stage of a process is a separate XML element of a larger XML file, similar to the exported ADOxx file. Overall, the XML structure in Blue Prism is crucial for describing the various components and their relationships within a process. However, the notation and structure of the XML file are completely different from the one generated in ADOxx. This means that in order to import

a process from outside into Blue Prism, the XML format must be understood and formatted correctly. Otherwise, the Blue Prism modeler cannot interpret the elements to be imported and place them on the user interface. This means that the exact XML notation and formatting of the individual elements and an entire process must be understood so that it can be imported into Blue Prism. For this reason, the XML notation of the elementary Blue Prism stages and a simple process are discussed in the following sections. The three lines of XML displayed below show how such a stage is defined in Blue Prism.

```
1 <stage stageid="UUID" name="Stage Name" type="Stage Type">
2   <display x="0" y="0" />
3 </stage>
```

Each stage in Blue Prism is defined in an XML within a “<stage>” element. Inside of this element, various attributes and sub-elements are used to define the characteristics of the stage. Every single stage always requires three basic attributes: “stageid”, “name” and “type”. The “stageid” attribute consists of a UUID (Universally Unique Identifier). This ensures that each individual element within a process is uniquely identifiable. Using UUIDs ensures that no two stages share the same identification number, thus avoiding confusion and conflicts within the process.

In addition to the “stageid”, the attribute “type” is essential for defining the type of stage. A type in the stage element determines what kind of object it is. In this case, for example, it can be the identified stages such as Start, End, Write, Read, or Navigate. Depending on the stage type the attribute are set accordingly. Another attribute that is used in every stage element is “name”. Each stage can be freely named using this attribute and thus offers a flexible way of describing the purpose or function of the respective process step. The name that is set in this attribute is also visible on the object itself on the user interface in Blue Prism while modeling a process.

Besides the three explained standard attributes there is one standard element which is also defined in every stage. The “<display>” element consists of two attributes: X and Y, which indicate the coordinates of the respective stage element on the user interface of the Blue Prism modeling tool. How this works is, that the Blue Prism modeling tool, uses a Cartesian coordinate system to visually represent the positions of the individual process steps. Whereas the X and Y coordinates defined in the display element determine where the stage is placed on the user interface. Therefore, coordinates in the display stage are crucial for the graphical arrangement of the process objects on the interface. Without these coordinates, all stages would be centered at the same position, which would lead to a confusing and unusable display.

For a user who just drags and drops stages on the Blue Prism interface while modeling a process, these coordinates are not directly visible. But for importing stages or a process into the Blue Prism environment, it is important that these coordinates are set correctly for each stage. This correct arrangement of the stages based on their coordinates is an important part of the transfor-

mation of a model from ADOxx to Blue Prism. Since both software have different scales and starting points on their coordinate grid of the user interface. Now that the basic elements and attributes have been explained, the individual stages can be visualized in XML form. “Start” stages, displayed in lines 1-3 and “End” stages, displayed in lines 5-7, have nothing special about them, except that the type must be set correctly as shown in the following XML lines.

```
1 <stage stageid="930f3c2a-a522-4556-8ff8-ef9e8ef1a97a" name="Start" type="Start">
2   <display x="15" y="-105" />
3 </stage>
4
5 <stage stageid="81df1fc0-a3d2-44e2-ba11-ea68336381a7" name="End" type="End">
6   <display x="15" y="90" />
7 </stage>
```

The same applies to the two stages navigate and read. Here, the type is simply set accordingly and the name of the stage can be set as desired. In the navigate stage, however, the element that defines the action, in this case for example a mouse click, is missing. The reason for this is, that the action can only be set after the UI element has been spied with the application modeler. As the application modeler is not imported into Blue Prism in this project, only a simple Navigate stage with the corresponding name will be used. Therefore, the XML element for navigate stages only includes these basic definitions. The action that is to be executed in the process must be selected manually in Blue Prism after importing the XML and after the spying of the UI element which is to be used in this stage. The following lines of XML display one Navigate and one Read stage.

```
1 <stage stageid="691ae35b-7f52-47ef-8655-33a251082b2a" name="Navigate" type="
  Navigate">
2   <display x="-30" y="-75" />
3 </stage>
4
5 <stage stageid="3ad13b18-c469-4205-bb1e-ab1d9dcc871" name="Read Text" type="Read">
6   <display x="-30" y="-30" />
7 </stage>
```

For the last stage, write, the same attributes are used with the exception of one additional element. The Write stage contains a “step” element which is embedded in the stage element. Inside it, the attribute “expr” is defined, which represents the input of the write stage. This means that if, for example, the robot is to write the value “Username” in a text field, then this attribute must be defined as “Username”. The example below displays such an element for a Write stage.

```
1 <stage stageid="6f52330e-f8de-455f-acfb-8b883e302915" name="Write Text" type="
  Write">
2   <display x="-30" y="15" />
3   <step expr="Text Input" />
4 </stage>
```

Now that the basic stages, which are used in the first prototype, have been explained, a small example process is shown and what it looks like in XML format. For this, the login process, which has been used as an example earlier in this paper, is used again for this purpose. As a reminder, the login process essentially consists of three actions: entering the username, entering the password, and then clicking on the login button. In this case, the two stages Start, and End are also included in Blue Prism, which mark the start and end of the process respectively.

```

1 <process name="__selection__Login Process">
2   <stage stageid="930f3c2a-a522-4556-8ff8-ef9e8ef1a97a" name="Anfang" type="Start"
3     >
4     <display x="15" y="-105" />
5     <onsuccess>c7c1219d-d29f-4dd6-8705-0c8a2e9c9df7</onsuccess>
6   </stage>
7   <stage stageid="81df1fc0-a3d2-44e2-ba11-ea68336381a7" name="Ende" type="End">
8     <display x="15" y="75" />
9   </stage>
10  <stage stageid="c7c1219d-d29f-4dd6-8705-0c8a2e9c9df7" name="Write Username" type
11    ="Write">
12    <display x="15" y="-60" />
13    <onsuccess>083546b9-16c8-4d56-ac8a-c31b6c90cee9</onsuccess>
14    <step expr="USERNAME" />
15  </stage>
16  <stage stageid="083546b9-16c8-4d56-ac8a-c31b6c90cee9" name="Write Password" type
17    ="Write">
18    <display x="15" y="-15" />
19    <onsuccess>14e97684-c329-4065-9240-260986dc6489</onsuccess>
20    <step expr="PASSWORD" />
21  </stage>
22    <stage stageid="14e97684-c329-4065-9240-260986dc6489" name="Click Login
23    Button" type="Navigate">
24    <display x="15" y="30" />
25    <onsuccess>81df1fc0-a3d2-44e2-ba11-ea68336381a7</onsuccess>
26  </stage>
27 </process>

```

In order to import an entire Blue Prism process in its XML form, a few things need to be added besides the stages. Firstly, the root element “<process>” which contains the name of the process has to be defined. Whereas the name is always given the prefix “__selection__”. The second part is then the process name which can be set freely, in this case, it is “Login Process”. Within this root element, all stages are then listed together with attributes and elements as previously shown. However, all stages except for the End stage are given an additional element with the name “<onsuccess>”. This element in each stage is used to define the sequence of the individual stages and thus the process flow. How this works, is that the “onsuccess” element contains the stage ID of the following stage. Consequently, the structure and order of the individual stages in the Blue Prism process are clearly defined.

In addition, the values in the display element show how all stages are lined up in a line. Since the X-coordinate in the display element is equal to 15 for all stages, they must all be in a line from top to bottom. For the Y-coordinates, the elements are always 45 points apart from each other on

the y-axis. In summary, the two elements “display” and “onsuccess” can define the entire structure, flow, and visual representation of a process in Blue Prism.

In summary, this XML represents a simple login process in Blue Prism. Such an XML can be imported into Blue Prism in exactly this format. The import process is very simple: an XML file is copied and then pasted into the Blue Prism studio. From there, further adjustments can be made to the process as required in order to automate the process later on. But before such a process can be imported in this project, the ADOxx XML file needs to be transformed into a Blue Prism version of the XML file. To achieve this, understanding the structure of such an XML for Blue Prism is eminently important, as a process can only be imported by using a correct XML that can be interpreted by Blue Prism. The reason for this is, that a script or program which can convert an XML file from ADOxx into a correct XML file for Blue Prism, can only be developed if the XML format for Blue Prism is understood perfectly. Hence, the examinations in this chapter provide the necessary understanding of a Blue Prism XML, that such a program can be developed. Therefore, goal of the next chapter is to develop a program that transforms the ADOxx XML file into an XML file that can be imported into Blue Prism.

5.5.3 Script for Model Integration in Blue Prism

As both XML formats of ADOxx and Blue Prism have been examined, the following sections explain the main parts of the script that transform the exported XML of ADOxx into a usable XML for Blue Prism. The goal of the program is to efficiently and accurately convert a modeled process in ADOxx into a format that allows integration into Blue Prism. This means that every model in ADOxx can be exported as XML and then imported into Blue Prism without errors after the transformation using said script. To achieve this, the editor Visual Studio Code and the coding language Java have been defined as go-to tools. These are used in this chapter to complete the final piece of the prototype for Blue Prism. In the next sections the script and its main components are explained. The entire script can be accessed in Appendix B.

A UML activity diagram is used first to present the script clearly and comprehensibly. Figure 5.15 displays the rough flow and most important steps in the script. The script starts with the loading of the XML file of the ADOxx process. This XML file is then parsed so that the important information of each element of the RPA process is stored as an instance in an array. As soon as all elements are defined as instances in the arrays, the output XML file can be constructed using the information stored in the arrays. Lastly, the output XML file, which is Blue Prism compliant, is saved. This diagram gives an initial overview of the script which will be examined in more detail in the following sections.

Figure 5.15: UML Activity Diagram for the Script

In a first step of the script the created XML file from ADOxx is deconstructed and sorted in arrays. In total seven initial arrays are defined. One for each class of the modeling language: Read, Write, Navigate, Start, and End. Another array named “instances” is created to list all elements of the process model. Lastly, the array “arcs” is used to list all relations between the elements. These seven defined arrays are listed below.

```

1  static ArrayList<Instance> reads = new ArrayList();
2  static ArrayList<Instance> writes = new ArrayList();
3  static ArrayList<Instance> navigates = new ArrayList();
4  static ArrayList<Instance> start = new ArrayList();
5  static ArrayList<Instance> end = new ArrayList();
6  static ArrayList<Instance> instances = new ArrayList();
7  static ArrayList<Arc> arcs = new ArrayList();
  
```

Each of the arrays is then filled up using the “processElementsByClass” method. As input for this method the XML document, the name of the class as string, and the corresponding array for the class are used. In the first step of the method, all elements of the XML with the given input class name are filtered and collected in “nodeList” using XPath. This list is then iterated and all the important attributes of the element are extracted or generated. In “id” a random UUID is generated. As seen earlier each Blue Prism stage needs a unique identifier, in the form of a UUID and therefore it is necessary to generate such an identifier as part of the transformation. Next, the

attribute name, which contains the name of the class element is filtered and saved into “name”. If the element has an attribute with the name “Input” then this value is also be extracted and stored in “input”. Obviously, only elements of the class write have an input value. As a reminder, this is the value that is written by the robot in a write stage in Blue Prism. Finally, the Y-position of the element is extracted and saved into the “position” variable. The code of the discussed method is listed next.

```

1 private static void processElementsByClass(Document document, String
   className,ArrayList<Instance> instances) {
2     try {
3         String xpathExpression = "//*[ @class=' " + className + " ' ]";
4
5         javax.xml.xpath.XPath xPath =
           javax.xml.xpath.XPathFactory.newInstance().newXPath();
6         NodeList nodeList = (NodeList) xPath.evaluate(xpathExpression, document,
           javax.xml.xpath.XPathConstants.NODESET);
7
8         String name;
9         String id;
10        double position = -100000000;
11        String input = "";
12        Node node;
13        NodeList bambinos;
14
15        for (int i = 0; i < nodeList.getLength(); i++) {
16            node = nodeList.item(i);
17            if(node.getNodeName().equals("INSTANCE")) {
18                id = UUID.randomUUID().toString();
19                name = node.getAttributes().getNamedItem("name").getNodeValue();
20                bambinos = node.getChildNodes();
21                for(int j = 0; j<bambinos.getLength();j++){
22                    Node bambini = bambinos.item(j);
23                    if (bambini.getNodeName().equals("ATTRIBUTE")) {
24                        if (bambini.getAttributes().getNamedItem("name").
25                            getNodeValue().equals("Input")) {
26                            input = bambini.getTextContent();
27                        }
28
29                        if (bambini.getAttributes().getNamedItem("name").
30                            getNodeValue().equals("Position")) {
31                            String regex = "y:(\\d+) ";
32                            Pattern pattern = Pattern.compile(regex);
33                            Matcher matcher = pattern.matcher(bambini.getTextContent());
34
35                            if (matcher.find()) {
36                                String indexValue = matcher.group(1);
37                                position = Double.valueOf(indexValue);
38                            }
39                        }
40                    }
41                }
42                Instance instance = new Instance(name, id,input,position,className);
43                XMLator.instances.add(instance);
44                instances.add(instance);
45            }
46        }
47    }
48 }

```

```

44     }
45     } catch (Exception e) {
46         e.printStackTrace();
47     }
48 }

```

After processing an element, the collected values are stored in an instance object containing the name of the element, a UUID, the input if there is one, the Y-position of the element, and the name of the class. For a write element for example the content of an instance would look as follows:

```
"Write Username", "b1234567-89ab-cdef-1234-56789abcdef0", "USERNAME", 10.0, "writes"
```

This instance is then added to the “instances” array and to the “writes” array. After processing, the instances array contains all elements of the process listed with that information. Each class array contains only the elements of its class. For example, the reads array only contains all elements of the class read, and so on.

Next, the method “orig_y_to_position” method is called, which rearranges the “instances” array that contains all elements. As in ADOxx the process is modeled from top to bottom of the screen, and the Y-values go from small to large in the same direction, the lowest Y-value element is obviously the first one. Therefore, this method sorts the elements in the array from the lowest Y-value to the largest Y-value to arrange the instances in the list in the same order as they appear on the user interface in ADOxx. This reordering is accomplished with the code below.

```

1 public static void orig_y_to_position(ArrayList<Instance> instances) {
2     ArrayList<Instance> copy = new ArrayList<Instance>();
3     copy.addAll(instances);
4     double min;
5     int cur;
6     int count = 1;
7     double cur_y;
8     while(!copy.isEmpty()){
9         min = Double.MAX_VALUE;
10        cur = -1;
11        for(int j = 0; j<copy.size();j++){
12            cur_y = copy.get(j).orig_y;
13            if(cur_y<min){
14                min = cur_y;
15                cur = j;
16            }
17        }
18        copy.get(cur).position = count++;
19        copy.remove(cur);
20    }
21 }

```

After sorting the instance array, the method “processArcs” is executed. This method is pretty similar to the “processElementsByClass” method, except that in this case the relationships between the elements are listed in an array instead of the elements. Again, using XPath all elements in the XML with the class “Flow”, which is the relationship class in the modeling language, are extracted into a list. Each element is then iterated to extract the values of its attributes “FROM” and “TO”. Variables “start” and “end” are then used to store the values from which element the arc starts and to which element it points. The final output of the method is an array with all the relationships including its start and endpoint in the process model.

```

1 private static void processArcs(Document document) {
2     try {
3         String xpathExpression = "//*[@class='\" + \"Flow\" + '\"]";
4         javax.xml.xpath.XPath xPath =
5             javax.xml.xpath.XPathFactory.newInstance().newXPath();
6         NodeList nodeList = (NodeList) xPath.evaluate(xpathExpression, document,
7             javax.xml.xpath.XPathConstants.NODESET);
8
9         Node parent = null;
10        String start = "";
11        String end = "";
12        NodeList childNodes;
13
14        for (int i = 0; i < nodeList.getLength(); i++) {
15            parent = nodeList.item(i);
16            childNodes = parent.getChildNodes();
17            for (int j = 0; j < childNodes.getLength(); j++) {
18                Node child = childNodes.item(j);
19                if (child.getNodeType() == Node.ELEMENT_NODE &&
20                    "FROM".equals(child.getNodeName())) {
21                    start =
22                        child.getAttributes().getNamedItem("instance").getNodeValue();
23                    start = id_by_name(start);
24                }
25                if (child.getNodeType() == Node.ELEMENT_NODE &&
26                    "TO".equals(child.getNodeName())) {
27                    end =
28                        child.getAttributes().getNamedItem("instance").getNodeValue();
29                    end = id_by_name(end);
30                }
31            }
32            assert !start.equalsIgnoreCase("") && !end.equalsIgnoreCase("");
33            arcs.add(new Arc(start, end));
34        }
35    } catch (Exception e) {
36        e.printStackTrace();
37    }
38 }

```

Completion of this method marks the first step in the script, in which all the needed data is extracted from the ADOxx XML file and stored in a way that it can be further processed. Only the needed information, to create an XML file that can be used for Blue Prism is stored in the defined arrays. Exactly that is the goal for the further methods in the script, which is to construct an XML file that can be imported into Blue Prism.

In order to create the output xml the “create_blue_prism_xml” method is called. First, a document object is created with the document builder. After that, the root element “process” and its attributes are added to the document. As examined in earlier chapters the root element is always the same for a Blue Prism XML, therefore it can be used for every generated XML. The root element is generated with the following code.

```
1 private static void create_blue_prism_xml() {
2     try{
3         DocumentBuilderFactory factory = DocumentBuilderFactory.newInstance();
4         DocumentBuilder builder = factory.newDocumentBuilder();
5         Document document = builder.newDocument();
6         Element processElement = document.createElement("process");
7         processElement.setAttribute("name", "__selection__Utility - Calculations");
8         processElement.setAttribute("type", "object");
9         processElement.setAttribute("runmode", "Exclusive");
10        document.appendChild(processElement);
11        append_stages(processElement, document);
12    }
13    catch (Exception e){
14        e.printStackTrace();
15    }
16 }
```

Now that the base of the XML output file is set, the Blue Prism stages can be added to it using the “append_stages” method. For this, the five lists for each class, namely Start, End, Navigates, Reads and Writes are iterated. Each instance in these lists is called in the method named “process”. In this method, which is displayed below, the instance gets the correct XML format and is then appended to the document as a child node.

In the “process” method the first three lines of code define the “stage” element. In this, both attributes, name, and id, are set. Both these values were saved in the instance earlier, one is the name of the action, and the other is the UUID. As a second step the child element “display” is generated containing the X and Y values which define the location of the stage in Blue Prism. Next, it is checked whether the stage has a relationship, if so then the child element “onsuccess” is added to the stage element. The value of this element is then the UUID of the following stage. If there is no following stage, then the “onsuccess” element is left out.

Finally, the type of the current stage is elaborated, and the attribute “type” is set accordingly. If the type of the current stage is “Write”, then an additional child is added to the stage element.

This child element named “step” contains the input value of the Write stage which is set in the “expr” attribute within the “step” element.

After iterating over all instances of all arrays, the XML document is complete and contains all the stages and attributes needed to represent a Blue Prism process. Therefore, the last method in the script “saveDocumentToFile” is called, in which the document is simply exported and saved as an XML file with the name “out.xml”. From there the content of this XML file can be imported into the Blue Prism modeling interface. To do this, the entire content must be copied and then pasted into Blue Prism. By doing this the complete model from ADOxx can be placed in the Blue Prism modeling toolkit. From there further adjustments can be made to the process model, such as spying out each single element, in order to later execute the process.

```
1 public Node process(String subsheet_id, Document doc, ArrayList<Arc> arcs) {
2     Node n = doc.createElement("stage");
3     ((Element) n).setAttribute("name", name);
4     ((Element) n).setAttribute("stageid", id);
5     Node disp = doc.createElement("display");
6     n.appendChild(disp);
7     ((Element) disp).setAttribute("x", Integer.valueOf(DEFAULT_X).toString());
8     ((Element)
9         disp).setAttribute("y", Integer.valueOf(DEFAULT_Y+position*Y_STEP).toString());
10    int idx = Arc.is_start(arcs, id);
11    if(idx!=-1){
12        Node suc = doc.createElement("onsuccess");
13        n.appendChild(suc);
14        ((Element) suc).setTextContent(arcs.get(idx).end_id);
15    }
16    if(type==Type.START){
17        ((Element) n).setAttribute("type", "Start");
18    }
19    if(type==Type.END){
20        ((Element) n).setAttribute("type", "End");
21    }
22    if(type==Type.WRITE){
23        ((Element) n).setAttribute("type", "Write");
24        Node step = doc.createElement("step");
25        n.appendChild(step);
26        if(input != null && !input.equals(""))
27            ((Element) step).setAttribute("expr", input);
28    }
29    if(type==Type.READ){
30        ((Element) n).setAttribute("type", "Read");
31        Node step = doc.createElement("step");
32        n.appendChild(step);
33        if(input != null && !input.equals(""))
34            ((Element) step).setAttribute("expr", input);
35    }
36    if(type==Type.NAVIGATE){
37        ((Element) n).setAttribute("type", "Navigate");
38    }
39    return n;
40 }
```

To give a better overview of the entire script, the used classes, methods, and attributes are displayed in a UML class diagram. The UML class diagram shown in Figure 5.16 illustrates the structure and relationships of the classes implemented in the script. The aim of the diagram is to clearly visualize the technical architecture of the script and to illustrate the logical connections between the individual components. Overall, it can be seen that the main class XMLator acts as the central control unit that coordinates the various steps of the transformation process. It works closely with the Instance and Arc classes, which also contribute to the entire transformation process.

Figure 5.16: UML Class Diagram for the Blue Prism Script

In conclusion, the script shows that it is possible to transform an exported model from ADOxx into an XML format that can be integrated into the Blue Prism software. This chapter has demonstrated how such a transformation can be done, with the help of a script. Said script lays the foundations for the successful integration of a platform-independent RPA modeling language into one RPA software provider. However, the aim of the thesis is to develop a platform-independent modeling language that can be integrated into multiple RPA solutions. This means that the script must be extended to support at least one other RPA software. It should make it possible to upload the exported XML from ADOxx not only to Blue Prism but also to a second RPA software, UiPath. To achieve this, UiPath is analyzed in the next chapter, similar to the approach with Blue Prism. After understanding how UiPath works, the goal is to create another script that allows a process to be uploaded to UiPath just as efficiently as to Blue Prism.

5.5.4 UiPath: Analysis of the XAML Structure

After successfully developing a solution to import a process into Blue Prism, the goal of this chapter is to analyze UiPath and find a similar solution that allows the import of a process that is modeled and exported out of ADOxx. Again, the first step is to look into how UiPath works and how processes are represented.

UiPath uses a similar drag-and-drop approach, just like Blue Prism, in order to model an RPA process. Whereas, each step of the process is represented by a building block, or also called activity in UiPath. These activities can be placed via drag and drop on the user interface of the modeling tool in order to create the desired process. In contrast to Blue Prism, however, UiPath does not use XML, but rather XAML to define individual blocks or entire processes.

XAML (Extensible Application Markup Language) is a declarative XML-based language that was originally developed by Microsoft. It is often used to define user interfaces and workflows in applications. In UiPath, XAML is used as a format for defining and storing processes. An XAML document describes the hierarchy, configuration, and properties of the various activities used in a workflow. Therefore, the way of defining single activities or an entire process is pretty similar to Blue Prism. But to fully understand it a close look has to be made at each activity that has to be imported and how it is defined in the XAML format. How such definitions in XAML look in UiPath is now explained using an example. This allows the individual elements and notations to be described and illustrated.

The content of the document always begins with the XML declaration and the namespace declarations. XML namespaces are required to give individual elements a unique name. They are necessary to interpret the structure and elements of the XAML document. Following is a list of the various XML namespaces used in UiPath to represent the UiPath elements.

```
1 xmlns="http://schemas.microsoft.com/netfx/2009/xaml/activities/presentation"
2 xmlns:sap2010="http://schemas.microsoft.com/netfx/2010/xaml/activities/
  presentation"
3 xmlns:scg="clr-namespace:System.Collections.Generic;assembly=System.Private.
  CoreLib"
4 xmlns:uix="http://schemas.uipath.com/workflow/activities/uix"
5 xmlns:x="http://schemas.microsoft.com/winfx/2006/xaml">
```

The exact functionality of XML and namespaces is not explicitly discussed here, but simply put, the first, second, and last namespaces are standard namespaces that are commonly used to interpret and name various elements and attributes. These are sort of standard namespaces to use in XAML. Then there is the “clr-namespace.” This is mainly used to create lists or collections within the XAML. In the case of UiPath, for example, this could be a list of activities in a modeled process. Finally, there is the “uix-xmlns”, which is a specific namespace for UiPath. All the activities in a UiPath process are defined using this namespace. This includes individual actions

such as Click, Get Text, or Type Into. The following XAML lines display a Click element in UiPath:

```
1 <uix:NClick x:Name="__ReferenceID0" ActivateBefore="True" ClickType="Single"
   DisplayName="Click" VirtualizedContainerService.HintSize="334,155"
   KeyModifiers="None" MouseButton="Left" Version="V3" />
```

The “NClick” XAML element defines a click activity in a UiPath workflow. This element belongs to the specific UiPath namespace (uix) and is used to execute a click on a UI element. Multiple attributes are defined within a “uix:NClick” element. Firstly the attribute `x:Name="__ReferenceID0"` assigns the element a unique reference ID within the XAML document, making it identifiable and linkable. The second attribute `ActivateBefore="True"` ensures that the target element is activated before the click to ensure that the click is registered correctly. Next, `ClickType="Single"` specifies that it is a single click and `MouseButton="Left"` indicates which mouse button is clicked. `KeyModifiers="None"` means that no modifier keys such as Ctrl, Alt, or Shift are used while the mouse Button is clicked. To give each activity a name `DisplayName="Click"` is used to define the name that is displayed in the UiPath Studio for this action, “Click Button” for example. `VirtualizedContainerService.HintSize="334,155"` defines the size of the virtual container for displaying the activity in the UiPath Designer, with a width of 334 pixels and a height of 155 pixels. Finally, the `Version="V3"` attribute specifies the version number of the click activity.

However, not all attributes are necessary. Some of these attributes, if omitted, simply assume a default value. This means that a click activity can also be defined in a simplified way, for example, as follows:

```
1 <uix:NClick x:Name="__ReferenceID0" DisplayName="Click" />
```

In this case, the remaining attributes that were not explicitly defined in this element, such as `ClickType`, `MouseButton`, and others, are automatically set to their default values. These default values correspond to those explicitly specified in the example above. Therefore, this definition is essentially the same as the more detailed version above. This is important because it simplifies the transformation of an XML from ADOxx to an XAML for UiPath if certain attributes can be omitted.

The “NGetText” XAML element represents a Get Text activity in a UiPath workflow. In this XAML element again most of the same attributes are used as in the click element. Such as the reference ID, display name, the size properties on the interface, or the version. Obviously, the attributes used for defining the click button and key modifiers do not exist.

```
1 <uix:NGetText x:Name="__ReferenceID1" DisplayName="Get Text"
   VirtualizedContainerService.HintSize="334,155" Version="V3" />
```

Again, for this element, multiple attributes can be left out, as they are set to default values anyways. In this case, the only two attributes needed are the reference ID and the display name. In this example the ID would be 1 and the display name is “Get Text”:

```
1 <uix:NGetText x:Name="__ReferenceID1" DisplayName="Get Text" />
```

For the last element “NTypeInto” which represents the Type Into activity in UiPath a few new attributes are used. First “ClickBeforeMode” is set to “Single”. This indicates that before any content is written into a text field, it is made sure that the field is selected, by clicking into the text box first. This value could be set to “none” if no click is required before typing or to “double” if a double click would be necessary before typing. Next, “EmptyFieldMode” is another new attribute, which is used to define if the text field should be cleared before anything is written into it. Again this value can be set to “none” if the text field should not be cleared. Setting it to “Single” deletes the entire line of text, if there is any in the field, before typing into it. Lastly, the most important attribute for this element is “Text”, which defines the input value that should be written into the text field. These new attributes together with other, already discussed attributes create the XAML element for a Type Into activity. The Type Into XAML element looks as following:

```
1 <uix:NTypeInto x:Name="__ReferenceID2" ActivateBefore="True" ClickBeforeMode="
  Single" DisplayName="Type Into" EmptyFieldMode="SingleLine"
  VirtualizedContainerService.HintSize="334,216" Text="Text" Version="V3" />
```

Once more, a few of the attributes can be omitted since they are set to default values if done so. This means that only the reference ID, ClickBeforeMode, DisplayName, EmptyFieldMode, and the Text as input are left as attributes for the XAML element “NTypeInto”. After simplifying, the Type Into element is shaped as follows:

```
1 <uix:NTypeInto x:Name="__ReferenceID2" ClickBeforeMode="Single" DisplayName="Type
  Into " EmptyFieldMode="SingleLine" Text="Input" />
```

Now that the three individual activities and their structure have been explained in XAML form, the next step is to examine how these activities are represented in an entire process and what the notation in the XAML file looks like when several elements follow one after the other. For this again the short example of a login process is used. As a reminder, the login process consists of the following actions: typing the username followed by typing the password and lastly clicking the login button.

To display multiple activities in UiPath, the clr-namespace is used to create a list of all the elements. As a result, all activities contained in the process model are listed in a list. For the login process example, this looks as follows:

```
1 <scg:List x:TypeArguments="x:Object" Capacity="3">
2   <uix:NTypeInto x:Name="__ReferenceID0" ClickBeforeMode="Single" DisplayName="
   Write Username" EmptyFieldMode="SingleLine" Text="USERNAME" />
3   <uix:NTypeInto x:Name="__ReferenceID1" ClickBeforeMode="Single" DisplayName="
   Write Password" EmptyFieldMode="SingleLine" Text="PASSWORD" />
4   <uix:NClick x:Name="__ReferenceID2" DisplayName="Click Login Button" />
5 </scg:List>
```

The list contains three elements and therefore the capacity of the list is set to 3. In the list then are the three defined elements which are two Type Into and one Click activities. Display names are set accordingly to their function: “Write Username”, “Write Password” and “Click Login Button”. For the text input the placeholder “USERNAME” and “PASSWORD” are set. In this list, all activities are now listed in the correct order. However, another list is required with the information in which order the activities should appear in the process flow:

```
1 <scg:List x:TypeArguments="x:Object" Capacity="3">
2   <x:Reference>__ReferenceID0</x:Reference>
3   <x:Reference>__ReferenceID1</x:Reference>
4   <x:Reference>__ReferenceID2</x:Reference>
5 </scg:List>
```

In this case, the “Write Username” element is the first activity in the process, as its reference ID is listed first and the “Click Login Button” is last, as its reference ID is listed at the end. If, in this example “ReferenceID0” and “ReferenceID2” would be swapped, then the Click activity would be the first element in the process and the Write Username the last one. Therefore, this list ensures that the sequence of activities is clear by defining the exact sequence of execution in the process model.

If all these parts, the namespace definition, the list of activities, and the metadata for the order of the process are now combined, a complete XAML file can be created for a login process in UiPath. However, in order to import this process into UiPath, it is necessary to add “ClipboardData” elements. These are used so that the entire XAML can be imported into UiPath. The “ClipboardData” containers complete the XAML and make it possible to manage and transfer these activities efficiently. One container encloses the whole package, another contains the list with all the activities and finally one includes the list with the metadata, in this case, the structure and order of activities. The end result of the XML for the login process is displayed below.

```

1 <ClipboardData
2   xmlns="http://schemas.microsoft.com/netfx/2009/xaml/activities/presentation"
3   xmlns:sap2010="http://schemas.microsoft.com/netfx/2010/xaml/activities/
4     presentation"
5   xmlns:scg="clr-namespace:System.Collections.Generic;assembly=System.Private.
6     CoreLib"
7   xmlns:uix="http://schemas.uipath.com/workflow/activities/uix"
8   xmlns:x="http://schemas.microsoft.com/winfx/2006/xaml">
9   <ClipboardData.Data>
10    <scg:List x:TypeArguments="x:Object" Capacity="3">
11      <uix:NTypeInto x:Name="__ReferenceID0" ClickBeforeMode="Single"
12        DisplayName="Write Username" EmptyFieldMode="SingleLine" Text="
13        USERNAME" />
14      <uix:NTypeInto x:Name="__ReferenceID1" ClickBeforeMode="Single"
15        DisplayName="Write Password" EmptyFieldMode="SingleLine" Text="
16        PASSWORD" />
17      <uix:NClick x:Name="__ReferenceID2" DisplayName="Click Login Button" />
18    </scg:List>
19  </ClipboardData.Data>
20  <ClipboardData.Metadata>
21    <scg:List x:TypeArguments="x:Object" Capacity="3">
22      <x:Reference>__ReferenceID0</x:Reference>
23      <x:Reference>__ReferenceID1</x:Reference>
24      <x:Reference>__ReferenceID2</x:Reference>
25    </scg:List>
26  </ClipboardData.Metadata>
27 </ClipboardData>

```

To summarize, UiPath uses an XAML notation in order to represent its processes. Such a XAML document can be separated into three basic blocks. Firstly, the namespaces ensure that the various elements and attributes are interpreted correctly within the XAML. Namespaces ensure that the activities used in UiPath, and their properties are correctly interpreted. The second block consists of a list with elements containing all activities that occur in the process. Whereas each activity, such as Type Into, Click, and Get Text, is described with its own specific attributes. In the third and last block, the metadata is assigned to the activities. This metadata is used to define the order of all activities in the process. As seen in the example, these three blocks from the entire XAML document can describe the login process in UiPath. This means that if this simple example process is to be implemented into the UiPath studio, then this exact XAML format has to be created. After that, all that needs to be done is to copy this entire code and paste it into a UiPath project. From there on the process can be developed further and then executed.

As the XAML format in UiPath is now understood, the next step is to create a script, with which such a file can be generated out of an ADOxx XML file. The approach is the exact same as done with Blue Prism previously, except that the output file has to be UiPath conform. Therefore, in the next chapter, this script is developed and described.

5.5.5 Script for Model Integration in UiPath

After the first script for Blue Prism, the creation of a second script adapted for UiPath is the goal of this chapter. As the notation and format of the file are different from Blue Prism, a new script has to be developed. However, some parts can be recycled and reused for the new script. For example, the code that deconstructs the ADOxx XML file and extracts the data into lists can be used again. Since most of the information stored in the instances in these lists are also needed to construct the XAML file for UiPath. These are for example the activity name, the input if there is one, or the type of activity. This means that the entire first part of the code that was explained in the Blue Prism script is reused. Including the creation of the arrays for each class followed by the method “processElementsByClass” which fills up these arrays with instances. As these parts of the code are exactly the same as in the Blue Prism script, they are not explained again. Furthermore, the structure of this script is the same as shown in the UML activity diagram in Figure 5.15 and discussed in Chapter 5.5.3. Only the major differences and new important parts of the code are discussed in this chapter. This mainly includes the construction of the output XAML file for UiPath. The entire script can be accessed in Appendix B.

In order to build the final file for a UiPath process, the method “create_uipath_xml” is called. Just like in Blue Prism first, a document object is created with the document builder. In a second step again the root element is defined. As examined in earlier chapters the root element “ClipboardData” contains all the namespaces for a UiPath XAML file. The code for the creation of this root element consists of the following six lines.

```
1 Element rootElement = doc.createElement("ClipboardData");
2 rootElement.setAttribute("xmlns", "http://schemas.microsoft.com/netfx/2009/
   xaml/activities/presentation");
3 rootElement.setAttribute("xmlns:sap2010",
   "http://schemas.microsoft.com/netfx/2010/xaml/activities/presentation");
4 rootElement.setAttribute("xmlns:scg",
   "clr-namespace:System.Collections.Generic;assembly=System.Private.CoreLib");
5 rootElement.setAttribute("xmlns:uix",
   "http://schemas.uipath.com/workflow/activities/uix");
6 rootElement.setAttribute("xmlns:x",
   "http://schemas.microsoft.com/winfx/2006/xaml");
```

As this root element and the namespaces are the same for each process in UiPath, this code remains the same for each execution of the script. Next, the “ClipboardData.data” element and its child element “scg:List” and its attributes are generated. Whereas the attribute “capacity” contains the number of activities in the process. As seen, there are no Start and End activities in UiPath, only the Read, Write, and Navigate activities are counted. This means that the login process for example would only contain three activities, instead of five when including Start and End. Finally, all these elements are appended to the document in its corresponding order.

```

1 Element dataElement = doc.createElement("ClipboardData.Data");
2 Element listElement = doc.createElement("scg:List");
3 listElement.setAttribute("x:TypeArguments", "x:Object");
4 int count = reads.size()+writes.size()+navigates.size();
5 listElement.setAttribute("Capacity", Integer.toString(count));
6 dataElement.appendChild(listElement);
7 rootElement.appendChild(dataElement);
8 doc.appendChild(rootElement);

```

In a next step, all the instances of the activities used in the UiPath process are looped and processed using the “process_uipath” method shown below. For each activity, an element is generated according to its type. All the elements get the attributes for the name that is displayed in UiPath. Also, each element gets the attribute containing its ID. The ID itself is generated out of a sorted list of all instances. Whereas the first activity of the process gets the lowest ID number starting at zero and in order of process the activities get each its ID, always growing by one. All Write activities get additional attributes, which are needed to define the input. After each iteration, the generated element is appended to the “scg:List” element which was generated in the code part above. Finally, after iterating over all instances this element contains all the activities in the process.

```

1 public Node process_uipath(Document doc,int count){
2     Element n = null;
3     if(type==Type.WRITE){
4         n = doc.createElement("uix:NTypeInto");
5         n.setAttribute("x:Name", "__ReferenceID"+count);
6         n.setAttribute("DisplayName", name);
7         n.setAttribute("ClickBeforeMode", "Single");
8         n.setAttribute("EmptyFieldMode", "SingleLine");
9         n.setAttribute("Text", input);
10    }
11    if(type==Type.READ){
12        n = doc.createElement("uix:NGetText");
13        n.setAttribute("x:Name", "__ReferenceID"+count);
14        n.setAttribute("DisplayName", name);
15    }
16    }
17    if(type==Type.NAVIGATE){
18        n = doc.createElement("uix:NClick");
19        n.setAttribute("x:Name", "__ReferenceID"+count);
20        n.setAttribute("DisplayName", name);
21    }
22    return n;
23 }

```

As the last part of the UiPath script, which is listed below, the “ClipboardData.Metadata” element and its child “scg:List”, containing the order of all activities is generated. For each instance of the sorted array holding all activities, one “x:Reference” element containing the corresponding ID is generated and appended to the “scg:List” element.

```

1 Element meta_data = doc.createElement("ClipboardData.Metadata");
2 rootElement.appendChild(meta_data);
3 Element meta_list = doc.createElement("scg:List");
4 meta_list.setAttribute("x:TypeArguments", "x:Object");
5 meta_list.setAttribute("Capacity", Integer.toString(count));
6 meta_data.appendChild(meta_list);
7 Element cur;
8 for(int i = 0; i<sort_instances.size();i++){
9     cur = doc.createElement("x:Reference");
10    cur.setTextContent("__ReferenceID"+i);
11    meta_list.appendChild(cur);
12 }

```

After iterating over all instances, the document is complete and should contain all information about the UiPath process. Including all information about the Activities and their order in the process. Therefore, just like in the Blue Prism script, the method “saveDocumentToFile” is called, in which the document is exported and saved as “out.xml”. The content of this file can then be copy-pasted into the UiPath software in order to import the process. From there on further modeling can be done such that the process can be completed and executed in UiPath.

Again To give a better overview of the entire script, the used classes, methods, and attributes are displayed in a UML class diagram. Figure 5.17 illustrates the structure and relationships of the classes implemented in the script for UiPath. The UML class diagram for the UiPath script is very similar in structure to that of the Blue Prism script, as the basic processes and data structures are almost identical. Only minimal adjustments were made to meet the specific requirements and formats of UiPath, such as the processing of XAML files instead of XML.

Figure 5.17: UML Class Diagram for the UiPath Script

With this second working script, it is now possible to transform the ADOxx XML file into two different RPA software. This means that when combining those two scripts with the modeling language in ADOxx makes it possible to model RPA processes platform independently and then using them in at least two different RPA software. However, at this point these two scripts are separate and not really user friendly. Therefore, the last missing piece is a easy to use application that allows a user to transform an ADOxx XML file into either Blue Prism or UiPath. To achieve this a simple desktop application, that combines both scripts and enables easy use, is developed and explained in the next chapter.

5.5.6 Desktop Application

In this chapter, the aim is to develop a user-friendly desktop application that combines both developed scripts. As for now, it is required to call each script individually and execute it in the terminal, which is impractical and time-consuming for the end user. Therefore, a simple application in which the user can transform a process with only a few clicks would make these scripts much more practical. The goal is that the desktop application merges these two scripts into a single, intuitive user interface. Users should be able to select an input file and then decide whether the transformation should be made for a UiPath or a Blue Prism process. After the selection, the transformed file is returned so that the user can import it directly into the corresponding software. This application is named “RPA Converter” and is developed in Java.

The user interface of the RPA converter is displayed in Figure 5.18. The application has three buttons: “Browse”, “Convert to Blue Prism” and “Convert to UiPath”. When clicking “Browse” a file explorer is opened, and the user can choose an XML file of a process that was developed and exported from ADOxx using the RPA modeling language. It is also possible to just paste the file path into the text box itself, instead of searching the file using the explorer.

Figure 5.18: Desktop Application

After selecting the file, the user has the option of selecting either “Convert to Blue Prism” or “Convert to UiPath”. If “Convert to Blue Prism” is selected, the corresponding script is executed and an “Out.xml” file is generated. In addition, the entire output of the transformed XML file is copied to the clipboard. This means that the user can then simply open Blue Prism and import the process into Blue Prism by pressing “CTRL-V” or by selecting the “Paste” option. If the process is to be imported into UiPath then obviously the button “Convert to UiPath” has to be clicked. In no time, the transformed process is saved to the clipboard and can be imported into the desired software, be it UiPath or Blue Prism.

If the user wants to save the output file, this must be done manually. For this, the “Out.xml” file can simply be renamed and moved to the desired folder. The automatic naming of a file and saving it in a desired folder could be implemented in further development and refinement of the prototype. But for now, this feature is not important and therefore also not implemented. Overall, this application considerably simplifies the entire transformation and import process. The user can transform an XML file and import it directly into the desired software without any great effort or technical knowledge. This not only significantly increases efficiency, but also user-friendliness.

With this application the whole process of using the modeling language would look like this: First, a process is modeled in ADOxx, using the RPA modeling language. In a second step, this model is exported as an XML file. Next, the RPA converter is launched, and the exported file is chosen using the “Browse” button in the application. At this point, either a conversion into UiPath or into Blue Prism is chosen by clicking the corresponding button. Lastly, the output that is saved in the clipboard can be pasted either into Blue Prism or UiPath. Additionally, if needed the “Out.xml” file can be renamed and saved anywhere manually.

Finally, this small desktop application concludes the practical development of the entire project, since it is now possible to model an RPA process platform independently and then import and use it in one of two RPA software providers. Hence, in a next chapter the goal is to evaluate the results and the entire prototype in general.

5.6 Results and Review of the Prototype

In Appendix B, the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and URL provide access to all developed code and the ADOxx modeling language, ensuring transparency and reproducibility of the work. Following this, the chapter shifts focus to an examination and evaluation of the developed prototype, aiming to critically assess the results achieved.

Before diving into the results of the developed prototype in detail, two example processes can be found in Appendix A. These examples demonstrate the entire modeling and transformation process with the created prototype. The process shown in example 1 of the appendix is used

to demonstrate everything including the process models and the corresponding XML code. For this, the simple process of creating a new user account was chosen. In this case for each step, a screenshot and the corresponding XML file are shown. First, the initial model in ADOxx and the corresponding XML structure are shown. Then this XML file is transformed to Blue Prism and UiPath using the developed desktop application. The resulting XML files and a screenshot of the imported process model in both RPA software are also displayed. These examples provide visual support and illustrate what each step of the prototype looks like. With this constellation, it is possible to get a better understanding of each XML structure behind the model itself and therefore get a glimpse of what the developed script produces.

The second example in the appendix is about a more complex process. This is to show the possibilities and also the potential of this modeling language. A common process in companies where RPA can be used is the processing of incoming forms, for example in connection with payments. In this example, forms are submitted by customers who are to receive a payment, for example for a refund. The process looks as follows: the robot opens the company's software that is intended for processing these payments. Then the first form is opened and the robot reads out the relevant data, such as the customer number and payment details. This data is then inserted into the corresponding fields in the business software. Once all the data has been transferred correctly, the robot saves the entries and sends the information for further processing. Finally, the form is closed and the robot opens the next form to go through the same process again. Although the modeling language does not currently support loops, the process can be represented by executing the steps sequentially. This means the robot would start over again at the second navigate element and open the next form. However, as this is not yet possible with this modeling language, the last navigate stage in the process is used as some sort of placeholder. To add a loop to this process, the user can simply add a loop element after importing the process into Blue Prism or UiPath. This is also shown in this example in the appendix. For UiPath, for example, a loop can be built in with which it is possible to loop through a list of files.

The current modeling language can therefore be used to reliably represent basic processes such as form processing. However, this also reveals limitations of this basic RPA modeling language. The inability to represent loops and decision structures makes the modeling of such processes more difficult, especially when a large number of forms need to be processed. With additional features such as the integration of loops, the entire process could be modeled more efficiently and realistically. Loops would make it possible to model the repetition of steps only once and represent the process more dynamically and compactly. Despite these limitations, this example illustrates how a more complex process can be modeled even with the basic actions. It also lays the foundation for possible extensions to the modeling language in order to be able to model complex processes even more precisely in the future. These conclusions provides the transition to the consideration of the entire chapter and the practical part.

Overall, this practical chapter included the entire development process of a platform-independent RPA modeling language. First, two low-fidelity prototypes were made in order to have a clear goal of how the final prototype should work and look like. Then the first research question (RQ 1) was addressed. For this, the core elements and building blocks needed in an RPA modeling language were examined by analyzing Blue Prism and UiPath. Based on these findings, a basic RPA modeling language was then developed in ADOxx, in order to tackle the second research question (RQ 2). This achievement at the same time means that requirements one and three, which were set up in Chapter 4.2, have been met. Since a modeling language was created in a modeling tool (Requirement 3). The modeling language can represent an RPA process (Requirement 1). However, these are simple and basic RPA processes that can be represented with the basic actions of the developed modeling language. Requirement 5 was also achieved, as modeling a process was designed to be simple and intuitive. Overall, the design of the modeling language is simple but efficient and should therefore keep modeling simple.

In the next sections, where the third research question (RQ 3) was addressed, a solution to transfer the created models in ADOxx to Blue Prism and UiPath was found. For this, an exported XML file of the developed process in ADOxx had to be transformed in such a way, that it could be imported in either Blue Prism or UiPath. For each of the RPA software providers, a script was developed. These scripts allow the transformation of the ADOxx XML file to either RPA software. With this successful solution, requirement 4 has also been fulfilled, as it requires a script that allows an efficient transfer of a model into RPA software. Requirement number 2 was also met, as the two scripts allowed the transfer to multiple RPA software platforms. Hence, this key requirement that was necessary to reach platform independence was also fulfilled.

Overall, all five defined requirements have been reached. However, when looking at the functionality of this prototype there is one missing element. The spying of elements that are necessary to execute an RPA process could not be implemented. As described, the implementation of such a platform-independent spying would be highly complex. Additionally, RPA providers like UiPath use methods that are a company secret and therefore not replicable. Hence, only the process model can be implemented platform-independent and the spying itself must be done after the import into the RPA software. Nevertheless, the prototype provides a concept that demonstrates how RPA processes can be modeled independently from any RPA platform. To conclude, the entirety of the project is summarized and evaluated in the next and final chapter.

Chapter 6

Discussion and Outlook

Chapter 6 discusses the main results of the prototype, the associated challenges for this project, and lastly recommendations for future work. The aim of this chapter is to critically evaluate the results achieved and provide an outlook for potential further developments. Chapter 6.1 begins with a summary of the key results and an evaluation of the prototype based on the defined research questions. After this, Chapter 6.2 discusses the limitations and challenges during the development phase of the project. Finally, section 6.3 offers recommendations for future work in order to lay the foundation for further optimization and expansion of the RPA modeling language.

6.1 Main Results and Evaluation

The main results of this thesis include the initial investigation in Chapter 3. This included an analysis of current approaches for platform-independent RPA modeling languages. This resulted in the conclusion that there is currently no completely platform-independent modeling language on the market that is directly applicable to various RPA solutions. Although some existing approaches show promising characteristics and in some cases achieve a certain degree of platform independence, no complete solution could be identified. Hence, in Chapter 4 a prototype for a platform-independent RPA modeling language was planned and specified. In Chapter 5 said prototype was then implemented and developed.

The analysis of Blue Prism and UiPath provided a solid basis for the selection and definition of the key concepts and core elements of an RPA process. As part of this development, the first research question was also addressed: “What key elements and concepts are necessary to represent RPA processes in a modeling language?”. The central elements of both leading RPA platforms, Blue Prism and UiPath, were analyzed in order to work out the basic building blocks of an RPA modeling language. By focusing on the fundamental and indispensable elements, a simple but functionally sufficient basis was created that enables a cross-platform representation of RPA processes. Hence, research question number one was answered with these examinations and findings.

As part of the second research question, “How can a modeling language that represents RPA processes be technically implemented?” the central RPA process components of UiPath and Blue Prism were brought together. Based on the core elements identified in the analysis, an RPA modeling language was designed. For this, the ADOxx metamodeling software was used for the implementation, which provided a flexible platform for developing the modeling language. The RPA modeling language was implemented in such a way that the modeling of RPA processes can be carried out independently of RPA providers such as UiPath or Blue Prism. This resulted in a platform-independent modeling language with which RPA processes can be modeled neutrally and independently.

In order to address the third and last research question: “To what extent is the developed modeling language platform-independent, and how efficiently can it be applied to different RPA platforms?” it was necessary to develop a solution for at least two different RPA providers. With the development of two different scripts, it was made possible to transfer a process model from ADOxx to either UiPath or Blue Prism. Both these scripts were then combined in a desktop application to enable simple usage. The scripts and application provide a solid solution of how the platform-independent RPA modeling language can be applied to multiple RPA platforms. However, the spying part of an RPA process still needs to be done in the RPA software itself as it could not be implemented in the developed modeling language.

All in all, the research questions were answered and the goal of creating a platform-independent RPA modeling language has been achieved. An approach and method were presented with which RPA processes can be modeled independently of the platform. The solution allows a user to model a simple RPA process followed by the possibility to import the RPA process into two different RPA providers. However, the prototype encountered certain challenges and hurdles, some of which were not overcome. These are explained and discussed in the next chapter.

6.2 Limitations and Challenges

Despite the successful development of a platform-independent RPA modeling language, several limitations and challenges came up during the project. These relate to technical aspects and the time intensity of the practical realization of a platform-independent modeling language. The most important limitations and the related challenges are discussed in detail below. This discussion provides a comprehensive picture of the results achieved and the discovered limits in regard to the project. Additionally, certain aspects with potential for optimization are highlighted.

One main limitation of this project was the spying of the elements. An optimal platform-independent RPA modeling language would have included spying on the user interface element. However, the many different approaches taken by the different RPA providers in regard to spying proposed a big challenge that could not be solved. The sheer complexity and variety of the used

solutions do not allow the creation of a platform-independent spying method. This, plus the fact that a competitive company like UiPath tries to keep its methods secret, makes it impossible to imitate certain spy methods. Hence, the prototype only allows modeling and import of the process model. The spying still has to be done manually in the RPA software after importing a model.

A major challenge of the project was to create an RPA modeling language that could be applied to multiple RPA providers. For this, it was key to find the common actions and elements of each RPA software. This was achieved successfully but the created modeling language was kept really simple and only included the main actions in RPA processes. Therefore, the modeling of a complex RPA process with decision points, loops, or other complex elements would be very limited. There are various reasons for why the modeling language was kept simple. On the one hand, the aim was to demonstrate the concept of a platform-independent modeling language. For this, the basic elements are sufficient, as more elements would not change the concept itself. Instead, the overall time investment would be increased, since all the additional elements would have to be developed and implemented. This means a more complex and broader RPA modeling language would have required a massive amount of time that was not available. However, this also means that with more time or another project, it would certainly be possible to expand this modeling language in such a way that it can represent complex RPA processes.

Another challenge was, that each RPA software has a different way of how their processes are displayed. This meant that for each RPA provider, another solution had to be developed. In this case two pretty similar scripts, but still different in many ways were developed. This also means that for every new RPA software, a new solution has to be found and implemented. In other words, the developed modeling language is always limited to the RPA providers for which a solution was implemented. In this case, that would be Blue Prism and UiPath. If a different RPA provider is to be used, a new solution must be found and implemented. For this project, two providers were enough to demonstrate platform independence. However, the prototype can certainly be extended to other RPA software providers in future work.

Overall, the limitations and challenges listed show that the development process of a platform-independent RPA prototype is a complex task. Especially since the various RPA providers are in great competition and therefore have no interest or advantages in a platform-independent RPA solution. It has also shown that not every challenge can be solved, such as the spying for example. Other challenges could be solved but some would still need more time to develop in order to reach the state where complex RPA processes can be developed. However, overall, it has been shown that it is possible to model RPA processes platform-independently, as long as the spying is still done in the RPA software itself. Therefore, these insights offer valuable approaches for future projects and developments in this area.

6.3 Recommendations for Future Work

Based on the learnings from this work, there are several possibilities for future work and therefore further development of the prototype. Even if platform independence has been reached, there is still a lot for improvement in regard to functionality, usability, and applicability that can be made. Hence, the following recommendations are intended to address new opportunities for research and development of the platform-independent RPA modeling language.

The first starting point is the extension of the modeling language itself. The current prototype only includes basic actions that can be used to model simple RPA processes. Future work could aim to integrate additional actions and elements into the language. For example, loops and decision points would enable the modeling of complex processes. These extensions would make it possible to model more sophisticated RPA processes that go beyond the current basic components. For this, a common basis for the various providers would then have to be found so that these new elements can be implemented independently from each platform.

Another aspect of future research is to extend the support of the prototype to other RPA software solutions. The current prototype was primarily developed for the RPA providers Blue Prism and UiPath. In the future, the prototype could also be adapted for other widely used platforms such as Automation Anywhere. Such an extension would further strengthen the platform independence of the prototype. Additionally, it would offer users more options to implement their RPA processes flexibly on different software.

A third aspect concerns the possibility of spying within the platform-independent RPA modeling language. In the future, it might be possible to implement this feature. However, it has already been pointed out that many RPA providers have little interest in integrating external spying solutions into their systems, as this could weaken their customer loyalty. However, further research in collaboration with these providers could provide a solution. Future work could explore a platform-independent spying method in cooperation with the RPA providers themselves. This could create a solution that allows spying to be done externally and then integrated into the specific RPA software. This could lead to more flexibility and independence, even though it conflicts with the interests of the providers.

Overall, these recommendations offer numerous potentials for future work to improve the modeling language, integrate additional technologies, and ensure further research for a platform-independent RPA solution.

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Appendix A

Examples

This chapter includes two complete examples of the prototype in action. The examples are structured as follows: First, an RPA process is modeled in ADOxx using the developed modeling language. This process model is then shown in the first figure. Then the Model is exported as an XML file, which is also displayed. After that, the created application is used to transform the XML file into a Blue Prism XML and a UiPath XAML file. These files are then pasted into the corresponding software. The first example includes a screenshot of the imported Process Model UiPath, and Blue Prism, followed by the XML code for each software. The other examples do not include only the screenshot of the process models in each software.

The first example is a short and simple standard process that can occur to anyone. It is kept short in order to show the XML code as well. Example 1 includes the process of creating a new account. Example 2 includes a more complex process. It includes the idea of repeating tasks. The process consists of extracting customer data out of a form in order to enter it into a company software. Here the XML code is not displayed as it would be very large and not bring any more insights.

Example 1

Figure A.1: Example 1 ADOxx Model

```

1 <ADOXML version="3.1" date="09.06.2024" time="16:08" database="adox18" username="
Admin" adoversion="Version 1.8">
2 <MODELS>
3 <MODEL id="mod.21006" name="Model 1" version="" modeltype="RPA">
4 <MODELATTRIBUTES>
5 </MODELATTRIBUTES>
6 <INSTANCE id="obj.31620" class="Start" name="Start-31620">
7 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:5.25cm y:2cm index:1</
ATTRIBUTE>
8 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
9 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:31620</ATTRIBUTE>
10 </INSTANCE>
11 <INSTANCE id="obj.31635" class="End" name="End-31635">
12 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:5.25cm y:17.5cm index:6</
ATTRIBUTE>
13 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
14 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:31635</ATTRIBUTE>
15 </INSTANCE>
16 <INSTANCE id="obj.33009" class="Write" name="Write Password">
17 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:5.25cm y:8.75cm index:3</
ATTRIBUTE>
18 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
19 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:33009</ATTRIBUTE>
20 <ATTRIBUTE name="Input" type="STRING">Password</ATTRIBUTE>
21 </INSTANCE>
22 <INSTANCE id="obj.33012" class="Read" name="Read confirmation">
23 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:5.25cm y:15cm index:5</
ATTRIBUTE>
24 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
25 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:33012</ATTRIBUTE>
26 </INSTANCE>
27 <INSTANCE id="obj.33015" class="Write" name="Write Email">
28 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:5.25cm y:6.75cm index:2</
ATTRIBUTE>
29 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
30 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:33015</ATTRIBUTE>
31 <ATTRIBUTE name="Input" type="STRING">Email@Email</ATTRIBUTE>
32 </INSTANCE>
33 <INSTANCE id="obj.33018" class="Navigate" name="Click Confirm">
34 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:5.25cm y:12.75cm index
:4</ATTRIBUTE>
35 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
36 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:33018</ATTRIBUTE>
37 <ATTRIBUTE name="Input" type="STRING"/>
38 </INSTANCE>
39 <INSTANCE id="obj.33025" class="Navigate" name="Click Create new Account">
40 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:5.25cm y:4.5cm index:10</
ATTRIBUTE>
41 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
42 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:33025</ATTRIBUTE>
43 <ATTRIBUTE name="Input" type="STRING"/>
44 </INSTANCE>
45 <INSTANCE id="obj.33028" class="Write" name="Write Confirm Password">
46 <ATTRIBUTE name="Position" type="STRING">NODE x:5.25cm y:10.75cm index
:11</ATTRIBUTE>
47 <ATTRIBUTE name="External tool coupling" type="STRING"/>
48 <ATTRIBUTE name="object-id" type="EXPRESSION">EXPR val:33028</ATTRIBUTE>

```

```

49     <ATTRIBUTE name="Input" type="STRING">Password</ATTRIBUTE>
50 </INSTANCE>
51 <CONNECTOR id="con.33021" class="Flow">
52     <FROM instance="Write Email" class="Write"/>
53     <TO instance="Write Password" class="Write"/>
54     <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:7</ATTRIBUTE>
55 </CONNECTOR>
56 <CONNECTOR id="con.33023" class="Flow">
57     <FROM instance="Read confirmation" class="Read"/>
58     <TO instance="End-31635" class="End"/>
59     <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:9</ATTRIBUTE>
60 </CONNECTOR>
61 <CONNECTOR id="con.33024" class="Flow">
62     <FROM instance="Click Confirm" class="Navigate"/>
63     <TO instance="Read confirmation" class="Read"/>
64     <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:8</ATTRIBUTE>
65 </CONNECTOR>
66 <CONNECTOR id="con.33031" class="Flow">
67     <FROM instance="Start-31620" class="Start"/>
68     <TO instance="Click Create new Account" class="Navigate"/>
69     <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:12</ATTRIBUTE>
70 </CONNECTOR>
71 <CONNECTOR id="con.33032" class="Flow">
72     <FROM instance="Click Create new Account" class="Navigate"/>
73     <TO instance="Write Email" class="Write"/>
74     <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:13</ATTRIBUTE>
75 </CONNECTOR>
76 <CONNECTOR id="con.33033" class="Flow">
77     <FROM instance="Write Password" class="Write"/>
78     <TO instance="Write Confirm Password" class="Write"/>
79     <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:14</ATTRIBUTE>
80 </CONNECTOR>
81 <CONNECTOR id="con.33034" class="Flow">
82     <FROM instance="Write Confirm Password" class="Write"/>
83     <TO instance="Click Confirm" class="Navigate"/>
84     <ATTRIBUTE name="Positions" type="STRING">EDGE 0 index:15</ATTRIBUTE>
85 </CONNECTOR>
86 </MODEL>
87 </MODELS>
88 </ADOXML>

```

A.1: Example 1 ADOxx XML

Figure A.2: Example 1 Blue Prism Model

```

1 <process name="__selection__Utility - Calculations" runmode="Exclusive" type="
  object">
2   <stage name="Start-31620" stageid="b999b5d2-9074-410c-8e56-80a6da454988" type="
    Start">
3     <display x="15" y="-90"/>
4     <onsuccess>a866ccd0-4d42-42f3-97b6-fa5f92653a0e</onsuccess>
5   </stage>
6   <stage name="End-31635" stageid="4bb40440-14ae-4615-b9c4-04ac796f0547" type="End
    ">
7     <display x="15" y="225"/>
8   </stage>
9   <stage name="Click Confirm" stageid="edea629f-313b-42b8-9ab2-a63ad805363e" type="
    Navigate">
10    <display x="15" y="135"/>
11    <onsuccess>8ac84c1c-66e6-40d8-be46-988a9f734741</onsuccess>
12  </stage>
13  <stage name="Click Create new Account" stageid="a866ccd0-4d42-42f3-97b6-
    fa5f92653a0e" type="Navigate">
14    <display x="15" y="-45"/>
15    <onsuccess>e23c1f78-8ec2-4825-ac62-9930663a938c</onsuccess>
16  </stage>
17  <stage name="Read confirmation" stageid="8ac84c1c-66e6-40d8-be46-988a9f734741"
    type="Read">
18    <display x="15" y="180"/>
19    <onsuccess>4bb40440-14ae-4615-b9c4-04ac796f0547</onsuccess>
20  </stage>
21  <stage name="Write Password" stageid="5b0afe27-7e0d-4574-b953-5b5d11346f56" type
    ="Write">
22    <display x="15" y="45"/>
23    <onsuccess>ccc14f0c-d1e6-40fd-9c7a-4c77af1b10ae</onsuccess>
24    <step expr="Password"/>
25  </stage>
26  <stage name="Write Email" stageid="e23c1f78-8ec2-4825-ac62-9930663a938c" type="
    Write">
27    <display x="15" y="0"/>
28    <onsuccess>5b0afe27-7e0d-4574-b953-5b5d11346f56</onsuccess>
29    <step expr="Email@Email"/>
30  </stage>
31  <stage name="Write Confirm Password" stageid="ccc14f0c-d1e6-40fd-9c7a-4
    c77af1b10ae" type="Write">
32    <display x="15" y="90"/>
33    <onsuccess>edea629f-313b-42b8-9ab2-a63ad805363e</onsuccess>
34    <step expr="Password"/>
35  </stage>
36 </process>

```

A.2: Example 1 Blue Prism XML

Figure A.3: Example 1 UiPath Model

```

1 <ClipboardData
2   xmlns="http://schemas.microsoft.com/netfx/2009/xaml/activities/presentation"
3   xmlns:sap2010="http://schemas.microsoft.com/netfx/2010/xaml/activities/
4     presentation"
5   xmlns:scg="clr-namespace:System.Collections.Generic;assembly=System.Private.
6     CoreLib"
7   xmlns:uix="http://schemas.uipath.com/workflow/activities/uix"
8   xmlns:x="http://schemas.microsoft.com/winfx/2006/xaml">
9   <ClipboardData.Data>
10    <scg:List Capacity="6" x:TypeArguments="x:Object">
11      <uix:NClick DisplayName="Click Create new Account" x:Name="__ReferenceID0"/>
12      <uix:NTypeInto ClickBeforeMode="Single" DisplayName="Write Email"
13        EmptyFieldMode="SingleLine" Text="Email@Email" x:Name="__ReferenceID1"/>
14      <uix:NTypeInto ClickBeforeMode="Single" DisplayName="Write Password"
15        EmptyFieldMode="SingleLine" Text="Password" x:Name="__ReferenceID2"/>
16      <uix:NTypeInto ClickBeforeMode="Single" DisplayName="Write Confirm Password"
17        EmptyFieldMode="SingleLine" Text="Password" x:Name="__ReferenceID3"/>
18      <uix:NClick DisplayName="Click Confirm" x:Name="__ReferenceID4"/>
19      <uix:NGetText DisplayName="Read confirmation" x:Name="__ReferenceID5"/>
20    </scg:List>
21  </ClipboardData.Data>
22  <ClipboardData.Metadata>
23    <scg:List Capacity="6" x:TypeArguments="x:Reference">
24      <x:Reference>__ReferenceID0</x:Reference>
25      <x:Reference>__ReferenceID1</x:Reference>
26      <x:Reference>__ReferenceID2</x:Reference>
27      <x:Reference>__ReferenceID3</x:Reference>
28      <x:Reference>__ReferenceID4</x:Reference>
29      <x:Reference>__ReferenceID5</x:Reference>
30    </scg:List>
31  </ClipboardData.Metadata>
32 </ClipboardData>

```

A.3: Example 1 UiPath XML

Example 2

This example includes the process of extracting data out of forms and writing this data into a company software. For the Blue Prism and UiPath model two screenshots are included. The left one is the model generated with the developed script. The right figure includes a loop that was manually inserted after the import of the model.

Figure A.4: Example 2 ADOxx Model

Figure A.5: Blue Prism Model

Figure A.6: Blue Prism Model with Loop

Figure A.7: UiPath Model

Figure A.8: UiPath Model with Loop

Appendix B

DOI

The prototype developed in this work was made available to readers on zenodo. The files can be accessed under the following DOI and URL:

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13961294

URL:

The following materials are provided:

- ADOxx modeling language
- Java files for the Blue Prism script
- Java files for the UiPath script
- Executable JAR-File that includes the developed Desktop Application combining both scripts

UNIVERSITÉ DE FRIBOURG
UNIVERSITÄT FREIBURG

Faculté des sciences économiques et sociales
Wirtschafts- und sozialwissenschaftliche Fakultät
Boulevard de Pérolles 90
CH-1700 Fribourg

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